

**CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND VALUE CO-CREATION:
A CASE OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland for the award of Doctoral in Business Administration

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July 2021

DECLARATION

I, Syed Muhammad Ali Shah, declare that this thesis, entitled ‘Customer engagement and value co-creation: A case of the textile industry in Pakistan’, contains no material that has been previously published or submitted for the award of any other degree or diploma, except where otherwise stated (References are attached).

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Personal details withheld.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Firstly, I would like to thank Allah for providing me with the strength and ability to finish this doctoral thesis successfully. I would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to my Director of Studies Dr Lucy Lu for her guidance and continued support throughout the research process.

I am grateful to Dr Shiraz Alam Malik for his suggestions and comments during the early stage of this research. I would also like to thank Dr Bronwyn Betts and Dr Mizan ur Rehman for their expert suggestions and guidance. I am also thankful to Dr Dipendra Bagale for providing suggestions on improving the structural and logical coherence of the thesis. I am extremely grateful to the examiners of my thesis, Dr Rajendra Kumar and Prof Ibrahim Sirkeci for their expert suggestions.

I appreciate the support provided by Lee Chun Lin, Jamil, Waqas, and Ali Raza as well as my fellow DBA researchers Tahir and Waseem at various stages of this research. Finally, I am extremely grateful to my parents for their continuous support, unwavering encouragements, and guidance. I am also thankful to other members of my family for being there whenever I needed their support.

ABSTRACT

Following the emergence of sophisticated modern technologies, marketplaces are becoming increasingly competitive globally. Brands are competing with each other in multiple ways for sustaining in the current competitive marketplace. Value co-creation is one of the key business practices that is becoming more and more common in the marketplace as, through value co-creation, brands are not only able to enhance customer satisfaction but also gather innovative ideas. Particularly in the textile industry, value co-creation practices have been adopted for a long time. Companies in western countries have been effectively utilising modern technology for engaging customers in value co-creation processes and many empirical studies have been conducted to assess the benefits of such engagements. However, a review of the existing literature indicated that no study was conducted in the Pakistani textile industry for assessing the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes as well as the role technology can play in facilitating such engagements; this study, therefore, investigates relationships between customer engagement and value co-creation attitude, advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation processes, and the roles modern technologies play in engaging customers in value co-creation processes.

This research followed a mixed-methods approach by combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. A total of 11 qualitative interviews and 332 quantitative questionnaire responses were collected for this research. Manual thematic analysis was used for the analysis of qualitative data whilst Chi-Square, ANOVA, and correlation tests were conducted for examining the relationships between different quantitative variables.

This research identified that customers that actively engaged with brands are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities. This research also identified that demographic factors such as age and gender significantly influence shoppers shopping frequencies. Additionally, five key advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes, namely meeting customers demand through product customisation and personalisation, developing better relationships with customers, innovation leading to competitive advantages, enhanced customer experience resulting in customer loyalty, and increased revenue collection were identified along with two challenges associated with engaging customers in value co-creation processes, namely damage in reputation due to inconsistencies in products/services offered and value destruction as a consequence of negative feedback from customers. Finally, this research also revealed that modern technologies immensely benefit the value co-creation processes by helping businesses to reach a wider range of audiences, providing digital marketing and electronic word of mouth opportunities, and offering enhanced support systems to customers. These findings make significant contributions to the literature by bridging the existing knowledge gaps.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION.....	II
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	III
ABSTRACT.....	IV
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	V
TABLES AND FIGURES.....	IX
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	X
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. RESEARCH BACKGROUND	1
1.1.1. THE CONCEPT OF VALUE CO-CREATION.....	3
1.1.2. IMPORTANCE VALUE CO-CREATION.....	4
1.1.3. DISTINGUISHING CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND VALUE CO-CREATION	6
1.2. RESEARCH PROBLEMS.....	7
1.3. RESEARCH AIM, OBJECTIVES, AND QUESTIONS	9
1.3.1. AIM OF THE RESEARCH.....	9
1.3.2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES.....	9
1.3.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS	10
1.4. RATIONALE	10
1.5. THE METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH.....	12
1.6. STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS.....	13
1.7. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS.....	14
1.8. CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE KNOWLEDGE	15
1.9. SUMMARY	16
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	18
2.1. INTRODUCTION	18
2.2. VALUE CREATION	19
2.2.1. THE CONCEPT OF VALUE.....	19
2.2.2. IMPORTANCE OF VALUE CREATION TO BUSINESSES	20
2.3. VALUE CO-CREATION	21
2.3.1. GOODS DOMINANT LOGIC.....	23
2.3.2. SERVICE-DOMINANT LOGIC	24
2.3.3. DISINCLINATIONS BETWEEN GOODS DOMINANT LOGIC AND SERVICE-DOMINANT LOGIC	26

2.3.4.	SERVICE LOGIC.....	27
2.3.5.	VALUE CO-CREATION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY	30
2.3.6.	VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDE	31
2.4.	CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT	34
2.4.1.	TYPES OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT	36
2.4.2.	ROLES OF CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE IN CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT	38
2.4.3.	OUTCOMES OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT.....	39
2.4.4.	MEASURING CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT	41
2.5.	CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND VALUE CO-CREATION	44
2.5.1.	RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND THEIR VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES	46
2.5.2.	ADVANTAGES OF ENGAGING CUSTOMERS IN VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES	47
2.5.3.	RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH ENGAGING CUSTOMERS IN VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES	49
2.5.4.	ROLES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES ON CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND VALUE CO-CREATION	51
2.6.	AN OVERVIEW OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY	52
2.6.1.	INTRODUCTION.....	52
2.6.2.	TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN	54
2.6.3.	CHALLENGES FACED BY THE PAKISTANI TEXTILE INDUSTRY	57
2.6.4.	KEY PLAYERS IN THE CLOTHING RETAIL SECTOR OF PAKISTAN.....	58
2.6.4.2.	CHALLENGES FACED BY TEXTILE RETAILERS IN PAKISTAN	60
2.6.5.	VALUE CO-CREATION AND CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT IN THE PAKISTANI TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	62
2.7.	CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES	63
2.8.	CONCLUSIONS	68
3.	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	70
3.1.	INTRODUCTION	70
3.2.	RESEARCH AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	70
3.3.	RESEARCH PHILOSOPHIES	71
3.3.1.	PHILOSOPHICAL ASSUMPTIONS.....	71
3.3.2.	PHILOSOPHICAL STANCES	72
3.4.	RESEARCH APPROACH	77
3.4.1.	INDUCTIVE APPROACH	77
3.4.2.	DEDUCTIVE APPROACH	77
3.4.3.	ABDUCTIVE APPROACH	78
3.4.4.	SELECTED APPROACH AND JUSTIFICATIONS.....	78
3.5.	RESEARCH STRATEGY.....	79
3.5.1.	SURVEY	79
3.5.2.	CASE STUDY	80
3.5.3.	ETHNOGRAPHY	80
3.5.4.	SELECTED RESEARCH STRATEGY AND JUSTIFICATIONS	80
3.6.	RESEARCH METHODS	81
3.6.1.	QUALITATIVE METHOD	81
3.6.2.	QUANTITATIVE METHOD	82
3.6.3.	MIXED METHODS	83
3.6.4.	SELECTED RESEARCH METHOD AND JUSTIFICATIONS.....	84

3.7. PILOT STUDY	86
3.8. DATA COLLECTION	86
3.8.1. SAMPLING METHODS	86
3.8.2. SELECTED SAMPLE SIZE AND JUSTIFICATIONS	88
3.9. DATA ANALYSIS	89
3.9.1. QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS	89
3.9.2. QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS	89
3.10. VALIDITY	92
3.11. RELIABILITY	93
3.12. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	93
3.13. CONCLUSIONS.....	94
<u>4. DATA ANALYSES AND FINDINGS</u>	<u>96</u>
4.1. INTRODUCTION	96
4.2. QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS.....	96
4.2.1. PILOT STUDY	96
4.2.2. MAIN DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS	98
4.2.3. DESCRIPTIVE FINDINGS.....	100
4.2.4. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESEARCH VARIABLES.....	104
4.2.5. INFERENCE ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS	105
4.2.6. HYPOTHESES TESTING	106
4.3. QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS	123
4.3.1. PILOT STUDY	123
4.3.2. QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION PROCESS	123
4.3.3. QUALITATIVE FINDINGS	125
4.4. CONCLUSIONS	138
<u>5. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS.....</u>	<u>140</u>
5.1. INTRODUCTION	140
5.2. RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND VALUE CO-CREATION.....	140
5.2.1. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS	140
5.2.2. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	141
5.2.3. EVALUATION OF THE FINDINGS	147
5.3. ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF ENGAGING CUSTOMERS IN VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES.....	148
5.3.1. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS	148
5.3.2. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	149
5.3.3. EVALUATIONS OF THE FINDINGS	154
5.4. THE ROLES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES ON VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES	154
5.4.1. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS	154
5.4.2. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	155
5.4.3. EVALUATIONS OF THE FINDINGS	158
5.5. CONCLUSIONS	159

6.	<u>CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS</u>	160
6.1.	INTRODUCTION	160
6.2.	SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH	160
6.3.	ACHIEVING RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES	163
6.3.1.	OBJECTIVE ONE	163
6.3.2.	OBJECTIVE TWO	164
6.3.3.	OBJECTIVE THREE	164
6.4.	CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE RESEARCH	165
6.4.1.	THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS	165
6.4.2.	PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTIONS	167
6.5.	RECOMMENDATIONS	169
6.6.	LIMITATIONS	171
6.7.	FURTHER RESEARCH	172
6.8.	CONCLUSIONS	172
7.	<u>REFERENCES</u>	173
8.	<u>APPENDICES</u>	211

TABLES AND FIGURES

Tables

Table 2-1: Conceptual Framework.....	67
Table 3-1: Qualitative Vs Quantitative	83
Table 4-1: Reliability Analysis of the Pilot Survey	97
Table 4-2: Reliability Analysis of the main Survey.....	99
Table 4-3: Gender	100
Table 4-4: Age	100
Table 4-5: Income.....	101
Table 4-6: Education.....	102
Table 4-7: Professions	102
Table 4-8: Favourite Brands	103
Table 4-9: Shopping Frequency.....	104
Table 4-10: Descriptive Findings of Research Variables	105
Table 4-11: Research Hypotheses.....	107
Table 4-12: the relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes ..	108
Table 4-13: the relationship between respondents age and their shopping frequency	110
Table 4-14: the relationship between respondents' gender and their shopping frequency	112
Table 4-15: the relationship between respondents' income and their shopping frequency	114
Table 4-16: Consumers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across income categories	116
Table 4-17: Consumers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across age categories	117
Table 4-18: Consumers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across gender categories.....	119
Table 4-19: Consumers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across professional categories	120
Table 4-20: Consumers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across education categories	122
Table 4-21: Profile of the Respondents.....	125

Figures

Figure 2-1: SDL Value co-creation Process	25
Figure 2-2: The Value Co-creation Process.....	28
Figure 3-1: Thematic Analysis Process	90
Figure 5-1: Advantages and Challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes	149
Figure 5-2: The roles of modern technologies in value co-creation processes	155

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Meanings
SD	Service Dominant
SDL	Service Dominant Logic
GDL	Goods Dominant Logic
SL	Service Logic
CPB	Customer Participation Behaviour
SNS	Social Network Sites
WOM	Word of Mouth
eWom	Electronic Word of Mouth
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CVCCA	Customer Value Co-Creation Attitude
CE	Customer Engagement
MSI	Marketing Science Institute
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
PCGA	Pakistan Cotton Ginning Association
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

Pakistan is one of the fastest-growing economies with gross domestic products (GDP) equivalent to 305 billion US dollars (World Bank, 2018). The country's GDP is expected to continue to grow and become the fourth-largest economy by 2030 (HSBC, 2018). Emerging countries roughly will account for 50% of the world economy by then, representing a seismic shift from half that in the year 2000 to have painted a picture. Another statistic pictures the world economic output as going to be doubled by 2050 (PWC, 2017), in which it is clear that economies such as that of Pakistan will even play a more significant role. One of the industries in Pakistan that have been continuously performing well at the national scale is the textile industry, which is contributing significantly to the economic growth by employing around 30% of the working population in Pakistan (Dawn, 2018). The textile industry in Pakistan is the largest manufacturing industry in the country in terms of employment and export revenues (The Nation, 2018).

Following the growth of technology and easier access to it, Pakistan is undergoing a substantial digital transformation, allowing for brands to reach and engage with customers who may have previously been overlooked (Google, 2018). The country domestically too has a large population online as a result of the declining smartphone prices and discounted data bundles that according to Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) adds up to about 59 million smartphones (PTA, 2018). From Instagram to Facebook to the use of popular hashtags, textile brands in Pakistan are now consciously using social media in creative ways to draw in their audience and engage with them (Dawn, 2016). Consumer involvement and engagement towards their brand is highly chased by the firms (Hollebeek, 2011). Such two-way communications can result in value co-creation involving the producers and consumers through which the sector shall thrive.

In the modern marketplace, firm and customer involvement is considered as a strategic resource for attaining higher quality level, cost leadership, quick delivery and satisfactory service (Mostafa, 2016). Vargo (2009) states that the marketing field is transforming to a

newer logic which is service-based, essentially based on interactions and co-creation of value, networked focused and, therefore fundamentally interactive. Surpassing prior formulation of associations, Service-Dominant (SDL) Logic contends that dealings of services and products appear at one occasion, associations relating to the participants are visible in the shared, communicating, cooperative, revealing and shared functions the people play in the network, in an ongoing value co-creation process (Vivek et al., 2014).

SDL is the central theory that describes value co-creation involving firms and consumers by putting value at the centre of study consideration (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). Vargo and Lusch (2004, 2008) articulated two initial ideas value is always co-created and “all social and economic actors are resource integrators” sense towards the progressively collaborative and interconnected, description of value creation (Vargo & Lusch, 2011). Liang (2017) states that “value co-creation” is the fundamental idea of SD logic, which requires an integration of resources sought through mutual exchanges and shared institutions, active participation of the customer in service creation. SDL underlines the customer character as lively in the process of value co-creation (Kohtamaki and Rajala, 2016). Also, an interesting phenomenon presented by Vargo & Lusch (2008) and Vargo & Lusch (2016) based on SDL is that the receiver uniquely determines the value always. On the other hand, Gronroos (2006, 2008) is of the view that customers create value, and if firms adopt service logic and establish communications between the suppliers and the consumers, value is co-created. The assumption is made in service logic that a customer will utilise all resources available to create value (Gronroos, 2019). Service providers and marketers should provide resources for customers to facilitate value co-creation (Gronroos, 2019).

Companies and customers engagement lead to value being co-created through interaction (Gronroos 2008, 2011). The interaction and utilisation of resources to benefit mutually refer to value co-creation (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). The formation of value now advances from a collaborative production process including the firm and the consumers (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004a; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004b). Co-creation of value is not achievable unless the customers permit the firm to interact (Grönroos et al. 2015). Therefore, the attitude of customers regarding interaction with the company to co-create value is vital (Salman et al., 2014). Gambetti et al. (2012) propose that as brands and customers co-create value through engagement and acquire deeper, more entrenched associations, they cultivate higher degrees of attraction, closeness, shared pledge, and equal conviction.

The label of engagement has been presented to describe clearly customers interactional brand associated actions. In contrast to conventional constructs comprising ‘participation’ and ‘involvement’, customer engagement has been proposed to reveal the characteristics of customer relationships with brands more meticulously (Poorrezaei, 2016). Bazi et al. (2019) state it as a multidimensional construct. Van Doorn et al. (2010) defined it as a consumer behavioural demonstration for a brand or towards a firm, beyond purchases as a result of motivational drivers. Over the last three decades, research surrounding the relationships of customer and brand has earned considerable interest from researchers (Brodie and Hollebeek, 2011; Hollebeek et al., 2014). Specifically, an influential study route has developed to investigate the new prospects of associations that have been facilitated with the progression of different technologies including the internet (Hollebeek et al., 2014). Three aspects of the concept of customer engagement have been presented by Vivek et al. (2014), comprising of conscious attention, social connection and enthused participation. Hollebeek et al. (2014) stated that customer engagement includes three factors, i.e. affection, activation and cognitive processing. Dessart et al. (2015) also categorised three engagement features, including, affect, behaviour and cognition, for engagement of customers by brands in an online setting. Marino and Presti (2018) reflected the three attributes of customer engagement existed as social connection, enthused participation and conscious attention.

1.1.1. The concept of value co-creation

The co-creation of value is becoming a more prominent theme in literature (Kohtamaki and Rajala, 2016). The “co-creation” label has flourished over the past decade (Ramaswamy and Ozcan, 2018). Current advancements in the marketing theory are designed about the idea of value co-creation (Laamanen & Skalen, 2014). Jaakkola and Alexander (2014), emphasise that the customer and firm relationships are shared activities encompassing cautious administration of the individual interactions amongst the exchange partners.

Haro et al. (2014) suggested that “co-creation” denotes any action in which the customer takes part in a functioning and direct mode with the firm in designing and developing new services, products, or processes. Scholars define value co-creation as a moment of exchange during which service providers and customers perceive that potential benefits might overcome the incurred costs (Lusch and Vargo, 2014; Payne et al., 2008). The interaction with and utilisation of resources for reciprocal gain denotes value co-creation (Vargo and

Lusch, 2008). The formation of value now results from a collaborative production practice comprising both the customer and the company (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

1.1.2. Importance value co-creation

The technological advancement, related to globalisation, shifts in purchasing behaviours, and customers transformed actions, have caused difficulty for the firms in distinguishing themselves from rivals. This novel economic and social structure requires reorganising the function of marketing in the value creation process (Kotler et al., 2010). As a consequence of this change, firms must focus less on enhancing their interior competence and rather pursue developing exterior resources in their exploration for value co-creation with a customer (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004b). In the consequential individualised interactions, the firm and the customer roles unite, both participants become collaborators and competitors concurrently – associates in the formation of value and rivals for the economic value subtraction (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004a).

Distinct from the conventional process of value creation, in which interaction pushed exclusively from the firm to the consumer, communication between firms and consumers progressively involve constant discourses, in which both partners are functional and involved in the process of learning (Ballantyne, 2004), so they co-create mutual value for both partners (Grönroos, 2008). If these communications facilitate customers to co-create distinctive experiences, firms likely appreciate a brand-new competitive advantage, which clarifies why the value must be created mutually (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004a). Which is, the co-creation of value is a required objective for both firms and customers, to assist firms to realise the requirements and inclinations of customers (Lusch and Vargo, 2006). It also assists decision making and swift learning by the dedicated business, because the experiences of customers signify resourceful ways to create value (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004a).

Technology and social media give contemporary customers entrance to massive sums of content and information, they believe more capable to exercise control and are keen to contribute significantly in the process of value creation (Ernst et al., 2010). Which is, customers have turned out to be dynamic co-creators of the services and products they purchase and utilise (O'Hern and Rindfleisch, 2010), and they create value via propositions that are co-produced and customised with the firm (Payne et al., 2008). In this new value-creation procedure, firms cannot consider customers as submissive receiver of value, to

which they distribute goods, experiences and services (Ramaswamy, 2009). Alternatively, users and customers now form the foundation of any enterprise and perform various functions in innovative processes that create value (Edvarsson et al., 2010). A firm's main objective is the customisation of offerings and achieving full involvement by customers in this process of customisation, to better match customer needs (Vargo and Lusch, 2004a).

Firms must realise the customers constantly evolving experiences outside of personalised communication incidents, alongside their pursuits with other participants in the facilitation of value co-creation (Heinonen et al., 2010). The significance of emotions was brought forward by Addis and Holbrook (2001) and, they defined the function of sentiments in behaviour; customers feel also think and achieve; the role of customers, outside of the action of buying, in the utilisation of the product in addition to the choice of brand. Chen (2018) states that once customers feel that the opinion they gave is being acknowledged by the company it results in value co-creation; the sentiment that they helped in the improvement of service encourages the engagement of customers and interaction in the online channels, eventually producing value for the customer. Perera et al. (2017) are of the view that the producer in the value co-creation process is genuinely concerned toward consumers to demand and tries to fulfil it.

Enhancing value co-creation interactions leads to two possible outcomes for the customers: (1) reduction in operating expenses, risk, and insecurity, and (2) it lowers the charges of the interaction for the customer (Rajah et al. 2008), which results in trust with and higher satisfaction in the firm (Vandenbosch and Dawer, 2002). It produces, personalised and custom made products, in comparison with regular commodities (Franke et al., 2009), produce higher value and enhance consumer satisfaction (Franke and von Hippel, 2003). The customer satisfaction level is dependent on customer experiences during the process of co-creation. If customers voluntarily take part and appreciate the process, they will develop a positive attitude, leading to enhanced satisfaction (Hoyer et al., 2010). Customers sense higher value from their involvement if they truly appreciate it (Franke and Schreier, 2010), therefore customers are inclined to disburse more for the products/services they have designed than for the conventional commodities (Franke and Piller, 2004).

Besides accumulating internal gains, external influences on firms rise from co-creation, such as effects on a firm's image and reputation. The firm offers a product or service, which is

being utilised, adjusted, and debated by the customers (Ind et al., 2012). Furthermore, relational interactions among customers are facilitated through co-creation, via technological platforms and online tools that allow them to access the information produced by other customers. Therefore, customers focus more on the brand, which must multiply the number of positive conversations about the brand and its offerings, alongside the identification of customers with these offerings and brands (Roser et al., 2009).

1.1.3. Distinguishing Customer Engagement and Value co-creation

The concept of consumer engagement is widely discussed in the literature for several decades (i.e., Van Doorn et al., 2010; Imtiaz et al., 2019); Hollebeek, 2011; Hollebeek et al., 2014), whereas value co-creation is an emerging concept that is receiving increased attention from academics in the recent decades (i.e., Alexander, 2012; Galvagno and Dalli, 2014; Laamanen & Skalen, 2015). Although the concepts of customer engagement and value co-creation appear closely linked on the surface, there are considerable differences between these areas; hence, these phenomena have grown as independent areas of investigation.

Customer engagement is a customer's behavioural manifestations that have a brand or firm focus, beyond purchase, resulting from motivational drivers (Van Doorn et al., 2010). It is an emotional connection between the firm and the customer on the basis of communication and contribution (Imtiaz et al., 2019). Furthermore, Hollebeek (2011) and Hollebeek et al. (2014) extend the explanation of engagement with the conception of an interactional association; they describe engagement as a reciprocal communication between the customer and the brand. Kumar et al., (2016) identify customer engagement as the mechanisms through which customers help create value for a firm by contributing directly or indirectly. The direct contribution here refers to the purchases done by the consumers and their consequent recommendations (Kumar et al., 2010). Whereas, the indirect contribution results from their referrals to other customers, which potentially leads to new feedback and suggestions, as well as taking part in social media conversations for reviewing a product or service that also reveal insights (Kumar, 2013). Seifert and Kwon (2018) further reiterate this and conclude that customers can bring special values to a firm by offering feedbacks for improvement and advocating the company to others. Roncha and Radclyffe-Thomas (2016) also emphasise that when customers are involved, it will result in the generation of new products/service ideas.

On the other hand, value co-creation is defined by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004b) as a joint creation of value by the customer and the firm; customers can have active dialogue and develop personalised experiences jointly by cultivating an experience environment. Lusch and Nambisan (2015) describe value co-creation as activities that cause resource integration and incorporate different actor roles in the service ecosystem. Nysveen and Pederson (2013) state that co-creation is regarded as a joint or a collaborative activity comprising both consumers and producers for the purpose of creating value. Similarly, according to Alexander (2012), value co-creation is a situation where value is created mutually and reciprocally by a firm, where the consequential value-in-use is superior to that of its constituent parts. Customers and company create value through interaction and co-creation is evolving as a new paradigm in the management literature (Galvagno and Dalli, 2014). Value co-creation is now becoming a dominant area of marketing research and current advances in marketing theory revolve around the idea of value co-creation (Laamanen & Skalen, 2015). Vargo and Lusch (2004) state that the customers are not submissive participants but are active value creators, operating as integrators of resources and adding to value creation through the integration of social, cultural and physical resources. From the perspective of co-creation, customers and service providers are not anymore on opposite sides as interactions take place between both parties to develop new business prospects (Galvagno and Dalli, 2014).

1.2. Research Problems

A review of the literature identified three key research problems in the area of this research.

- The concept of value co-creation and its benefits are not widely understood by the practitioners in the Pakistani textile industry.

The concept of value co-creation is well-established in the West with many brands such as Nike, Lego, Starbucks, BMW, and DHL (Gilliland, 2018; Crandell, 2016) already involving consumers in the process of designing new products. Companies in the West have been able to benefit tremendously through customer engagement in these processes as they have been able to incorporate the ideas and requirements of the customers in new product and service development processes, eventually being able to innovate efficiently (Crandell, 2016). In the context of the textile industry in Pakistan, although there exists some form of customer engagement in the new product design process, such involvement is limited. In most cases,

many customers are unaware that these co-creation related services exist in the industry. Value co-creation is not only restricted to the service or sales interaction, but customers can also suggest new designs for clothes (Gouillart, 2012). Given that value creation through customer engagement is proven to be a successful approach in the west, Pakistani textile companies can also benefit tremendously by engaging customers in such processes. Benefits could include increased customer loyalty and profitability through increased customer satisfaction and revenues. However, a review of the literature indicated that no prior study was conducted in the Pakistani textile industry to provide guidance to the practitioners on how consumer participations in value co-creation activities can be enhanced. It is expected that this study will address this problem and provide clear guidance to practitioners in the industry, ultimately encouraging companies to implement value co-creation initiatives.

- Prior studies do not comprehensively theorise the customers' attitudes towards value co-creation.

An extensive review of the literature revealed that no prior empirical study comprehensively addressed all key aspects of value co-creation. Rather, prior studies focused merely on some distinctive features of value co-creation (i.e., commitment or role of customers in the “co-creation” process (Hoyer et al., 2010; Bogers et al., 2010), internet and social media role in the “co-creation” process (Fuller et al., 2009; Hoyer et al., 2010), a typology of “co-creation” (O'Hern and Rindfleisch, 2010; Piller et al., 2012), customers motivations to “co-create” (Xia and Suri, 2014), or “co-creation” as an engine of innovation and new product development (Westerlund and Leminen, 2011; Orcik et al., 2013). However, Laamanen & Skalen (2014) argues that, while theorizing the concept of value co-creation, all dimensions must include personal and joint as well as conflictual facets of value co-creation. Therefore, this study takes a comprehensive approach by studying all key dimensions of value co-creation in order to address an existing research problem.

- The roles modern technologies play in value co-creation processes are not previously explored in the Pakistani textile industry

Modern technologies have been playing a substantial role in determining how businesses interact with their consumers (Ahmad et al., 2015). In the current digital marketplace, brands are extensively utilising social media channels for gathering consumer ideas as well as

engaging them in the process of value co-creation (Nasir et al., 2018). In order to be able to develop effective strategies for engaging customers in value co-creation processes, it is essential to understand how modern technologies can be useful. However, an extensive review of the literature suggested that no prior study was conducted to explore how modern technologies can be used for engaging consumers in value co-creation processes; thus, leaving a gap in the literature. Firms globally are utilising more and more technologies to interact with consumers following the changes brought by the Covid-19 pandemic. This study, therefore, attempts to address this research problem by highlighting how modern technologies can be effectively used for enhancing consumer participation in value co-creation processes.

1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

1.3.1. Aim of the Research

This research aims to recommend strategies for enhancing the level of customer engagement in value co-creation processes in the textile industry of Pakistan.

The above research aim will be achieved by investigating the relationships between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes, exploring the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation processes, and identifying the roles modern technologies play in engaging customers in value co-creation processes.

1.3.2. Research Objectives

To systematically achieve the aim above, the following five research objectives are outlined:

Objective 1: To assess the impacts of customer engagement on their value co-creation attitudes in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

Objective 2: To evaluate the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation processes in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

Objective 3: To assess the roles of modern technologies in engaging customers in value co-creation processes in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

Objective 4: To recommend strategies for engaging customers in value co-creation practices for increasing profitability and enhancing organisational sustainability in the textile industry in Pakistan.

1.3.3. Research Questions

The following research questions are developed for achieving the above objectives:

RQ1: What kind of impacts, if any, customer engagement has on customers' value co-creation attitudes in the textile industry in Pakistan?

RQ2: What are the key advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process in the textile industry in Pakistan?

RQ3: What kind of roles do modern technologies play in engaging customers in value co-creation processes in the textile industry in Pakistan?

RQ4: What kind of strategies can be proposed for increasing the engagement of customers in value co-creation processes?

1.4. Rationale

Various researchers have studied the concepts of customer engagement and value co-creation in different research contexts; for example, Hollebeek et al. (2014) established a customer brand engagement scale in explicit social media; Dessart et al. (2016) conducted research on conceptualisation and operationalization of customer engagement in the context of online brand communities, and social media-facilitated customer-brand relationships were examined by Halaszovich and Nelc (2017). Furthermore, Gong (2018) focused on consumer brand engagement behaviour in online communities; antecedent and consequences of value co-creation behaviours, participation (CPB), and customer citizenship (CCB) behaviour were investigated by Frasset-Deltoro (2019). Seifert and Kwon (2019) discussed (SNS)-based brand-related electronic word-of-mouths (eWOMs) influences customer engagement in brand value co-creation and brand trust change. And last but not least, Bazi et al. (2019) investigated the rules of brand engagement and intention of co-creation in social commerce. However, no study investigated whether increased customer engagement with brands leads to their enhanced participation in value co-creation activities, precisely in the context of the textile sector. This study, therefore, is considered relevant to bridge the knowledge gap that currently exists in the literature.

Engaging customers in value co-creation processes brings numerous advantages for companies. Alexander (2012) asserts the firms that engage customers in co-creation processes acquire unique competitive knowledge regarding the marketplace – such insights are not instantly available to competitors. Through co-creation activities, companies generate information that helps to meet customers' needs and produce ideas to design and manufacture (Jaworski & Kohli, 2006) together with enhancements to customer experience (Ramaswamy, 2011). Co-creation activities can help a company in terms of loyalty gains as customers develop a bond with the company and attachment towards the firms (Jaworski and Kohli, 2006). The adoption of value co-creation practices in the textile industry of Pakistan is extremely low to non-existent. Given that such practices can bring numerous benefits to firms, the finding of this study is expected to contribute towards the success of the industry by making effective recommendations and encouraging businesses to incorporate value co-creation practices in their daily business activities.

In a competitive marketplace, attempts are made by brands to bring the most creative designs and products. Brand consciousness due to the influence of television and social media is shifting the mindsets of the customers. Customers are not only conscious about brands but mostly youth prefer to buy and compare products online. E-commerce operations are playing an integral part in Pakistan's fashion industry and there are an estimated 16.648 million fans on the e-commerce platform of different online sections of brands (Arifeen, 2017). Pakistan has over 40 high-end fashion brands and they generate billions of rupees of yearly revenues (Iris, 2016). Over the last decade, the clothing industry in Pakistan has grown significantly and a growing segment of consumers are using branded clothes and following new trends (Cruz, 2019). Online social network platforms have made brands more accessible to consumers (Abrar et al., 2020) and with the help of social media, customers are empowered to co-create novel services in partnership with the service firm by interacting through platforms like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter (Kaur, 2016). This shows the potential of engaging customers electronically in the value co-creation process leading to better design ideas, enhancing product quality, and better customer experience. Pakistani textile brands need to adopt strategies that make them more open and proactive in terms of changing the needs of customers while adopting new technologies. An extensive review of the literature revealed that no prior study was conducted precisely in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan to assess how technologies can facilitate enhanced participation of customers in value co-creation activities.

This study is also relevant because the textile industry globally is rapidly transforming following the emergence of modern technologies that facilitate smoother communications between brands and consumers. In order to sustain in such a rapidly transforming marketplace, companies must engage customers in both product and service development as well as delivery processes. Although companies in the western world have already been using the practices of value co-creation (engaging customers in the process of service/product development), textile companies in Pakistan appear to be lagging far behind their western counterparts. This study investigates not only the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes but also study how modern technologies can facilitate such engagements more efficiently. The findings of this study will provide significant guidance to the practitioners in the Pakistani textile industry in order to be able to innovate by incorporating the requirements and ideas of customers in product/service development processes.

The selection of the current research topic and context for the purpose of this thesis is closely linked with the researchers' past work experience in the Pakistani textile industry as well as his future career aspirations. The researcher previously worked in the Pakistani textile industry for five years in a managerial position and designed multiple marketing campaigns as a marketing manager. The researcher actively involved in the area of brand building and ongoing market research. This experience allowed the researchers to have an insider perspective of the industry, eventually allowing him to better interpret the collected research data. In the future, the researcher hopes to apply the learning of this research in the Pakistani textile industry. With an enhanced theoretical understanding of various marketing-related issues, the researcher will be able to develop more effective marketing strategies. Another reason for selecting the Pakistani textile industry as the context of the research was due to the researcher having a great network within the industry. With the help of network developed during the past career, it is anticipated that the researcher can access the research participants more easily and have an effective and efficient data collection process.

1.5. The Methodology of the Research

In order to achieve the above-mentioned research objectives and to be able to make practical recommendations to the practitioners in the Pakistani textile industry, a pragmatic research philosophy is selected for this research. A pragmatist researcher values the practical

relevance of research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Mixed-methods research that combines both quantitative and qualitative methods is identified as the best fit for identifying emerging insights as well as revealing findings that can be generalisable. A survey strategy is considered as the appropriate research strategy as it allows to collect the primary data from both customers and managers in the textile industry in Pakistan.

As a part of this research, a total of 11 qualitative interviews were conducted with the managers in the Pakistani textile industry whilst a total of 550 questionnaires were distributed among customers in the industry. The qualitative research focused mainly on evaluating the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes whilst the quantitative research focused on identifying whether or not increased customer engagement leads to higher customer participation in value co-creation activities. In order to analyse the quantitative data, SPSS software is used whilst manual thematic analysis is used for the analysis of qualitative research data.

1.6. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis contains six chapters.

Chapter One comprised of research background, stated research problem and aim, set objectives and provided a rationale for the research, description of the chosen research methods given, and stated research limitations alongside its scope.

Chapter Two deals with the review of the existing literature. This chapter addresses the various theoretical aspects of this research. Relevant theories and concepts such as GDL, SDL, SL, Value co-creation and customer engagement are reviewed. After an analysis of the literature, a new framework regarding the relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation attitude is conceptualised in this chapter. Research hypotheses are also outlined in this chapter.

Chapter Three offers justifications regarding chosen research philosophy, approach and research method after critically evaluating philosophies, approaches and research methods. Procedures followed during data collection, scale purification and data analyses are also discussed. This chapter also reviews different data collection processes and challenges related to them.

Chapter Four highlights and provides an explanation for the strategies adopted for data collection and analysis. Various methods including pilot interviews, qualitative interviews, pilot questionnaire survey and its analysis, main questionnaire development are dealt with in this chapter. To statistically tests the research hypotheses established in chapter two, Chi-square tests, and correlation tests are used.

Chapter Five examines the findings of the research and a comparison is provided with the evidence available in the literature. Research objectives are separately and systematically discussed in this chapter alongside their expected results and actual results. Contributions made to the body of knowledge based on the findings of the research are highlighted.

The final chapter of the current research is concerned with the summary and main conclusions, contribution to the knowledge and practice as well as recommendations. Then this chapter describes the limitations of the current research and recommendations for further study.

1.7. Scope and Limitations

This research aims to identify the relationship between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitude in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan. Customer engagement and value co-creation processes are evaluated in this research. Participants of the study are customers of clothing brands in Pakistan and are aged 18 or over.

The current research could be affected by the following limitations:

- Lack of generalisability of the findings: the research is conducted specifically on customers and firms in the textile industry of Pakistan, comprising of few companies. Findings may not be applicable to the textile sectors in other countries.
- Electronic data collection: Considering the implications of COVID-19, most of the participants were recruited through electronic channels. This may have resulted in participant bias.
- Lack of prior studies: After an extensive literature review on the topic revealed that no prior study concerning value co-creation was conducted in the Pakistani textile industry. This may have limited the opportunities related to developing robust questionnaires for data collection.

1.8. Contributions to the Knowledge

The research is expected to make the following contributions to the knowledge:

- Revealing the advantages and challenges of engaging consumers in value co-creation processes from the managers' perspectives.

Previous literature has highlighted both the advantages and challenges of engaging consumers in value co-creation processes. For example, Zhang and Chen (2008) state that firms can attain competitive advantages through personalisation and by engaging customers to co-create value. Through co-creation activities, companies generate information that helps to meet customers' needs and produce ideas to design and manufacture (Jaworski & Kohli, 2006; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Value co-creation can help a company in terms of consumer loyalty as customers develop a bond with the company and attachment towards the firms (Jaworski and Kohli, 2006). On the other hand, if a company cannot fulfil the promises made to customers, the customers can promote negative word-of-mouth, which damages the brand's image (Zhang and Chen, 2008). Angry customers may post negative comments about organizations/brands online (Zhang et al. 2018), eventually doing more bad to organisations than good. All of the above studies were conducted from consumer perspectives. This research aims to contribute to the body of knowledge by investigating the opportunities and challenges of engaging consumers in value co-creation processes from a managerial perspective.

- Identifying statistical associations between consumer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes in the context of the Pakistani textile industry.

Various prior studies conducted on value co-creation and customer engagement in different industries identified positive and significant statistical associations between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes. Research conducted by Oyner and Korelina (2016) on the Russian hospitality industry identified a positive association between customer engagement and value co-creation. Harrigan et al. (2020) examined the relationship between value co-creation and customer brand engagement on social media and identified that value co-creation positively affects customer brand engagement behaviours. Furthermore, Rosenthal et al. (2017) identified that value co-creation will enhance attachment with the brand. However, no prior study was conducted particularly in the context of the Pakistani

textile industry, hence there remains a knowledge void. The findings of this research is expected to bridge the existing knowledge void by making significant contributions to the literature.

- Providing contextualised strategic recommendations to the businesses in the Pakistani textile industry for enhancing consumer participation in value co-creation initiatives.

As aforementioned, numerous studies were conducted globally to understand how consumers can be better engaged in value co-creation initiatives. However, in the context of the Pakistani textile industry, no comprehensive study was previously done. This research aims to make strategic recommendations after critically assessing the relationship between consumer engagement and consumers' value co-creation attitudes, exploring the opportunities and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes, and assessing the roles of modern technologies in facilitating such engagements. Based on the finding of this research, it is expected that the researcher will be able to make contextualised strategic recommendations that are highly applicable in the Pakistani textile industry. It is also expected that this contribution of this research will provide clear guidance to the practitioners and aid in encouraging them to introduce more value co-creation initiatives.

1.9. Summary

With the textile industry becoming more and more competitive following the emergence of new online and high street competitors as well as rapidly changing market trends, the bargaining power of customers has grown significantly in recent years. In order for a textile business to remain sustainable, it is essential that they clearly understand the needs and requirements of the customers and transform them accordingly for being able to design products and services that can meet those requirements. In recent years, the concept of value co-creation is being widely adopted by clothing retailers globally not only to address the specific needs of their customers but also to be able to innovate by gathering ideas from customers. In order to be able to propose strategic recommendations on enhancing customer participation in value co-creation activities for increasing customer loyalty and profitability of the clothing retailers in the Pakistani textile industry, in this chapter, four specific objectives were outlined. This chapter also provided the rationale for the research whilst

highlighting the possible limitations of the findings. The subsequent chapter now reviews the existing literature related to this research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

The traditional theories of value creation, such as goods dominant logic (GDL), consider businesses as key units that create value during the goods and services production process, while the role of customers' are submissive getting value through the exchange of products or services (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004a). A strong foundation of service-dominant logic (SDL) in marketing developed by Vargo and Lusch (2004) is based on a central idea that service is the general denominator in exchange and not the goods. Vargo and Lusch (2004) also highlighted that the process of value-creation takes place when a customer utilises a product or service, instead of when the product is manufactured (Payne et al., 2008). SDL attaches significance to the value-creation process that engages the customer as a "co-creator" of value (Lusch and Vargo 2006). The co-creation phenomenon is supported by SDL (Vargo and Lusch, 2004b, 2008). SDL claims that "value is always co-created, jointly and reciprocally, in interactions among firms and customers through the integration of resources and application of competencies" (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). Gronroos (2008) highlights that the co-creation aspect concentrates on the value-in-use concept where value is being created by the customers through the utilisation of good and services. This notion of value co-creation is established in service logic.

In the service logic concept, the firm is considered as the facilitator of value, which inserts the prospective value in goods and services while planning, designing, producing and delivering (the providers' sphere) (Gronross, 2008). The value is created by customers who create it through the consumption process, e.g. value-in-use (the customers' sphere). Furthermore, value is at times co-created after the company participate in direct interactions by affecting customers value creation process and participation in discourse (the joint sphere). If there is no interaction between the company and its customers, there will be no co-creation of value (Gronroos, 2008, 2011, 2012; Gronroos and Voima, 2013). Customers attitude towards "value co-creation" is affected by the level of customer engagement with firms (Shamim et al., 2017).

Engagement is a mutual communication between the customer and the focal entity (i.e., a brand). Customer engagement incorporates experiences, exchanges and links among

customers and the entities (brands), websites, actions and more customers (Mollen and Wilson, 2010). In order to have a broader understanding of the literature as well as to identify the current state of knowledge in the area of customer engagement and value co-creation, this chapter evaluates various theories such as SDL, GDL, and Service Logic. Additionally, concepts such as value co-creation and customer engagement are also explored in detail in order to understand their dimensions as well as identify tools for measuring them in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

2.2. Value Creation

2.2.1. The concept of Value

The conventional marketing concept of value assumes that it lies in products and services (Rocca & Snehota, 2014). On the other hand, Gronroos (2017) proposes that, theoretically, a “value in exchange” is a sale concept and “value in use” does not start unless the resource has been utilised. Value is being described as the value in use by Gronroos and Gummerus (2014) which means that customers create and determine value when they are utilising the products or services being provided by the originator of the products or services. Value is mainly defined as customer value in various marketing sub-domains such as pricing, consumer behaviour and strategy (Kumar & Rajan, 2017). Though the concept of value is appealing, translating it for commercial practice is not easy (Rocca & Snehota, 2014).

In recent marketing literature, the concept of value has been narrowed down to product and services only. However, as Kotler (2017) argues, we must replace the idea of a product with a total product that includes both product and services and value needs to be measured and weightage should be treated differently for customer perception about different elements of product and service. It is inevitable for value practitioners to develop a scorecard to assess the vector of progression in holistic terms (Snelgrove & Magers, 2017). Daprian & Kam (2017) categorises key drivers for value including facilitation, process alignment, value orientation, relational factors and value creation as the result of multiparty interfaces in the product return chain. The current value practitioners believe that the concept of value goes beyond traditional interaction between the customer and the manufacturer and multiple values and benefits could be obtained throughout their lifetime (Snelgrove & Magers, 2017; Kumar & Rajan, 2017).

The connotations of the concept of the value and its associated notions like value appropriation and value creation have been subject to much confusion in marketing and management (Hallber, 2017). The concept of value is broader and its application in today's dynamic business environment requires participation from the customers. For practical decisions associated with value creation in business, it is critical to understand the concept of value and the factors that join in the formation of value (Rocca & Snehota, 2014).

2.2.2. Importance of Value Creation to Businesses

According to Pavlinek & Zenka (2017), value creation is the activity of a firm that increases the value of manufactured goods and services in contrast to the raw materials, translational goods and services and the cost of production. It is also the execution of inspired, conscious activities that increases the overall good and wellbeing of goods and services, people, ideas, institutions including society, and all stakeholders and things waiting to happen (Mahajan, 2017). The creation of value occurs in processes by activities, tasks and behaviours in the organisation before the company delivers the product or service as output; and also, outside the organisation when the delivered product or service, the output being utilised by the customer (Aslund & Backstorm, 2017; Kumar & Rajan, 2017). Rocca & Snehota (2014) propose that value creation is related to the arrangements of identifying the needs, creating a solution and shift this solution to the customer in return for something else; this idea is also shared by Haas et al. (2012). Corsaro (2014) indicates that organisations have been taking decisions without assessing the capability of the dependents leading to a non-interactive relationship, value was inserted while manufacturing, entrenched in the offerings and objectively determined through the price paid.

Recent studies underpin the demand to further examine value creation as a process (i.e., Payne et al., 2008; Edvardsson et al., 2012; Grönroos and Voima, 2013; Gummerus, 2013). During the 1980s, research in the discipline of strategy, operation management and organisation identified value creation" as a process and stressed the significance of additional component of the investigation, i.e., value creation activities (Porter, 1985; Borys and Jemison, 1989).

Though value creation is highly discussed in the number of academic literature still there is no common classification of this concept especially in relation to those who could benefit

from it (Teti et al., 2014). The theoretical confusion is perhaps due to the variety of research disciplines including marketing management captivated in value creation and in customers versus firms perspectives and other subjects of investigation goods versus service-dominant logic, dealing with it, based on SDL that the customers create value and the firms only extend value propositions (Vargo et al., 2008; Terblanche, 2014). Lately, the role of the firms have been re-assessed: firms role is of a value facilitator with the creation of prospective value and value can be co-created through direct interaction with consumers (Grönroos, 2011; Grönroos and Voima, 2013; Smaliukiene et al., 2015).

Gronroos (2017) states that, in order to develop organisational level value and value creation understanding, these should be studied at a micro-level. The long-term success of a business relies on generating vast value for its customers because the business premise lays on the customers demand so the value created for customers is also the value business creates for itself (Reinartz & Käuferle, 2015). Kumar & Rajan (2017) introduced 3 characteristics of value creation i.e. i) all associated parties despite their different nature and role are expected to create value, ii) value can be destroyed if the participants of value creation don't realize the value created by their relationship, iii) value is realized on a continual basis that determines where value is being created or destroyed. Reypens et al. (2016) emphasise that besides understanding the value creation process, it is also crucial to realise how stakeholders acquire their value share. O'Ngo and Cass (2012) are of the view that while building relations with business customers and collaborating with them, the importance of providing the customer with superior value in the core product must not be neglected. Customers value creation (value co-creation) is pivotal to attain successful business development and the attention in the subject of value creation keep on rising in the management research (Carrington & Neville, 2016). The next section now explains value co-creation along with key theories associated with it.

2.3. Value Co-Creation

“Value co-creation refers to the interaction with and usage of resources for mutual benefit” (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). It is a moment of exchange during which service providers and customers perceive that potential benefits might overcome the incurred costs (Lusch and Vargo, 2014; Payne et al., 2008). Gronroos and Gummerus (2014) state that “value co-creation is a joint process that takes place on a co-creation platform involving, for example, a service provider and a customer, where the service provider's service (production) process

and the customer's consumption and value creation process merge into one process of direct interactions". In this unified process, there may be engagement from a service provider with the value creation of customer and, by mutual co-creation activities, impact the customers' formation of value-in-use; service provider role can be adopted by customers and co-create value with the supplier (Gronroos and Gummerus, 2014). Furthermore, Alves et al. (2016) state that no agreement exists amongst the researchers on the classification of value co-creation, although they agree on the role of customers and the subjective nature of value.

Both firm and the customer embraces a joint production process to create value (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004a; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004b). The association between the service provider and customer are joint processes including carefully managing the personal communication between the involved groups (Jaakkola and Alexander, 2014). The co-creation of value is becoming a more prominent theme in the literature (Kohtamaki and Rajala, 2016). The co-creation label has flourished over the past decade (Ramaswamy and Ozcan 2018). Current advances in marketing theory have been designed around the idea of value co-creation (Laamanen & Skalen, 2015).

Co-creation exists in various field and diverse approaches like, (1) driving business innovation through co-creation, (2) new products and services development, (3) customers experience in the process of co-creation, and (4) customers experiences of brands are getting noteworthy importance, and have co-creation as the basis for market associations (Alves et al., 2016). The marketing field has been through three generations of development stages from the product to customer and from customer to human experience; customers give attention to the ecosystem, social activities, vision and mission of the companies (Gohary & Hamzeli, 2016). Alves et al. (2016) state that various fields and sides organise co-creation of value-enhancing different aspects, some focus on firms' value, some on the development of value and others on customers value. Based on service-dominant logic, "value co-creation" is not restricted to the present interaction between a customer and the service provider; it also involves previous and forthcoming experiences and prospects (Baumann et al, 2016). According to Mostafa (2016), many companies' success relies on creating specific value for their customers, if we look closer at the activities employed by companies like Intel, FedEx, UPS, Caterpillar, linked to their capabilities of creating higher value for their enterprise clients with the application of co-creation.

According to Gronroos and Gummerus (2014), a customer is the value creator, the service provider may participate with the customers process in the “co-creation” of value. Gronroos (2012) points out that customers can also act as a service provider and affect the company's processes, in terms of offering feedback about protentional enhancements to current processes. According to Gronroos (2008) with the application of service logic, the firms establish prospects of interacting with its customer during their value creation process and engages directly in the fulfilment of value for the customers hence becoming a value co-creator. In order to adopt service logic, in terms of aiming to endorse and assist customers, routine rehearses, alongside collecting information about its customer requirements the firms must obtain detailed insights into their practices too (Gronroos and Gummerus, 2014).

Prevailing researches of value co-creation are mostly fixated with individualised and harmonious discussions and it leads to distorted assumption rather than showing the messy social existence in and around value co-creation. Laamanen & Skalen (2015) is of the view that while theorizing all dimensions must include personal and shared as well as conflictual aspects of value co-creation. Baumann et al. (2016) argue that the concept of value co-creation is an abstract concept with very limited implementation in practice and without much empirical advancement. The increase in the research on this topic has highlighted the shortcomings of understanding its conceptual boundaries and empirical elements (Ranjan & Read, 2016). The concept has been adopted and applied in various organisation and industries including textile. As observed in the literature, there exist three key theories of value co-creation, namely goods dominant logic (GDL), service-dominant logic (SDL), and service logic.

2.3.1. Goods Dominant Logic

Goods Dominant Logic (GDL) is based on the goods of products, comprising of both tangible (goods and intangible services) components of production, as typical components of exchange (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). Goods dominant logic is inherited by marketing from economics whose emphasises have been on the exchanging of manufactured products, entrenched value and demonstrable resources (Skalen et al., 2015). Vargo and Lusch (2004) state that, in its very simple outline, the goods-centred belief proposes the following: The function of economic activity is to produce and dispense products which can be sold and embed value in these during the manufacturing process and must be sold for a profit to the customer. For efficiency, the manufacturing preferably takes place in separation from the

consumers and leads to uniform, inventoriable goods (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). According to Gutman and Mills (1982) products are resources to accomplish various states, including happiness, security, and achievement; most of the time people buy goods because possession of them, their display, and the experience they get, results in satisfactions other than those associated with the essential product functions. Vargo and Morgan (2005) stated that from the time of Smith's (1776) statement that 'productive' means creating excess tangible possessions that could be disseminated to improve national wealth, the lexicon of society, commerce and economics, in general, has established around a logic of tangible goods. The service-dominant logic (SDL) by Vargo and Lusch (2004, 2008) challenged the embedded value in the manufacturing viewpoint.

2.3.2. Service-Dominant Logic

Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing by Vargo and Lusch (2004), a groundbreaking piece of writing induced an exemplary shift in the marketing field. The SDL offers a view of markets and marketing in the broader context where service is exchanged for service; it challenged the old goods centric approach which comprised of tangible outputs exchange, producing the value and entrenched in goods during manufacturing processes controlled by the firm and then delivered into the market to value-destroying customers (Brodie et al., 2019). Vargo and Lusch (2004) proposed service as the base of all exchanges, their focus has been on intangible possessions, "co-creation" of value and associations; they developed foundational principles in this new perspective.

SDL has been generating vast attention in academic and expert spheres with the intention that SDL has the ability to considerably amend a firm's operations, culture, and general strategic outlook to produce joint benefits for firms and actors (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Few doubted it and consider it as "old wine in new bottles," as indeed features of notions including market orientation, services and relationship marketing, alongside network perspectives and integrated marketing communications can be found in SDL (Aitken et al., 2006). Also, SDL combines these concepts into a unified articulate concept that is not only applicable to specific aspects of marketing but also has the capability to change the entire field in theory and practice (Meunier-FitzHugh et al. 2011).

SDL is an approach for integrated consideration of the objective and nature of organisations, market and society (Vargo and Lusch, 2018). The basic argument of SDL is that firms, markets, and society are primarily related with the trading of services, the functioning of competencies for benefitting of a partner; that is, “service is exchanged for service, all firms are service firms, all markets are centred on the exchange of service, and all economies and societies are services based” (Vargo and Lusch, 2018). Vargo and Lusch (2008) state that SDL deems service as a process instead of a component of output (goods). In the marketing field, SDL has lessened the gaps between producers and their customers (Vargo and Lusch,2008). Under the SDL view, customers are key actors in the organisation network, firms need association with consumers to create value as they are a source of information, ideas and knowledge for a firm (Djelassi and Decoopman,2013). Firms offer customers means related to their business (Arnould and Thompson, 2005). By joining their resources with another party, customers and firm co-create value (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). SDL features significance to the value-creating process that includes the customer as a “co-creator” of value (Lusch and Vargo 2006). The recent development of SDL supports the co-creation phenomenon (Vargo and Lusch, 2004, 2008). Vargo and Lusch (2008) state that, in SDL, value is always co-created, mutually and equally, in communications among a company and its consumers by combining their resources and utilising their competencies.

FIGURE 2-1: SDL VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESS

Source: Vargo and Lusch (2016)

As presented in the figure 2.1, the theoretical framework presented by Vargo and Lusch (2016) with relatively lesser progressing fragments linked by a simple description of value co-creation through the integration of resources by actors involved in shared service exchange harmonised by institutions and institutional arrangements in the service ecosystem. According to Vargo and Lusch (2017), SDL can begin to be something more than the lens, framework, and perspective. It affords the completion of a relatively coherent narrative of value cocreation through resource integration and service exchange, coordinated by shared institutional arrangements that define nested and overlapping service ecosystems. The service ecosystems are seen as nested and overlapping (Vargo and Lusch, 2018). According to Vargo and Lusch (2017), the conceptual investigation of service ecosystems and organisations has just began. Over the next 10 years, much of the metatheoretical work in S-D logic to be fixated on these concepts.

The concept of value co-creation is the central idea of SDL, it is neither a completely new concept nor it has been established in sequence with SDL (Meunier-FitzHugh et al. 2011). The SDL considers value is each time “co-created” through joint participation of the firm and its customers, but the significance of the service in use is decided by the customer alone (Cova and Salle, 2008; Etgar, 2008; Lusch et al., 2010). The firm can only propose value offers, in SDL, the value is not entrenched in a good or service while producing, it cannot offer value on its own, the value has to be developed/experienced by the consumers (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). Value co-creation has subcategories including “co-creation” and “co-production” (Ballantyne and Varey, 2008; Lusch et al., 2007).

2.3.3. Disinclinations between Goods Dominant Logic and Service-Dominant Logic

During the 20th century, marketing researchers received the understanding that value (utility) was embedded in a product from economics (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). However, lately, it is being considered that the service centred viewpoint of marketing is customer-centric (Sheth et al., 2000) and market-driven (Day, 1999). Vargo and Lusch (2004) elaborate on this and state that instead of just being customer-oriented; it involves working in partnership with and acquiring knowledge from customers and being flexible to their dynamic and personal needs: a dominant logic which is service centred infers that value is characterised through co-

creation with customers rather than inserting in outputs. Sense and respond strategy is being adopted by successful firms moving away from create-and-trade strategies (Haeckel, 1999). Vargo and Lusch (2008) feature critical dissimilarities between GDL and SDL: the SDL considers service as the utilisation of capabilities for benefiting other parties in terms of creating value. On the other hand, SDL stresses that value is co-created by several players, comprising firm and customers, (b) evaluated by players in situation, and (c) the result of the players' actions and exchanges in which resources are unified and utilised (Edvardsson et al., 2011; Gummerus, 2013; Vargo and Lusch, 2004, 2008). Vargo and Lusch (2011) argue that SDL takes us towards more robustness and relevance (Vargo and Lusch, 2011). The SDL considers service as a process in terms of accomplishing something for other parties; the position of value creation shifts from the “producer” to a joint process of “co-creation” between participants (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). The notion of value-in-use and “co-creation” is being adopted by SDL instead of entrenched value concepts and value-in-exchange of GDL (Vargo and Lusch, 2018).

2.3.4. Service Logic

From a service perspective, every type of resources including goods and service are utilised for one purpose: to dispense services to customers (Vargo & Lusch, 2008). Gronroos (2011) remarked that the basic buildings of the service-dominant logic do not entirely back the perception of value creation and co-creation in such a way that is valuable for developing theory and decision making for enterprise and market practice. According to Gronroos (2006), service logic stands for firms facilitating processes that back value creation by customers. As customers are involved in these collaborating progressions, firms and customers are “co-producer” of service and co-creators of value (Gronroos, 2006). Figure 2.2 demonstrates the process of value co-creation in accordance with service logic theory.

FIGURE 2-2: THE VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESS

Source: Gronroos and Voima (2013)

Figure 2.2 shows the service logic model of value co-creation in service and its different phases, actors and goals. The model presents a methodical conceptualisation of the metaphorical assessments of value co-creation and creation in SDL, all the important features of the value-generating process. According to Gronroos and Voima (2013:141), the model of service logic for the value co-creation process includes three spheres:

- The provider sphere: “This sphere is closed to the consumer; the firm’s role in the value-generating process is to facilitate the consumer value creation process by fostering and offering possessions that provide the need to encourage the consumers value-in-use. Potential value-in-use is offered by the firms.”
- The joint sphere: “In this sphere, the presence of direct interactions creates a platform for value co-creation. If actors manage to use this platform, co-creation of value takes place.”
- The customer sphere: “This sphere is closed to the service provider and near to the service provider; there, the customer freely creates value as the value in use. If direct

interactions between the customer and actors in the customer's ecosystem occur, the independent value creation depends on a collective social value co-creation process as well.”

According to Gronroos and Gummerus (2014), the above-stated process is not essential as direct as the figure states. Consistent value creation processes and different spheres can be linked, such that co-creation actions may materialise in the midpoint or before the start of activities in the provider sphere. In the product development or service or design activities, the customers might engage, prior to manufacturing or operation activities attach to the consumer materialise. In the joint product design and development processes, the direct interactions take place and produce a value co-creation platform. The service logic perspective is genuinely based on value creation and the customer is the driver of value creation. Therefore, the service logic is highly customer-centric (Gronroos and Gummerus, 2014).

Gronroos (2011) asserts that the stance of service logic is not that customers are eternally the co-creators of value but in specific conditions, the firms acquire prospects to co-create value with their consumers. Korkman (2006) highlighted a service logic grounded on the influences of services on the utilisation process as a system. Understanding service logic, value is not created, it materialises for a customer through a well-maintained system (Korkman, 2006). Furthermore, Gronroos (2017) states that by assisting consumers value creation, the firms offer prospective value which develops as a value in use during utilisation; if the players can create a platform of co-creation through direct interactions, the customers and service providers process combine into one collaborative, interactive and dialogical process, this will let the firm to co-create value with customers. Gronroos (2008) notes that by adopting service logic, firms find it easy to get engage with consumers value-creating activities, alongside playing an active role in value fulfilment for consumers, which, is not possible without the adoption of service logic. Furthermore, Gronroos (2008) highlighted that, in service logic, interaction is the core concept in marketing, not exchange. Interaction focuses on consumers value creation and value fulfilment; it allows the firm's co-creation of value with its consumers. On the other hand, exchange buries the significance of customer value creation and the prospects for a firm to function as a value co-creator (Gronroos, 2008). This research precisely focuses on investigating the practices of “value co-creation” in the textile industry

of Pakistan. The foregoing section discusses the current “value co-creation” related practises within the textile industry.

2.3.5. Value co-creation in the Textile Industry

The term co-creation, coined jointly by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004a), represents a new philosophy, it refers to the activity through which services, products and experiences are formed in collaboration by firms and their stakeholders, leading to a different world of value. Customers, as an important stakeholder group, and the firm are closely engaged in creating value that is truly unique and rewarding to the extent that users’ values are considered. This new approach includes shifting away from the overriding firm-centric understanding of value creation in the textile industry that regards consumers as simple submissive receivers of a value proposition of identical trends imposed unilaterally by textile firms, to a new mindset of human experiences that actively involves customers in defining and delivering enhanced value, resulting in enriched and meaningful experiences. The engagement platforms can be set up by textile companies to offer space for dialogue with each other and with their customers, two parties can meet to co-create unique experiences (Lopez-Navarro and Lozano-Gomez, 2014). Involvement of customers in the new products development process does not indicate that firms are lacking in ideas; instead; the firms want to be closer to their customers, to get their viewpoints, producing unique value for their customers, and changing the old methods of business practices (Bujor et al., 2017).

The current textile industry model is based on pushing customers to buy clothes that do not always address their requirements; as Max-Neef (1992) points out, the protection need is met with clothes while fashion satisfies the human emotional needs for identity, creativity, affection and participation. The clothes are no longer the end objective but the means by which customers satisfaction is achieved (Niinimaki, 2009). The focus should be on customer needs and satisfaction during product design rather than on price, speed and built-in ineptness (Lopez-Navarro and Lozano-Gomez, 2014). Co-creation processes are achieving momentum as a customer involvement instrument that has important implications for brands in terms of brand co-creation and new product development (Cuenca and Gasco, 2018). This will enhance clothes emotional value, will result in a longer life span and less replacement, leading to sustainability with less consumption and production (Lopez-Navarro and Lozano-Gomez, 2014).

In the textile industry, the strategy based on co-creation of personalised experiences results in unique experiences and manufacture textiles with emotional consequence; resulting not only in an attachment to the garments, which are kept longer but also to brand values, initiating a long-lasting and profitable relationship between brands and customers (Park et al., 2010). Moreover, customers increasingly want to participate in defining these experiences, whether individually, with experts or with other customers (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000). Customers creativity has been utilised by engaging them by shifting to active experiences rather than having product-centric utilisation experiences. (Moreau, 2011). This is evident by witnessing mass customization, crowdsourcing, and various service design encounters with “Nike ID” and “Threadless”, customers are getting a feeling of pride from resourcefully adding to a product through “I design it myself” (Franke et al., 2010).

Furthermore, the textile industry employed these design experiences to observe sustainable utilisation and increase product lifecycles (Hirscher & Niinimäki, 2013). Hur and Beverley (2011) designed the Sustainable Fashion Bridges Ideation Toolkit, which involves customer creativeness in a category of stages to move towards sustainability in the initial phases of the design process. Bujor et al. (2017) gave an example of AwaytoMars first brand in the world totally co-created/generated by users. The fashion platform has found a way to get closer to fashion lovers, by using co-creation as an open innovation tool. The idea behind the platform is to engage and empower people in the innovation process of fashion products recognising, by both: 1) Crowdsourcing: the innovation work is done online by a crowd of people (creative community) 2) Crowdfunding: the money for products manufacturing is donated, also online, by people. Guillard (2012) states that a British clothing brand (Burberry) has introduced a digital platform ‘Burberry World’ that lets its retail stores, sales and service staff and consumers transform their communications as a small group. Additionally, consumers can also interact with the brand based on their comfort, they can utilise this portal for appointments booking, viewing a newly launched product or fix the items bought in past. Communication between the firm and customers is crucial to “co-create” value and customers value co-creation attitudes play a considerable role in the “value co-creation” process.

2.3.6. Value co-creation Attitude

Value co-creation is the consequence of customers psychological attitude towards their prospective engagement in-service experiences (Tommasetti et al., 2017). Gronroos et al. (2015) argue that, in service logic, engagement in value co-creation is eventually dependent

on customers disposition which lets a firm equally participate in value co-creation. The value co-creation is dependent on customers reaction towards firm offer for interaction leading to value co-creation (Gronroos et al., 2015). Therefore, the attitude of customers in engaging with the firm to co-create value is vital (Salman et al., 2014) and a significantly vital feature for “value co-creation” (Tommasetti et al., 2017). Superior value can be jointly created by engaging with the service provider by customers with a positive attitude (McCull-Kennedy et al., 2012). When the customers lack constructive attitudes about engagement in value co-creation, they will restrict the firm to impact their value-creating process (Shamim et al. 2017). The firm holds the position of a value facilitator rather than a player; therefore, customers having a constructive attitude and cooperating with firms will let them shape the value creation process for the possibility of value co-creation (Tommasetti et al., 2017).

Direct interaction between customers and firm leads to value co-creation as stated by service logic (Gronroos, 2011; Gronroos and Voima, 2013; Gronroos et al., 2015) and the decision is under customers’ control to keep the communication. The “constructive theory” of attitude explains consumers approach towards participating in collaboration for value co-creation is impulsive instead of regained from memory (Argyriou and Melewar, 2011). Shamim et al. (2017) detail that a customer’s inclination to participate in interacting directly with the service provider for co-creation of value is determined by three attitudes of customers, comprising of interaction attitude, knowledge sharing attitude, and responsive attitude.

2.3.6.1. Interactions Attitude

Interaction is at the core of value co-creation to materialise (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004a). Multiple actors comprising of customers, firms, resources and environment can interact with each other (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). Service logic considers interaction as a basic and important component of value co-creation (Gronroos and Voima, 2013). Interaction is a process of exchange (Ballantyne and Varey, 2006) requiring two participants to inspire each other in joint activity (Gronroos, 2011). Shamim et al. (2017) point out that interaction between customers and service providers takes place for sharing of ideas, knowledge and potential explanations; each participant inspires others in process of production and consumption of service. Furthermore, Grönroos (2011) states that interactions are not similar but a two-way process that is combined into one unified process of harmonised arrangements where one participant inspire others. Interaction is a vital feature to attain success (Gustafsson

et al., 2012). The firms can influence customer value creation by facilitating dialogue to take part in that with a positive attitude and make “value co-creation” possible. Shamim et al. (2017) highlight that customer “interaction attitude” in “value co-creation” is the customer’s readiness, triggered by situational considerations, to answering positively to the firms’ control in its value creation process.

2.3.6.2. Knowledge Sharing Attitude

The basic principles of SDL include that customer is forever a “co-creator” of value (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Customer knowledge sharing signifies a customer’s transmission of specific distinguished brand information which comprises of evidence or experience-based information, In their networks with others to create value for themselves, the receiver or both (Hollebeek and Chen, 2014). According to Shamim et al. (2017), service logic states service providers generate service with the application of capabilities and other possessions to generate possible value in goods and services arrangement. Value creation takes place by customers by integration of assets acquired from a service provider along with their own assets and application of knowledge (Gronroos and Voima, 2013). For example, If a customer buys some vegetables from a store and to make a nice dinner with these vegetables, they require cooking knowledge alongside other supplies such as energy and cooking appliance; the function of knowledge for value in use is essential to create value (Shamim et al., 2017). Thus, for “value co-creation”, it is essential for customers to distribute their knowledge to create value with the value facilitators such as a firm while having direct interactions (Grönroos and Voima, 2013).

The co-created value resulted in new knowledge through the knowledge sharing between a customer and the service provider is higher to the value created separately (Gronroos et al., 2015). Companies can innovate and achieve sustainable competitive benefit through the knowledge shared by consumers in the co-creation platform (Gronroos et al. 2015). Thus, information is the central basis of value creation (Vargo and Lusch, 2008) which requires to be distributed value co-creation to emerge (Gronroos et al., 2015; Lengnick-Hall, 1996). Those consumers who are more inclined towards sharing knowledge with the firms are expected to gain better value (Ennew and Binks, 1999).

2.3.6.3. Responsive Attitude

Alba et al. (1997) state that there are three main advantages of having a personal interaction between firms and customers: dyadic, immediate, and contingent. When two parties interact on a digital platform, one part follows the other (Stewart and Pavlou, 2002). The instantaneous and constructive response is a significant feature of meaningful interaction (Shamim et al., 2017). If the service provider and consumer interaction take place with resources only, the establishment of a dialogical platform is not possible (Gronroos and Gummerus, 2014).

The dialogical platform can be established through the positive response of customers to the firms when they initiate interaction (Shamim et al., 2017). Customers cooperation, engagement in interaction, and easy acceptance of the control of service provider in the value-creating process are imperative to co-create value (Bettencourt, 1997; Yi and Gong, 2013). Customers responsive attitude turns out to be crucial for an effective prosperous value co-creation (Shamim et al., 2017).

2.4. Customer Engagement

Customer engagement is widely discussed by marketing researchers recently (Koetz, 2019). The customer engagement concept attracted increased attention from academics and practitioners (Brodie et al., 2011). Researchers looked at customer engagement from the viewpoint of an organisation and stated it as the functions which facilitate exchanges that reinforce the sensitive, mental or physical asset a customer has in a brand (Sedley, 2006). In the information systems field, researchers consider customer engagement as the passion of customer involvement with the agents of the firm and with other customers in a joint information sharing procedure (Wagner and Majchrzak 2006).

Van Doorn et al. (2010) describe customer engagement as “a customer’s behavioural manifestations that have a brand or firm focus, beyond purchase, resulting from motivational drivers”. Customer engagement is an emotional link among the firms and their customers on the basis of communication and contribution (Imtiaz et al. 2019). Hollebeek (2011) and Hollebeek et al. (2014) broaden the description of engagement with the conception of an interactional association; they describe engagement as a reciprocal communication between the customer and the brand. Kumar et al. (2016) state customer engagement as the mechanisms through which customers help create value for a firm by contributing directly or

indirectly. The direct contribution here refers to the purchases done by the customers and their consequent recommendations (Kumar et al., 2010). Whereas the indirect contribution results from their referrals to other customers, which potentially leads to new feedback and suggestions, as well as taking part in social media conversations for reviewing a product or service that also reveal insights (Kumar, 2013). Baldus et al. (2015) further state that engagement results when customers seek product information, promotions and brand news; it also includes usage of online services for products and service purchase, downloading products or brand-related apps or promotional coupons (Chen et al., 2018).

The notion of customer engagement and its views have resemblances across academics (Vivek, 2012). Customer engagement seems to incorporate experiences, interactions and links among customers and objects, including brands, websites, actions and other consumers (Mollen and Wilson, 2010). Some have heavily focused on the empirical nature of the notion as the source (Cadler et al., 2009). Engagement also emerges to be mainly motivational (Brodie et al., 2011). Various other scholars focused on its behavioural manifestations, which is the primary thrust of MSI and many practitioners (Bijmolt et al., 2010; MSI, 2006; Van Doorn et al., 2010; Verhoef et al., 2010). Further, MSI (2006) considers customer engagement to represent “customers’ behavioural manifestation toward a brand or firm beyond purchase”. Vivek et al. (2012) expand on this concept by indicating that customer engagement embraces those “who interact with the brand without necessarily purchasing it or planning on purchasing it, or on events and activities engaged in by the consumer that are not directly related to search, alternative evaluation, and decision-making involving brand choice.”

Researchers have a disagreement on whether the concept is unidimensional (Sprott et al., 2009) or multidimensional (Brodie et al., 2011; Calder et al., 2009; Vivek et al., 2012). Calder et al. (2009) proposed two simple categories of engagement in personal and social collaboration. The comparative demonstration of these engagement categories differs for diverse media. Personal engagement is more appropriate with newspapers, relating to thoughts like education and inspiration, while social collaborative engagement is in relation with online attributes, and encompasses mixing and contributing in the virtual communities (Vivek et al., 2012). Gambetti et al. (2012) contend for two aspects; the experiential aspect; which focus on hedonic factors related to utilisation and interacting with the brand, and the

social aspect; concentrating on interaction, co-creation, distribution of brand contents and significances, incorporating social interactions with colleagues.

From a customer viewpoint, the advantages for participating in the customer engagement process comprises of monetary benefits or feeling emotionally fulfilled, such as delight and satisfaction (van Doorn et al., 2010). Consumers engage with brands through both offline and online mediums, when consumers associate with the company, they anticipate to be known and served on demand irrespective of the channels they are utilising (Hyken, 2018). Channels are a means to purchase a product (Neslin et al., 2014). The various channels through which customers engage with the brands should be sensibly managed to offer a reliable customer experience (Frow and Payne, 2007). In the next section, both offline engagement and online engagement are briefly discussed.

2.4.1. Types of Customer Engagement

2.4.1.1. Offline Engagement

Gong (2018) states that previously brand communities were geographically restricted and only were present in offline form. According to Pine and Gilmore (1999), a physical store offers a staged experience where customers can enter and engage with retailers in a somewhat predefined way. Cox et al. (2005) state that shopping through retail stores can be enjoyable, physical stores provide the prospect to experience something that cannot be attained through online shopping. For businesses, brand engagement is vital in promoting products/services and enhancement of word of mouth (Lin et al., 2017). Nasir et al. (2018) state that Pakistani women believe in the conventional word of mouth more reliable than social media for making their shopping decisions in relation to clothes. Furthermore, in their study, Nasir et al. (2018) found that fifty-six per cent of customers acquire their information about new product launches through friends and family, twenty-seven per cent through company ads and only seventeen per cent acquire this information from social network sites. Hence, family and friends word of mouth and referrals play a crucial part in establishing brand awareness for Pakistani women and WOM can also influence the consumers brand perception and engagement.

2.4.1.2. Online Engagement

Academics and organisations explore ways, how they can manage the increased customer involvement effectively in brands favour (France et al., 2015). It is observed that sharing views about a particular clothing brand on social media is considerably important to raise the image and awareness about that brand (Khan et al., 2019). The feedback and reviews customers give on products are vital factors in building a brand image or creating awareness (Nasir et al., 2018). Communication among customers in online brand communities can produce demonstrable returns for brands/vendors provoke emotional reactions from customers (Hsu, 2017). Hyken (2018) states that in the past customer used to communicate with companies in different ways than today. Internet is an effective platform for customer interaction and many brands are actively using social media including “Facebook” and “Twitter” (So et al., 2014). Customers can connect with companies in multiple ways by using Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Instagram (Hyken, 2018).

Social media has become the go-to medium for people expressing themselves around the globe as well as how they interact among themselves (Ather et al., 2018). Khan et al. (2019) are of the view that firms are facing challenges in attracting prospective customers through social media marketing. Sviri and Olsen (2012) state that when a service failure is assigned by the customer to the firm, they also share their adverse experience with friends and family and also post that on online platforms. Moreover, in terms of sharing their experience online customers usually share with both familiar and new people (Lee et al., 2018).

According to Bilal et al. (2014), the usage of online platforms has a convincing impact on the buying choices of the customers; they obtain knowledge about various firms and their products and services. Seifert and Kwon (2018) state that at present more and more consumers use Twitter, Facebook and Instagram for sharing their brand-related stories, express their thoughts and beliefs in favour of or in disapproval of a brand. Thomas and Roncha (2016) state that customers are highly interested in brand stories shared by the successful brand as part of their engagement with customers on Instagram. Similar to offline engagement, online engagement also produces significant impacts on the overall customer experience.

2.4.2. Roles of customer experience in customer engagement

Customer engagement is affected by experience and enhances customer behavioural intention in the future (Ahn and Back, 2018). According to Lemon and Verhoef (2016), customer experience concentrates on a customer's cognitive, emotional, behavioural, sensorial, and social reactions to a company's contributions throughout a customer's whole acquisition drive. Customer service, product quality or how a customer perceives a company's customer experience is the deciding factor for the customer to continue with the brand (Hyken, 2018) and in the formation of brand loyalty (Zhao et al 2017). Furthermore, Frow and Payne (2007) state that attaining a seamless customer experience is an extremely important objective of an organisation for enhancing customer loyalty and increasing profits. A uniform customer experience is the most vital aspect for satisfying customers, higher sales and promotion (Grimonpont, 2016).

If a firm fails in providing a quality experience to its customers, this can lead to negative outcomes (Kawaf and Tagg, 2017) as current customers are more knowledgeable as more information is easily available, and are in control of driving their experience (Jung and Seock, 2017). If a firm fails in meeting customers expectations, it is actually encouraging the customers to switch to its competitors, and customers can utilise these options easily (Holloway and Beatty, 2003; Singh and Crisafulli, 2016). Berry et al. (2002) state that to build an emotional bond between customer and company, many firms are methodically utilising instruments of customer-experience administration for strengthening customer loyalty.

Arnold et al. (2005) state that in the perspective of retail settings the idea of unpleasant customer experiences has not been explored, the past studies have focused on the identification of frustrating and satisfying occurrences in customer service. In retail settings, Schneider and Bowen (1999) explained that a terrible shopping experience will result in leading to outrage if customers' requirement for safety, fairness or self-respect is dishonoured somehow. The brand experience is exhibited in various associations with the brand comprising of sensory, affective, behavioural and intellectual experience which jointly influence customers emotional association with the brand, which afterwards leads to their engagement behaviour (Prentice, 2019). Grewal et al. (2017) state that if retailers want to enhance a customer experience that results in more interaction, social media can be used to

achieve that. Roggeveen and Grewal (2016) suggested five forces that push customers to interact via social media: “connected, network, information, dynamic, and timeliness effects”. Based on the above evidence, it can be comprehended that customers that have a better experience with brands are more likely to engage in the long term. Such engagements can bring tremendous positive benefits to an organisation. The next section reviews the possible outcomes of customer engagement.

2.4.3. Outcomes of Customer Engagement

Existing studies have highlighted several significances of customer engagement, such as competitive advantage (Pansari and Kumar, 2017); loyalty intention (Dwivedi, 2015); purchase intention (Gopalakrishna et al., 2017); and firm functioning, and revenue benefits and cost savings (Harmeling et al., 2018).

2.4.3.1. Relationship Commitment

The survival of a business relies on its customers, developing a good relationship is key for long term business survival (Nammir et al., 2012). According to Goodman and Dion (2001), customer evaluation of their satisfaction could be affected by the relationship between firms and customers. Customer engagement demands the formation of trust and commitment to customer and seller relationships (Sashi, 2012). According to Morgan and Hunt (1994) trust endures when one partner has assurance and consider their exchange partner is reliable and honest. When customers trust their firms/brands they become advocates for them. Gustafsson et al. (2015) state that affective commitment leads to an emotional connection between firm and customer that seizes trust and exchange in an association. Commitment exhibits an individual’s constructive approach to the entity (Beatty and Kahle, 1988), a result of customer engagement can be a commitment to the firm or brand and therefore, relationship commitment is considered one of the main outcomes of customer engagement. Commitment is the emotional affection that a customer possesses towards a brand or a retail store (Evanschitzky et al., 2006). Relationship commitment signifies a lasting aspiration to uphold a treasured association with a firm or brand (Moorman et al., 1992; Rabbanee et al., 2012). Some consumers will engage more than others in these associations, showing that the degree of relationship commitment may differ among consumers (De-Wulf et al., 2001). Relationship commitment is a conviction that continuing an association with their chosen

brand or company is valuable to customers and that upholding the association deserves their concentrated determinations (Rabbanee et al., 2012).

2.4.3.2. Customer Purchase Behaviour

Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015) identified a positive correlation between customer engagement and customer purchase behaviours. Customer engagement has the capability to convert non-transactional activities into acquisition actions (Prentice, 2019). Researches conducted previously has revealed how customer engagement has a direct positive association with customer purchase and loyalty (Brodie et al., 2011; Hollebeek, 2011; Prentice et al., 2018). Thakur (2019) advocates that a higher degree of engagement among satisfied customers yields positive outcomes in terms of investigating newly launch products ultimately resulting in strong purchase targets, instinct acquisitions, early consumptions and higher product/service promotion. Customers' individual insights of the firms' uniqueness, branding, promotion and channel engagement are influential factors that shape consumers shopping decisions (Straker and Wrigley, 2016). Prentice (2019) found that the more customers are engaged in the online community, they will buy the products or services with the help of the community. A customer who is engaged and has developed intense and enduring linking with the community usually chooses to purchase and utilise products/services as a form of demonstrative manifestation (Prentice, 2019).

2.4.3.3. Customer Loyalty and Satisfaction

An important intangible asset an organisation can have is customer loyalty. Repeat purchases of product and services have been defined as loyalty by earlier researches (Homburg and Giering, 2001). Moreover, Kandampully and Suhartanto (2000) state that if a customer repurchases and recommend it to others will stay loyal to the company. This aspect of customers have been used by companies to understand and generate more information regarding customer demands and to produce according to customer demands and delivering that to keep them loyal (Bilal et al., 2014).

Researchers have adopted the consumer online behaviour concept in terms of investigating online loyalty as more and more customers are switching to online platforms for making purchases (Anderson and Srinivasan, 2003; Toufaily et al., 2013). Customer loyalty could be expressed in an online context through the consistent usage of services, spreading positive

word of mouth, promotion of brand products, and interacting in online communities, reacting to firms request for reviewing their offerings (Anderson and Srinivasan, 2003; Kim et al.,2009). Customer engagement can enhance customers loyalty and satisfaction with the firm (Jaakkola and Alexander, 2014). Engagement can be utilised as an instrument by firms to influence customers, creating a loyal customer base for the firms (Thakur, 2016).

According to Oliver (1999), there is an inseparable link between customer loyalty and satisfaction. Both have an asymmetric relation as loyal customers are most generally satisfied, while satisfaction does not totally transform into loyalty (Oliver, 1999). Kandampully and Suhartanto (2000) contradicts this and states that a positive relationship exists between customer satisfaction and loyalty. Thakur (2019) further support this by stating that a higher satisfaction level enhances customer loyalty and result in repetition of purchases. Gong (2018) is of the view that customers might perform as brand followers who are less likely to change brands and offer an opinion for brands. Thakur (2019) states that the relationship marketing literature generally believes that enhanced satisfaction results in positive word of mouth and recommendations.

2.4.4. Measuring Customer Engagement

The current study conceptualises customer engagement as a psychological state that arises due to collaborative and co-creative customer experiences with a brand or firm through various channels, involving online and offline. After carefully considering the approaches used for measuring customer engagement by Hollebeek et al. (2014) and Vivek et al. (2014), a holistic view of customer engagement is considered in the current study. Thus, four dimensions of customer engagement, namely “conscious attention”, “cognitive engagement”, “affective engagement”, and “enthused participation” are taken into consideration for measuring customer engagement.

2.4.4.1. Conscious Attention

Conscious attention is the level of attention that the customer has or desires to have in cooperating with the organisation and its processes (Vivek et al., 2014). Vivek (2009) state that the level of attention the person possesses to have in cooperating with the emphasis of their engagement is similar to Hollebeek’s (2011) aspects of engagement and activation and Calder et al. (2009) personal dimension. So et al. (2014) state that researchers have

repeatedly emphasized attention as an important aspect of engagement. Rothbard (2001) stated attention as an aspect of employee engagement and is the period of keeping focus, and mental obsession with the occupation. In this respect, So et al. (2014) is of the view that attention offers an invisible material source that a customer can assign in many ways; highly engaged customers have focused attention, knowingly or instinctively, on the item of engagement. Likewise, individual engagement is linked with sensing attentive, linked, unified, and focused on one's role functioning (Kahn, 1992), stressing the importance of attention in occupation engagement.

The consideration of attention as a characteristic of customer engagement is verified by marketing theory (So et al., 2014). Regulatory engagement theory states engagement as continuous attention, in which behaviourally moving attention away from something decreases the degree of engagement (Scholer & Higgins, 2009). Engagement is equal to focused attention (Lin et al. 2008), and the idea of attention is coherent with the concept of conscious participation (Vivek, 2009), which encapsulates a customer's degree of conscious attention to the brand. An engaged consumer is fascinated by material associated with the brand; an active customer tends to exert an enhanced degree of attention towards information in relation to the brand including news, promotions and offerings (So et al., 2014).

2.4.4.2. Cognitive Engagement

Cognitive engagement depicts the involvement of the customer both inside and outside trade circumstances between the customer and that company (Vivek et al., 2012). The cognitive characteristics of customer engagement empower consumers to reflect regarding a firm's processes, motivating customers to learn more about the firm. The demand for cognition indicates that an entity engages in and likes thinking (Cacioppo and Petty, 1982). According to Halaszovich and Nel (2017), cognition is central to two issues i.e. the type of information, and the essential processes that aid the gaining and utilisation of the information. Hollebeek et al. (2014) assert that cognitive engagement is a customer brand engagement framework that involves a customer level of the brand-related thinking process and amplifies in an explicit customer-brand contact. Furthermore, Halaszovich and Nel (2017) gave an example of social media and suggested that by considering that cognition demands acquiring of knowledge aided through a different process, customers can use Facebook fan pages as a knowledge source to assist cognitive handling in a customer brand engagement settings;

therefore, a higher level of cognitive processing can increase a customer aim to join a company page in order to acquire knowledge.

According to Soderlund (1998), WOM intentions/actions are positively associated with customer satisfaction, when consumers are more gratified with the offerings, they will engage in positive WOM about brands offerings. To help customers in their satisfaction evaluation during brand interactions cognitive engagement is vital; without brand-related thought processing not possible to grasp satisfaction evaluation; expectations against experiences cannot be assessed (Caro and Garcia, 2007; Oliver, 1993). A positive balance cognitive activity communicated by the customer brand engagement factor increases customer intention to engage in word of mouth (Halaszovich and Nel, 2017).

2.4.4.3. Affective Engagement

“Affective engagement refers to a customer’s degree of positive brand-related effect in a specific customer/brand interaction” (Hollebeek et al., 2014). It features the emotions of future or existing customers for the firms and their processes among various channels (Vivek et al., 2012). Brand affect is being defined by Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001) as a brand capability to produce a constructive emotional reaction in the typical customer as an outcome of its utilisation. Consequently, the brand effect produces an emotional reaction on the basis of brand experience (Halaszovich and Nel, 2017). Furthermore, affection in a brand setting incorporates positive thoughts, attitudes and emotional reaction concerning the brand (Tsiotsou, 2011). Jones et al. (2007) state that word of mouth is a result of an emotional reply to a utilisation situation. Ladhari (2007) states that gratification in a utilisation situation positively influences word of mouth behaviour. Furthermore, Halaszovich and Nel, (2017) state that it is possible that customer effective engagement will encourage the customer of a brand for engaging in positive word of mouth. Attitudinal loyalty and purchase loyalty is the outcome of brand affection (Matzler et al., 2006; Sung and Kim, 2010). It also leads to a commitment to the brand (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001). Furthermore, Halaszovich and Nel (2017) state that customer with a higher level of brand affection will be more attentive towards brand communications due to continuing customer-brand relationships.

2.4.4.4. Enthused Participation

Enthused participation is the level of customer involvement in the production or delivery of the service (Dabholkar, 1990). It enables collaborative environments for which satisfies the mutual interest of both customer and the firm (Vivek et al., 2012). It is the representation of an entity robust anticipation and attention in regards to the emphasis of engagement (Vivek, 2009). Academics have described enthusiasm as a positive sentimental condition in the setting of both work engagement and customer engagement; in the context of work engagement, it incorporates the employee feeling of worth, enthusiasm, motivation and satisfaction (Salanova et al., 2005; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Furthermore, So et al. (2012) state that employees who are engaged senses passionate and excited about their job and position in the workplace; this view is coherent with the aspects of vigour (Patterson et al., 2006) and activation (Hollebeek, 2009) as these aspects indicate a higher degree of strength while performing their job, revealing the feeling of excitement.

The concept of engagement is different from other associated concepts, such as satisfaction due to energy and enthusiasm (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Satisfaction signifies consumers general assessment of the functioning of a contribution (Johnson & Fornell, 1991) and its basis on experiences in past, while enthusiasm is categorized by a solid sensation of pleasure (Bloch, 1986), which is a persistent and dynamic state. According to So et al. (2014) on a level of a brand, a customer who is engaged can be characterised by their strong feeling of anticipation and enthusiasm feeling, as a constructive activity is a fundamental sign of customer engagement with a brand.

This research precisely aims to understand how customer engagement and value co-creation are related in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan. Besides, this study also aims to investigate various aspects related to engaging customers in value co-creation practices. Therefore, the forthcoming section (chapter 2.5) reviews how customer engagement and value co-creation are related in detail.

2.5. Customer Engagement and Value co-creation

According to Gronroos (2008), as ‘value’ was once considered to be embedded into goods by firms, it is now considered to be embedded in the perception of customers, their experiences and context, and evolving only through customer usage and consumption. Built around the concept of two-way engagement, customers are now described as fundamental, dynamic and

involved participants in the value co-creation process (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). Value is co-created with customers, who participate and incorporate their assets (Akaka et al., 2013). The newest method of proposing unique value to customers is through customer engagement in value co-creation processes (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000).

Technological advancement across the globe has led businesses to wake up to the influence of customers engagement (Brodie et al. 2011). Consumers have more say in companies' daily activities and decision making regarding a brand. It is not a one-sided affair anymore, social media had given consumers the power to interact with the company and others (Javornik and Mandelli, 2012). From a good dominant to be a service-dominant, marketing has leaned towards customer dominance and engagement. Furthermore, Van Doorn et al. (2010) state that there are three important factors involving customer engagement: the focus is on the customer rather than the marketer, emphasis on the active role of the customer in brand, it remains after the consumption and translates into post-purchase behaviour of the customer.

The Idea of customer engagement in value co-creation is grounded on the concept of relationship marketing (Gordon, 1998), open innovation (Chesbrough, 2003), service-dominant logic of marketing (Vargo and Lusch, 2006) and service logic (Gronroos, 2006). Through the demonstration of open innovation, a firm transforms and advertises the concepts generated both inside and outside of the company so that the barriers between a firm and its surroundings are removed (Chesbrough, 2003). Joining the ideas from outside and internal development, firms pursue to assimilate their experiences and abilities with consumers, and with others in the supply chain (Oyner and Kerolina, 2016). Service dominant logic advocated that the value must be created jointly with a customer, instead of only coming from the company, so the companies focused on customers are urged to engage customers in value co-creation (Vargo and Lusch, 2006). Therefore, the customer transforms into a direct participant involved in the process of value creation, creation and delivery of commodities (Gordon, 1998). O'Hern and Rindfleisch (2008) defined co-creation as a joint novel product development activities in which the consumers play a dynamic role in choosing the substance of the new product offering. According to Prahalad, Ramaswamy (2004) many firms are unaware of the expertise and experience their customers' possess, firm should invite customers and provide a platform for open communication that allows customers to apply their expertise and skills for the benefit of other customers and the firm. Co-creation raises the prospect of developing more successful new products, as the company is aware of

customer requirements and addressing those needs, this solves the problem of information irregularity among customers and the firm (Thomke and Von Hippel, 2002). Value co-creation is indistinguishably connected to customer engagement in communication with the company as Brodie et al. (2011) investigated the notion of engagement as a connecting concept in service-dominant logic and relationship marketing (Ashley et al., 2011).

Understanding how customer engagement can direct value co-creation can be useful for brands in order to include customers in their value creation processes. Prior researchers investigated the prospects of co-creation for the hotel industry (Shaw et al., 2011), and studied customer-led co-production and co-creation process in hospitality (Chathoth et al., 2013). Morosan and DeFranco (2016) investigated the utilisation of mobile devices for facilitating co-creation in hotels, and Chathoth et al. (2016) enriched the information of enhanced customer engagement and co-creation in the hospitality context. Also, Oyner and Korelina (2016) developed a conceptual model in their research on the Russian hotel industry describing the relationship between customer engagement in value co-creation. The researcher found that companies which have familiarity with co-creation and have means are more likely to engage in value co-creation processes with their customers.

Value co-creation positively affects customer brand engagement (Harrigan et al., 2020). The researcher observed the association between value co-creation and customer brand engagement on social media. Further findings by Rosenthal et al. (2017) specify that value co-creation enhances attachment with the brand. According to Nysveen and Pedersen (2013), co-creation has a positive impact on brand experience attributes; suggesting that participating in co-creation activities with customers reinforces the experience of a brand. In China, various international brands like Coca-Cola, Pepsi Co, Nescafe, Ford and Volkswagen engaged their customers for feedback into designing new products and services in value co-creation (Mane and Diop, 2017). Mane and Diop (2017) uncovered that inducting customer engagement in value co-creation is vital for companies to understand how they are perceived by their customers in terms of delivering value in products/services.

2.5.1. Relationships between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes

Value co-creation is reliant on customer response towards firms offering for interaction leading to value co-creation (Gronroos et al., 2015). Therefore, a customer attitude towards

interaction with the firm to co-create value is critical (Salman et al., 2014) According to McColl-Kennedy et al. (2012) value can be mutually produced through engaging with the service provider by customers with a positive attitude. Shamim et al. (2017) pointed out that if the customers' attitude towards value co-creation is not positive, they will not permit the firms to impact the value creation process. According to Leclercq (2017), customer engagement can lead to positive or negative impacts on the co-creation platform due to various users' background. Banyte and Dovalience (2014) state that there is a considerable association between customer engagement into value co-creation and customer loyalty. Furthermore, Grisseman and Stokburger-Sauer (2012) also analysed the impact of customer engagement into value co-creation and stated that it has an impact on customer satisfaction with the firm, loyalty and expenditures, and customer satisfaction with the firm influences their loyalty. Chen and Wang (2016) proposed a conceptual model for investigating links between customer participation, value co-creation and customer loyalty in air transportation. The data was collected from Taiwanese air passengers and observed that customer participation while using the online check-in system is positively related to value co-creation, which boosts satisfaction with respect to the system.

Bazi et al. (2019) state that customer engagement has a positive impact on co-creation. According to Xie et al. (2008), attitudes, capabilities and ongoing behaviour can have a positive impact on customer intention to be prosumer. Engaging customers in value co-creation is endorsed as a significant means of creating a discourse with customers (Ballantyne and Varey, 2006), starting a community around company interest (Healy and McDonagh, 2013), establishing the pledge towards new offerings and stimulating positive attitudes from customers (Kaptein et al. 2015; Nishikawa et al. 2013). Auh et al. (2007) examined the direct impact of customer engagement on value co-creation in the setting of financial services. Their results established the existence of an association between customer engagement and value co-creation. Research conducted by Rajah et al. (2008) on tourism services firms exhibited that engagement of customers into value co-creation leads to an enhanced association between company and customer. The next section examines the advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes in detail.

2.5.2. Advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

The advantages of customer engagement and co-creation have been extensively reviewed in the literature (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). According to Mostafa (2016), customers holds a

standing to produce particular modifications in a firm's business models and to significantly change the logic of value creation. According to Zhang and Chen (2008), for the satisfaction of their customer's needs, firms are increasingly offering customised products/services to their customers. Durav (2002) pointed out that customers can engage in the co-development of new products, retail and after-sales services. Personalisation and engaging customers in value co-creation can result in a competitive advantage for the company (Zhang and Chen, 2008). Furthermore, Alexander (2012) stated that firms can also gain information from customers to attain a competitive advantage. Co-creation activities will let companies gather knowledge to meet customer needs and new design ideas (Jaworski & Kohli, 2006; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Personalisation and customisation will lead to better quality, better service experience and satisfaction for the customers (Zine et al., 2014).

Customer engagement in value co-creation can lead to loyalty and satisfaction with the brand (Jakkola and Alexander, 2014). As, level of customer engagement increases, customers may become uniformly more dedicated to the value co-creation process and contribute more towards it (Dong et al., 2008; Wilson et al., 2008). According to Vargo (2009), enhanced engagement in customer communities can generate more gains through enhanced brand and consumer relationships. Furthermore, Rajah et al. (2008) stated that the engagement of customers in value co-creation enhances customer satisfaction and trust. Increased contribution towards the firm may give the customer sentiment of achievement, self-efficacy and largely satisfaction of the process itself (Dong et al., 2008; Meuter et al., 2005). Co-creation helps firm in terms of loyalty benefits as customers foster a bond with the company (Jaworski and Kohli, 2006), this may also benefit firms to stop their customers from switching (Dowling and Uncles, 1997; Uncles et al., 2003). Thakur (2016) states that customer engagement has a considerable effect on customer loyalty alongside customer satisfaction.

Engaging customers in co-creation will also help companies to offer a better customer experience (Ramaswamy, 2011). Customers can be engaged in developing new products as Dell idea storm allowed customers to share their ideas to make computers better. Ahn and Back (2018) pointed out that customer engagement is inspired by the experience and it affects their future engagement. Better customer experience will benefit both company and customer in terms of improved quality in exchange. Customers will also increase their co-creation activities offering opportunities for higher advances (Auh et al., 2007).

Customer engagement in the value co-creation process brings numerous advantages such as customer contribution into the preparation of firm capabilities and word of mouth (Piligrimiene et al. 2015). Jaakkola and Alexander (2014) state that the significances of customer engagement for a firm can be obtained directly or indirectly through positive or negative word of mouth. Interaction among customers in online channels can produce meaningful results for the company (Hsu, 2017). With the help of the internet, customers interact with their brands and customers are keeping their existence on various social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram (So et al., 2014). In the past customers used to communicate among them and with the company differently (Hyken, 2018).

Employees working in firms might also benefit if the firms enhance their co-creation activities; employee workload may be lessened if customers engage as co-creators with higher involvement (Alexander, 2012). According to Schneider & Bowen (1995), customer involvement descends positive feelings in workforces as they undertake suitable functions within the exchange which helps a firm to save additional costs. Nonetheless, as the process of engaging customers in value co-creation activities is a complex process and requires the coordination of multiple parties, such engagement may not always yield positive results if not conducted appropriately. The literature also suggested numerous risks associated with engaging customers in value creation processes, which are discussed in the upcoming section:

2.5.3. Risks associated with engaging customers in value co-creation processes

William et al. (2009) state that customers have high expectations from their brands. A failure to meet customer requirements will result in service deficits, which can have detrimental effects on a brand's reputations (Ann, 2013). The subsequent uncertainty and absence of clearness are likely to cause stress and worry and have a negative impact on the welfare of the customer (Moschis, 2007), damaged emotions such as anger and sadness will result (Shaver et al., 1987). Furthermore, customers may remorse in their decision in contributing to the company's value proposition (Inman, 2007). According to Zhang et al. (2018) firms offer many possibilities through value co-creation but when the customers are involved in the process and when the company try to avoid their complaints and could not fulfil the promise they meant to deliver, the customers become aggressive, and it damages brand equity.

Firms have to offer training to their employees to deal with engaged customers in value co-creation (Schneider & Bowen, 1995). Extra pressure on training will be required if more staff leave the company and in the meantime, the company has to deal with regular customers with new employees (Auh et al., 2007). Managers in manufacturing organisations might find the change towards a service-dominant approach challenging (Salonen, 2011). Furthermore, capital is required to build the technological infrastructure required for successful customer engagement and value co-creation.

According to Gibbert et al. (2002), firms face two challenges in utilising customer knowledge, the inner culture of a firm not incorporating or trusting their customers' knowledge and also where a firm may not have the capabilities for active engagement of customers due to inadequate system and procedures. Bateson and Hoffman (1999) state that customer engagement with the company to co-create may lead to fighting over control of the interaction between staff and customer and increases staff role stress. Hsieh et al. (2004) contradicted the view that engaging customers in the value co-creation process will lessen staff workload, if staff workload lessens the companies usually reduces the numbers of staff, so the level of works remains the same. Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) point out that customer engagement in value co-creation handovers customer control over risk and benefit but not a liability.

Similarly, Alexander (2012) states that engaging customers in co-creation faces challenges and is not without risks. In some instances, the value may be co-destructed by customers and firms (Plé and Chumpitaz Cáceres, 2010). According to Surachartkumtonkun et al. (2015) lack of resources, faulty technologies and arguments can turn customers upset and angry. Annoyed customers can post negative remarks about the firm/brands online (Zhang et al., 2018). Negative word of mouth is an instrument for those seeking public backing as a coping strategy (Yi and Baumgartner, 2004). Ple and Caceres (2010) state that there are customers who accidentally or by design, do not engage in co-creation but destruction of value, and their negative actions result in damage for the company. Fournier and Avery (2011) pointed out that negative feedback generated in customer communities will affect brand reputation and known as hijacking. Recently, modern technologies have been playing tremendous roles in engaging customers with brands. In many cases, such engagements had led to value co-creation. The next section now reviews the roles of modern technologies on customer engagement and value co-creation activities.

2.5.4. Roles of modern technologies on customer engagement and value co-creation

Customers are increasingly engaging with brands by using technology, and it affects the industry in many ways by offering the platform to interact with customers and promote their products (Elizabeth, 2011). According to Ahmed et al. (2015), through technological platforms, fashion houses and clothing brands enable and validate their associations in real-time with customers. Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015) found a positive association between customer engagement of social networking and customer purchase behaviour. Technological platforms including social media channels, help brands to communicate better with their consumers which in return affects their purchases in a positive way and let the company know about customers shopping trends (Barhemmati and Ahmad, 2015). The brands' value co-creation occurs in the exchange between the firm and the customers (Iglesias et al., 2013). This includes the points of communication comprising of online platforms and offline retail stores and products, which are termed “co-creation experiences” (Binkhorst and Dekker, 2009). With the help of social media, customers are empowered to co-create novel services in partnership with the service firm by interacting through platforms like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter (Kaur, 2016).

According to Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015), social media is beneficial for marketers as customers these days select their preferred groups that make target marketing quite easier. Social media can be utilised as a useful advertising instrument (Ather et al., 2018). King et al. (2014), observed that there is an agreement in academia that word of mouth is influential, the impact it makes is much higher than other types of marketing messages. Verhoef et al. (2010) state that customers interact with firms and other customers is easier over social media, customers generate electronic word of mouth and do marketing for the company through social media. Electronic WOM can affect buying intention through value co-creation (See-To and Ho, 2014). There is a positive association between social media marketing and customer purchase behaviour (Ather et al., 2018). There is also an increase in the utilisation of social media by businesses in the fashion industry (Ahmed et al., 2015).

There are customers who value the price or quality of the good or services offered but then there are customers who are devoted to technological platforms and care how a company interacts and offer care to their customers virtually or physically (Barhemmati and Ahmad, 2015). Mangold and Faulds (2009) investigation found that customers have higher

engagement with products and brands when they can offer their feedback; many companies also have set up programmes to enhance this engagement. In India, Tanishq, a Tata group jewellery brand, utilised crowdsourcing procedures on social media as an instrument for customer co-creation in ideation stages of new product development by starting an engagement platform called “My Expression” (Sarmah and Rahman, 2017).

Firms that focus on customer knowledge management should utilise technological platforms including social media to maximise their knowledge about customers, so a decision could be taken to support customers (Bilal et al., 2014). To support customers, an online shopping experience is provided to many consumers in accustomed and accessible settings (Buttner and Goritz, 2008). Optimal and effective utilisations of modern technologies can not only help firms to engage more customers in value co-creation processes but also enables them to serve customers more appropriately by accurately understanding their needs and requirements in a timely manner. As this research precisely focuses on the textile industry of Pakistan, the next section now introduces the textile industry as well as the value co-creation practices that currently exist within the industry.

2.6. An Overview of the Textile Industry

2.6.1. Introduction

Every country in the world has its own textile industry; however, the textile product and services range is quite diverse. The biggest textile importers are mainly the developed countries like the United States, Canada, Japan and the European Union and exporters of textile and apparels are Bangladesh, Macau, Cambodia, Pakistan, Sri Lanka and others (Shafi, 2014). China is the number one supplier of textiles and apparel to the United States (ITA, 2016). The current consumption of fashion good stands at 3 trillion dollars worldwide (Kusters, 2017) and 300 million people are being employed in the textile value chain (MacArthur, 2017).

Azmeh & Nadvi (2014) state that textile firms in Asia can play a central and strategic role in drawing the geography and organisational restructuring of the global value chain. India is the largest exporter of yarn, cotton in the global market having 25 percent of the share the industry employs 35 million people (Gupta, 2016). Germany was overtaken by India as the second largest textile exporter in 2014 reaching 40 billion and expected to touch 300 billion

exports by 2025 (ITA, 2016). The Vietnamese textile industry is the leading export sector of the industry with over 3800 companies and also the country is turning into a prime location of investors in the textile industry (ITA,2016). The textile industry has a massive contribution to the Turkish economy exports volume comprising 18% only came through this industry in 2013 (Baydar et al. 2014). Turkey textile sector has sustained more numbers of direct jobs even in the face of relatively high costs (Morris and Barnes, 2014). Among South American countries only Brazil holds a top place in textile production having 2.4 percent of global production (ITA, 2016). Furthermore, Mexico's 20 percent of all manufacturing employment comes from the apparel and textile industry and accounted for 6 percent of the country GDP in 2013 (ITA, 2016).

The textile industry is mainly related to the assembly of yarn, cloth and the successive designing or manufacturing of clothing and their circulation. The system is multi-tiered and complex which comprises of cultivation of cotton and its harvesting, production of fibre, manufacturing of yarn, preparation of fabrics and its processing which includes bleaching, dyeing sub-processes among different other and final product fabrication (Baydar et al., 2015). The biggest utilised natural fibre in the textile industry is cotton having global production of 24.5 million tonnes in the year 2013 (Turrillas and Guardia, 2017). Cotton is one of the vital important components of natural textiles it is widely used in the clothing industry because it holds excellent properties like softness, environmental friendliness, hygroscopic properties and has compatibility with human skin (Monteiro et. al,2014).

The textile production chain is quite long, with the intrinsic ability for value addition at a separate phase of a procession from cotton to ginning, spinning to fabric production, dyeing and finishing, made-up and garments (Wadho and Chaudhary, 2018). The textile value chain goes through many steps before ending up as a final product for its consumer. The current global trend of the textile industry is concerned with cultivating and manufacturing efficient textile products with high added value (Monteiro et al., 2014). Many multinational textile producers have developed widespread and functional integrated value chains that are dominant in Asia but also extended to Africa, Central America and the Middle East (Azmeah & Nadvi, 2014).

At present, the textile industry is facing pressure on environmental programmes from global competition and government protocols and on top of that customer pressure. Organisations

are pushed to adopt sustainable systems for improving their environmental outlook over their financial performance (Diabat et al., 2014). It is being stated that the textile industry is a clear threat to the environment but still it holds opportunities in terms of sustainability and to acquire that product development process is of vital importance (Moreira et al., 2015). It is also being found that textile organisations have an outstanding environmental understanding and are involved in keeping their consumers happy by progressing environmental performance (Diabat et al., 2014). Valentine et al. (2017) state that there is a clear disconnection between designer, manufacturer and customers who are unsatisfied in long term and being given a choice to easily replace or buy new products and also there is little information available on the ethics of designer on the textile industry. Furthermore, it is being stated that the new textile economy is aligned with the circular economy leading to new design ideas and results in better business and environmental results (MacArthur, 2017).

2.6.2. Textile Industry in Pakistan

Textile is the only successful industry in Pakistan out of many manufacturing industries, one-fourth of manufacturing industry value addition comes from this sector (Wadho and Chaudhary, 2018). Abrar et al. (2016) state that the textile industry plays a pivotal role in the economy as textile exports bring foreign remittances receipts for textile products export to international markets. Textile industry contributes 60% to the country exports (GOP, 2020) and Pakistani textile goods the main market is the United States and Europe (Shah et al., 2012). As of June 2018, the Pakistani textile industry comprises of 517 textile units (40 composite units and 477 spinning units) (TCO, 2018). Pakistan also produces a large amount of raw wool and cotton as an agricultural country. Pakistan textile sector produces five types of fabric: Blended, bleached, dyed, printed and grey (Rasiah & Nazeer, 2015). Pakistan is the third-largest yarn producer in the world (Abrar et al., 2016). The Pakistani textile industry comprises various sectors as discussed in the forthcoming section.

2.6.2.1. Cotton Production Sector

Pakistan is the fourth-largest producer of cotton globally; cotton crops have a 1 percent share in GDP, and it contributes 5.5 percent in agricultural value (MOFP, 2018). The cotton production in Pakistan showed a remarkable growth of 12.3 percent as compared to the year 2017, but it is still less than the period between 2014-2015 which stood at 13960 bales and

the cotton ginning also registered 8.52 percent growth this year (MOFP,2018). Agriculture plays a vital role in Pakistan and the cotton industry is described by an integrated production chain that starts from cotton cultivation to ginning, weaving, knitting processing and finished fabric but with little technological upgradation (Rasiah & Nazeer, 2015).

The usage of natural raw resources in all life cycle phases of cotton and the need for concentrating on the customers' behaviour and sustainable procedures in the usage stage of the product alongside in the printing and fabric procession phase is of high importance (Baydar et al., 2014). Pakistan is directly competing with India, China and the USA for global domination and market share as they are holding the top three spots (Ali, 2008). Due to problems faced by the textile sector, it cannot consume the produced cotton in the country to fulfil the local demand as well as to meet the international order on time (Shah et al., 2012).

2.6.2.2. Cotton Ginning Sector

Cotton ginning is a method of detaching the cotton seed from lint for additional processing in the textile industry. Cotton ginning is a vulnerable connection in the textile chain (Aslam and Rasool, 2013). Ginning sector performs as a link between the grower and textile industry. Pakistan Cotton Ginning Association (PCGA) represents over 1200 ginning manufacturing plants all over Pakistan and has been effective towards the enhancement of this sector since 1958 (PCGA, 2019). Pakistan harvests the finest quality cotton, but ginning factories receive poor quality and polluted cotton due to inadequate transportation and storage amenities (Aslam & Rasool, 2013). Ginning sector should be upgraded on a war footing. The sector already lacks formal training and expertise and the use of outdated technology is making things worse (Muhammad et al., 2013)

2.6.2.3. Spinning Sector

The spinning process involves the conversion of the loose fibre bundle to an actual yarn, the parallel fibre bundle is twisted giving yarn tenacity. Ring spinning, open-end spinning and air-jet spinning are predominant spinning technologies (Perez et al., 2017). Current textiles in historic setups have been produced from some of the latest industrial human-made polymers,

comparing with their film and plastic corresponding items having the same composition, old fibres hold more stability (Quye, 2014). Shafi (2014) states that spinning and composite textile companies have superior capital management practices.

Spinning is a basic process and all other value addition processes rely on it. Any change in spinning product quality directly affects the whole value chain (Shah et al., 2014). As of June 2018, the Pakistani textile industry comprises 477 spinning units alongside 40 composite units. There are some 28,500 shuttle-less looms and 375,000 conventional looms and has grown with rising export demand and cotton production (TCO, 2018). The main strength of the industry is in Karachi, Hyderabad, Multan, Lahore and Faisalabad and some spinning units are very old of partition time (Shah et al. 2014). The spinning industry in Pakistan is operating in a systematic manner with in-house weaving, colouring and finishing services (Abrar et al., 2017). Memon (2012) is of the view that the organized sector apparently shifting to cotton spinning rather than investing in modernising the weaving sector.

2.6.2.4. Weaving sector

Perez et al (2017) state that after spinning the process continues into textile flat structures, fabrics, woven fabrics, knitted or mesh through weaving. It is an art in which interlacing of two separate sets of threads form fabrics or clothes (Shah et al., 2019). The weaving sector in Pakistan is dominated by power looms (Cororation & Ordon, 2007). Memon (2014) is of the view that the power loom sector uses outdated technology; it faces a shortage of quality yarn and needs institutional funding for its growth and low value-added grey cloth is being produced by the unorganised part of the weaving sector. The non-mill loom segment comprises more than 90% of the over fabric produced, Air-Jet weaving units have been installed both as independent units or alongside spinning units (TCO, 2019). The integrated mills running their own spinning and dyeing services, manufacture about 10 percent of the total cloth/fabric produced and also Pakistan have very little share in the international clothing market due to the production of grey fabric (Cororation and Ordon, 2007).

2.6.2.5. Designing and Printing Sector

After the knitting and weaving stage, the fabric produced goes through dyeing and further processes including bleaching (Iqbal et al., 2010). During this stage, the steps are taken to give textiles the visual, material and aesthetical properties, which customers demand (Perez et al., 2017). There is a problem with handloom products like colour fastness and many customers are reluctant to purchase those products due to this issue. Relying on the old method of dyeing causes this kind of issues, a better dyeing technology at the cluster level will help to solve this quality issue and can result in higher demand (Gupta, 2016).

Alvi & Shahid (2016) state that in Pakistan the printing segment rules the general processing industry. In the Pakistani textile industry, the defect rate at the printing stage tends to be 10 per cent (Iqbal et al., 2010). Kazmi and Takala (2014) argue that the textile industry in Pakistan is lacking in product development and design expertise and no such consideration being given to update the systems to compete globally.

2.6.2.6. Ready-Made Clothing Sector

Clothes are made from cotton fabric and synthetic fibre, the clothing production in Pakistan is assembled largely in Lahore, Faisalabad and Karachi and exported mainly to developed countries like the USA, Australia, Japan and Europe (Shah et al., 2014). The government of Pakistan, during the 2003-04 Trade policy, decided to set up garment cities in Karachi, Lahore and Faisalabad, the Karachi garment city could not be materialised (Yearbook, 2018). In the garment sector, knitted Ready Made Garments exports remained at \$2.52 billion and woven at \$2.47 billion in 2017, symbolising 1.1 per cent of world exports in these groups, and ranked Pakistan as the 17th and 18th largest exporter of knitwear and woven garments in the world respectively (PBC, 2018). The highest value addition in the sector comes out of the clothing industry, it comprises of small, medium and large-scale units having fifty machines or less, larger units are part of the organised section of the industry (SECOM, 2012).

2.6.3. Challenges faced by the Pakistani Textile Industry

Pakistani cotton is being considered of low quality (Ali, 2008). Pakistan produces 36 unapproved varieties of cotton and these varieties have poor fibre quality and prone to

diseases (Ahsan and Altaf, 2009). High yarn and the raw material is a huge problem for the textile industry as the distributors make more money than the growers of cotton, so most of the time the growers do not grow or burn their crops leading to higher prices (Shah et al., 2012). Pakistan has low wages for cotton growers and low labour costs (Hussain, 2010). For creating value in the textile economy, cotton regenerative agricultural and restorative methods are used for biological based input such as cotton. The use of pesticides in cotton production cause environmental concerns (MacArthur, 2017).

According to Hussain et al. (2010), the Pakistani textile industry has a weak ginning sector, lower cotton yield per acre, low technical skills, less foreign direct investment and there is also a weak ultimate customer link. Batool & Saeed (2017) pointed out that the textile sector contributes more than half of Pakistan's exports and is facing immense pressure in a new globalized economy. Exports in the textile industry are comprised of low and medium value-added products, also there is a weak relationship between the cotton industry and the textile industry, these factors negatively impact the industry as a whole (Batool & Saeed, 2017).

Furthermore, Shah et al. (2012) state that Pakistani textile companies face enormous challenges like energy crisis, no stability in yarn prices, gas supply shortages and electricity load shedding, currency devaluation, and less research and development culture. According to Rasiah & Nazeer (2015), due to less modern machinery and high production costs, the industry is losing its market share globally. Manufacturing with little diffusion of new technologies, firms are unable to access international best practices, hence the industry cannot involve in high value-added activities (Rasiah & Nazeer, 2015). As this research focuses on the readymade retailers of garment products, the next section elaborates upon the characteristics of the readymade garments retail sector as well as the challenges and opportunities involving it.

2.6.4. Key Players in the clothing retail sector of Pakistan

Pakistan has around 40 plus high-end fashion brands in the country and they generate billions yearly through sales (Iris, 2016). The clothing retail industry in Pakistan collected total revenues of \$9.9.bn in 2017 out of which the men segment had 5 billion accumulating fifty per cent of overall value. The industry produces baby clothing, casual wear, formal wear, bridal, outerwear for men, boys and girls (Reportlinker, 2018). Besides attracting customers

from the local market, female clothing brands of Pakistan has international customers too (Munir et al., 2017). In terms of exports, the Pakistani clothing line has a limited product line and most of the exports are made in the men's segment (Tanveer & Zafar, 2018). Some of the most renowned Pakistani textile clothing brands are Alkaram Studio, Khaadi, Bareeze, HSY Studio, ChenOne, Gul Ahmed, Junaid Jamshed, Nishat Linen, Maria B, and SanaSafinaz (Hadi, 2018).

Most of the above-stated brands are expanding their geographic footprints. According to Rehman (2019), the numbers of stores have increased and the growth has been significant; for instance, Khaadi has 52 stores, J. has 89, and Gul Ahmed has over 100. Likewise, Sana Safinaz has got 31 stores in 14 cities. A new entrant Zellbury already has an existence in 28 metropolises across the country. Various brands are operating internationally, comprising of Khaadi and J. (Rehman, 2019). Cruz (2019) states that consumers became aware of the existing clothing brands in Pakistan by promoting brands through print media, social media, and advertising companies.

2.6.4.1. Brief Outlook of the Pakistani Consumer Market

Gallup Pakistan estimated that between the year 2016 and 2019, Pakistanis paid a total of 700 billion rupees (\$45 billion) on textiles (Rehman, 2019). The clothing industry in Pakistan is growing and the young population which represents thirty-two percent of Pakistan's people seem to be the controlling power behind it; clothing brands are also chasing the young population and accommodating their requests (Iris, 2016). In Pakistan, women are more inclined towards buying lawn fabrics because of product functionality, emotional connection and enhancement of status and self-image (Zafar, 2013). Male customers who have a constructive attitude toward brands demonstrate a higher level of participation in branded clothing (Arora, 2012).

The clothing market in Pakistan is massive; the middle class is willing to spend more on better quality clothes (Arifeen, 2017). Rehman (2019) states that income inequality is high in the market of over 200 million consumers, and thus, catering to the needs of rich customers is as appealing as it was in the past. Different approaches in terms of price strategy, product variety or marketing has been taken by the brands (Iris, 2016). Munir et al. (2017) found in

their study that individuality, public image, CSR, value, country's origin are the appealing factors for customers to spend price premium correspondingly and the managers must give attention to being different, their social image and CSR in order to enhance customer spending.

2.6.4.2. Challenges faced by textile retailers in Pakistan

According to Rehman (2019), the GDP growth of Pakistan was only 3.2% in 2018-19, and this had a noticeable influence on the retail sector which saw a slowdown from 6.57% in the year 2017-18 to a sheer 3.11% in the year 2018-19. Tanveer & Zafar (2012) pointed that lack of product diversification is the main hurdle in the expansion of the textile sector, sustainable competitive advantage could be achieved while competing with international brands through product diversification enhancement. Female consumers are enthusiastic about paying more for stitched clothing if the brand image has appeal and uniqueness (Munir et al., 2017). According to Akhtar (2019), maintain a supply chain is a big issue for fashion retailers, they face challenges in keeping their supply chain in continuously changing designs, fabric or colours. Technology brought new challenges in terms of giving power to consumers, they can compare prices online and shop online instead of visiting retail stores (Akhtar, 2019). Javed (2020) identified that customers substituted in-store purchase with online purchases. According to Ali (2020), online shopping is only convenient when customers are confident about the quality and reputation of the brand or store.

Khan et al. (2014) state that the offline buying experience was found consistent with the following features: 1) overall purchasing experience, 2) warranty and returns and 3) variation. Physical store does not face customers trust challenge hence they can create their customer base easily (Ali, 2020). If a customer wants to return clothes it can be done easily through retail stores than returning back online and even if the online sellers states return policies, customers could be reluctant to return the items due to the lengthy process (Khan et al., 2014). Customers also prefer to visit the retail outlets with a pleasant store environment because customers want reliable services besides catering for their needs in terms of the shopping experience (Azim et al., 2016).

2.6.4.3. Opportunities for Pakistani Clothing Retailers

In the last decade, the clothing industry in Pakistan has significantly grown resulting in more awareness and information about branded clothes and the latest trends among consumers (Cruz, 2019). The clothing sector in Pakistan has seen the joining of various major textile groups in recent times, by grasping the opportunity through the introduction of distinguishing lawns, brands and products related to fashion and style in the market (Iris, 2016). Brands have adopted a mass approach and are working hard to expand their customers base and they have this realisation that profits will come through higher sales volume (Rehman, 2019). The brands' image has been promoted with the help of various marketing channels available including social media, print, promotion firms and companies themselves, to the consumers of their latest clothing offerings (Cruz, 2019).

Magazines associated with other media channels can offer enhanced results to marketers in terms of achieving higher sale; also, take an of celebrity on board will magnify the outcomes (Zeb et al., 2011). Marketers can increase brands sales by promoting products through magazines than other channels and utilisation of celebrity will enhance the results (Zeb et al., 2011). Yousaf & Siddiqui (2019) is of the view that developing brand equity will generate more value for the firm as more customers response is constructive from positive brand equity. With the increased adoption of technology by all customer segments, textile retailers in Pakistan now have opportunities for reaching out to customers efficiently.

In Pakistan, the majority of the transactions of branded clothing is being done through retail franchises that have the permission to sell these brands only, the online sales, on the other hand, is also growing, generally among youths (Iris, 2016). According to Farooq (2020), the growth of e-commerce was observed in 2019 because of increased internet and smartphone penetration, specifically in big cities. Khan et al. (2020) highlighted that people prefer shopping online mainly because of three features: value, accessibility, and brand reputation. The selection of clothing products comprises of the finest designs compared with the physical stores where customers have to spend a lot of time in finding the desired item, technology has made it easier with different tools available (Khan et al., 2014). A sale event is a significant factor in changing customers attitude and opinion; the sales function can be utilised by clothing brands to manipulate customer shopping decision (Zeb et al., 2011).

2.6.5. Value co-creation and Customer engagement in the Pakistani Textile Industry

Clothing brands in Pakistan are progressing towards co-creating collections (Bokhari, 2020). Bokhair (2020) highlighted that customers also want the ability to customise their clothes and businesses are learning and adapting; clothing brand Zara has utilised voice technology to get a real-time response from customers remarks on their products, featuring those modifications in the upcoming products. DYOT a Pakistani clothing brand lets customers customise their clothes appearance while ordering from home or anywhere else in the world (Bokhari, 2020). According to Sarmad and Khan (2020), in the Pakistani textile sector, social media has turned out to be a significant tool that reinforces both, customer and firm to interact with each other and modernizing the firm's mode of relationship with customers. Besides seeking information, customers can also discuss with other customers, likewise, it is helpful for marketing people to utilise social media as an alternative medium to interact with customers directly (Lee, 2013). This radical reciprocal interaction has developed relationships among customers and promoters which ultimately offers prospects within business dealings (Husnain & Toor, 2017). This novel advancement permits customers and brands to communicate with each other, regardless of time and place. It enables reciprocal interaction by enabling the involvements of both customer and retailer (Kim & Ko, 2012). Customers express their opinions regarding the type of products they want and help companies to create products and experiences for them.

Bokhari (2020) states that the current marketing strategies used by clothing brands have switched from traditional styles to full-fledged online marketing campaigns and more brands are embracing this shift from traditional channels to digital channels. Brands such as Nishat Linen and Sapphire have witnessed their online sales skyrocket. The new local brand Lulusar, for example, has a robust existence on social media with a well-defined marketing strategy that involves the audience as an individual (Bokhari, 2020). Innumerable billboards showing the astonishing newest designer collections and beautiful models enhance the whole charm of the brand. Youth mindset can be altered through fashion shows (Iris, 2016). Sarmad and Khan (2020) highlight that the networking capability, image transferability and personal extensibility capabilities of social media helps to engage the consumer and also change the consumer behaviour about products, brands, and services.

However, as Sarmad and Khan (2020) state, the clothing sector in Pakistan needs to engage a customer with more rigorous social media capabilities to save firms during harmful and robust circumstances; their study considered trust as an important moderating factor while exhibiting social media importance. Many prior studies have explained that customers use social media for “status-seeking, information hunting, socializing, and entertainment” (Lee & Ma, 2012; Husnain et al., 2016; Khan, 2016; Wang et al., 2016). Social media is an extremely collaborative package that let customer and groups discuss and distribute users’ content (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Social media platform can be used as a strategic tool by business organisations to promote their products (Weinberg, 2009). It is crucial to understand how social media performs its part in customers acquisition and promotion of products and services (Husnain & Toor, 2017). Online social network platforms like Facebook, Twitter and Instagram are providing ways through which customers can find out products so easily that express their feeling (Abrar et al., 2020). Social media platform can be used as a strategic tool by business organisations to promote their products.

2.7. Conceptual Framework and Research Hypotheses

In this chapter, prior to developing the conceptual framework, an extensive range of existing literature was critically analysed. Table 2.1 presents the key literature that informed the formation of the conceptual framework of this research:

TABLE 2.1: KEY STUDIES RELATED TO THIS RESEARCH

Authors Name	Topic of Investigation	Research Context	Variables Investigated	Dimensions considered
Vivek et al. (2014)	A Generalized Multidimensional Scale for Measuring Customer Engagement	Measuring Customer Engagement- Apple iPod/Apple iPhone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Dominant Logic • Customer Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conscious Attention • Enthused Participation • Social Connection • Value Perceptions • Benevolence Perceptions • Affective Commitment
Hollebeck et al. (2014)	Consumer Brand Engagement in Social Media: Conceptualization, Scale Development and Validation	Customer brand engagement in LinkedIn.com brand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Involvement • CBE Cognitive Processing • CBE Activation Factor • Self-Brand Connection
Desserat et al (2015)	Consumer Engagement In Online Brand Communities	Online Brand Communities on Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Engagement • Value Co-creation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affective Engagement • Cognitive Engagement • Behavioural Engagement
Marino and Presti (2018)	Disruptive Marketing Communication for Customer Engagement. The New Frontiers of Mobile Instant Messaging	Customer Satisfaction, Customer Relationship Management, Mobile Instant Messaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conscious Attention • Enthused Participation • Social Connection • Customer Satisfaction • Behaviour-based CRM
Rabbanee et al. (2019)	Managing Engagement In An Emerging Economy Service	Service Employees of Banks in Bangladesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee Engagement • Customer Engagement • Relationship commitment • Switching Intention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vigour • Dedication • Absorption • Conscious Attention • Cognitive Engagement • Affective Engagement • Enthused Participation • Relationship Commitment • Switching Intention
Salman et al. (2014)	Attitude Towards Co-creation of Value: Scale Development	Turkish Airline Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Dominant Logic • Value Co-creation • Value Co-Creation Attitude 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interaction Attitude • Responsive Attitude • Knowledge Sharing

Oghazi et al. (2012)	Antecedents of Technology-based Self-service Acceptance: A Proposed Model	Swedish Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer acceptance • Technology-based self-service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived Ease of Use • Perceived Usefulness • Perceived Enjoyment • Attitude Toward Using Self-Service • Intention to Use Self-Service
Shamim et al. (2017)	Construction and Validation of Customer Value Co-creation Attitude Scale	Malaysian Hypermarket Customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value Co-Creation • Customer attitude • Service-Dominant Logic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiential Value • Playfulness • Customer Return on Investment • Interaction Attitude • Knowledge Sharing • Responsive Attitude • Customer Participation Behaviour • Customer Citizenship Behaviour
Yi and Gong (2013)	Customer Value Co-creation Behaviour: Scale Development and Validation	University Student Encounters with Service Industry (Restaurants, hair salons and health care facilities) in South Korea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Dominant Logic • Customer Value co-creation • Customer Participation Behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information Seeking • Information Sharing • Responsive Behaviour • Personal Interaction • Feedback • Advocacy • Helping • Tolerance

The survival of a business depends on its customers and developing a good relationship is key for long term business existence (Nammir et al., 2012). Gronroos (2008) states that the value is embedded in the perception of customers, their experiences and context, and evolving only through customer usage and consumption. Built around the concept of two-way engagement, customers are now described as fundamental, dynamic and engaged participants in the value co-creation process (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). Value is co-created with customers, who participate and incorporate their assets (Akaka et al., 2013). The newest method of proposing unique value to customers is through customer engagement in value co-creation processes (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000). Co-creation raises the prospect of developing more successful new products, as the company is aware of customer requirements

and by addressing those needs, this solves the problem of information irregularity among customers and the firm (Thomke and Von Hippel, 2002).

Consumer engagement and value co-creation are understood to be closely associated. Oyner and Korelina (2016) conducted a study in the Russian hotel industry and found that companies which have familiarity with co-creation and have means are more likely to engage in value co-creation processes with their customers. Auh et al. (2007) examined the direct impact of customer engagement on value co-creation in the setting of financial services and identified the existence of an association between customer engagement and value co-creation. Another research conducted by Rajah et al. (2008) on tourism services firms exhibited that engagement of customers into value co-creation leads to an enhanced association between company and customer. Harrigan et al. (2020) also observed a positive association between value co-creation and customer brand engagement on social media. Rosenthal et al. (2017) specified that value co-creation enhances attachment with the brand. According to Nysveen and Pedersen (2013), co-creation has a positive impact on consumer experience. Mane and Diop (2017) uncovered that customer engagement in the value co-creation process is vital for companies to understand how they are perceived by their customers in terms of delivering value in products/services.

A review of the literature above suggested that customer engagement plays positive roles in customers' value co-creation attitudes. This chapter of the thesis not only reviewed the associations between customer engagement and value co-creation but also reviewed the approaches for measuring customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes. Engaging customers in value co-creation practices can indeed bring numerous advantages to organisations. They include enhanced customer experience, increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, innovation, and increased revenues. Based on the findings of the literature, a framework (as presented in figure 2.3) is conceptualised for this research by incorporating the dimensions of customer engagement (Vivek et al., 2014; Hollebeek et al., 2014) and value co-creation attitudes (Shamim et al., 2017).

FIGURE 2-3: RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: The Author

The literature suggested that a significant relationship exists between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes. Studies by Oyner and Korelina (2016), Harrigan et al. (2020), Leclercq (2017), Nysveen and Pedersen (2013), Chen and Wang (2016), Auh et al., (2007), Banyte and Dovalience (2014), and Grissemann and Stokburger-Sauer (2012) indicated the existence of a positive relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation. Therefore, the following research hypothesis is developed.

Hypothesis No 1

Customer engagement is significantly and positively related to customers' value co-creation attitudes in the context of the Pakistani textile sector.

In order to investigate the relationships between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes as well as to observe how demographic factors influence customers shopping behaviours in the context of the Pakistani textile sector, multiple research hypotheses are developed by giving careful considerations to the literature evidence. The literature suggests that there is a significant relationship between demographics factors and customers' shopping frequency. For example, younger people buy more often than older people (i.e., Carpenter, 2006; Pare and Pourazad, 2016; Bhatnagar, 2007); female customers shop more often than men (Dholkia, 1999; Rield et al., 2010); and income level of customers play significant roles in their shopping frequency (Rocha et al., 2005; Roy et al., 2016). The following hypotheses and sub-hypotheses are developed on the basis of the literature evidence.

Hypothesis No 2:

Demographic factors significantly influence customers' shopping behaviours in the textile industry in Pakistan.

The following sub-hypotheses are formulated to answer the above researcher hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2A

There is a significant relationship between shopper's age and their shopping frequency in the context of the Pakistani textile sector.

Hypothesis 2B

There is a significant relationship between shopper's gender and their shopping frequency in the context of the Pakistani textile sector.

Hypothesis 2C

There is a significant relationship between shopper's income and their shopping frequency in the context of the Pakistani textile sector.

2.8. Conclusions

This chapter engaged with the theoretical aspects of the research. Key concepts discussed in the chapter include service-dominant logic, goods-dominant logic, service logic, value co-creation and customer engagement. This chapter also examined the relationships between

customer engagement and value co-creation whilst discussing the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes, and the roles of modern technology in engaging customers in value co-creation processes. The central aim of this chapter was to find the knowledge gaps in the literature, that can be filled through an empirical investigation of the Pakistani textile industry. The following research gaps were identified after conducting an extensive literature review.

- ◆ **GAP 1:** No prior study was conducted in the Pakistani textile sector to empirically examine the relationships between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes.
- ◆ **Gap 2:** No prior study qualitatively assessed the advantages and challenges of engaging consumers in the value co-creation processes in the Pakistani textile sector.
- ◆ **Gap 3:** No prior study evaluated the roles of modern technologies in customers value co-creation attitudes in the Pakistani textile sector.

As the marketplace is becoming more and more competitive, the concept of value co-creation is attracting tremendous popularity among academics. Engaging customers in value co-creation processes yields many benefits to firms such as innovation, increased revenue, and increased customer loyalty. An extensive review of the literature indicated that, despite value co-creation bringing long-term benefits to firms, no significant research was yet conducted in the context of the Pakistani textile industry to identify how value can be co-created through effectively engaging customers in the process. This research, therefore, was initiated to not only understand whether or not increased customer engagement leads to increased value co-creation but also to investigate what kind of roles modern technologies play to facilitate such co-creations. The next chapter now deals with the methodological aspect of this research.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents and justifies the methodology used in this research to investigate the impacts of customer engagement on their value co-creation attitudes. In this chapter, multiple research philosophies and different approaches are compared in order to choose the most suitable philosophy for the research. After the selection of appropriate research philosophy, various data collection and data analyses approaches are evaluated. Besides, this chapter also deals with sampling technique and sample size along with the ethical considerations made throughout the research.

3.2. Research and Research Methodology

Research is often viewed as the cornerstone of scientific progress. Kothari (2004) states that research in common terms refers to the search for knowledge. More rigorously, it can be defined as the systematic approach which scientifically looks for a particular piece of knowledge on a specific topic (Kothari, 2004). It is an investigation of ideas of what we know and how, in other words obtaining a better understanding of the world around us (Williman, 2011). Research is a process of thinking than a set of skills and is undertaken within many professions in order to help test new theories and generate new knowledge in that field (Kumar, 2011). Bacon-Shone (2013) highlighted a research process which comprises of defining a problem, searching for information, formulation of hypothesis, deciding on research design, data collection, qualitative or quantitative analysis of data for verification, modification or rejection of hypothesis, writing the report and finally it is important that other researchers can replicate your research findings.

As Brayman and Burgess (1994) state, research, sometimes, can be messy as conducting research does not always involve completing a straightforward set of activities; researchers have to move back and forth between different arrangements while conducting research and priorities has to be set. It is a systematic and unbiased way of finding a solution to a problem by finding an answer to the question or supporting the hypothesis through the generation of verifiable data (Bacon-Shone, 2013). There is no single path to good research, alternatives are always available. A researcher is required to take decisions at any stage of any enquiry,

making decisions and applying discretion in order to successfully finish a project (Denscombe, 2010).

Research in business studies is different compared to other areas (Greener, 2008). In the context of business, an empirical can be defined as a methodical and planned effort to study a particular problem stumble upon in the context of the business world which requires a solution (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The world of business encompasses several fields including law, economics, finance, marketing, interacting to come up with the final product/service (Greener, 2008). Thus, it is important for a business researcher to have an interdisciplinary understanding of multiple areas in order to conduct a study that leads to impactful business strategies. Methodologies, on the other hand, refer to a different set of methods that align with a specific philosophical position for achieving research objectives (Slevitch, 2011). Below, various research philosophies and relevant research methods are reviewed.

3.3. Research Philosophies

Prior to discussing various research philosophies, brief discussions are made on philosophical assumptions.

3.3.1. Philosophical Assumptions

Research philosophy lays the foundation for data collection, analysis and interpretations; before discussing any research philosophy, it is imperative to understand key philosophical assumptions incorporated in social science studies as each philosophy makes different assumptions. Ontology, epistemology and axiology, are stated by Saunders et al. (2016), as three central assumptions which all research philosophies make. Important considerations, ontological, epistemological and axiological assumptions, have practical implications for designing and conducting research while the researcher chooses a stance on each (Creswell, 2007). A brief description has been given below about different philosophical assumptions.

3.3.1.1. Ontological Assumptions

As defined by Neuman (2011: 125) ontology is “An area of philosophy that deals with the nature of being, or what exists; the area of philosophy that asks what reality is and what the fundamental categories of reality are”. Ontology is the learning of existence and is involved with what is the nature of existence and the construction of reality as a result (Crotty, 1998).

Simply It is all about what is possible to know about the world (Snape & Spencer, 2003). The ontological issue relates to the nature of reality and its features, the reality is subjective and different researchers embrace different realities (Creswell, 2007). Ontological positions establish our process of knowing (Slevitch, 2011).

3.3.1.2. Epistemological Assumptions

Epistemology deals with the ways through which reality can be discovered (Saunders et al., 2016), knowledge may be produced (Holmes and Lindsay, 2018). It is about theorising knowledge dealing with how we know things and what to regard as acceptable information in the domain (Williman, 2011). Epistemological assumptions lead to the question of whether or not a researcher believes that the phenomenon is known (Slevitch, 2011). While conducting qualitative research under the epistemological assumption, the researcher tries to get nearer to the participant being studied, as qualitative researchers conduct field studies where participants are located trying to enhance their knowledge which develops over time (Creswell, 2007).

3.3.1.3. Axiological Assumptions

Axiology is connected with the judgement of the role of the researcher's own value on the entire process of research (Li, 2016). Axiological assumptions acknowledge that the values and ethics of scholars play central roles in entire research as to in what way investigator can articulate and deal with issues that noticeably impact study results (Saunders et al., 2016). The axiological viewpoint of a research paradigm is intended towards illustrating the degree of uniformity, reliability or else restructuring or developing the earlier held theories or interpretation (Neuman, 1997).

3.3.2. Philosophical Stances

In the social sciences, philosophy narrates the progression of knowledge and the classification of that knowledge in the social world (Bahari, 2010). As Saunders et al. (2016) states, a research philosophy is a classification of values and assumptions about the progression of knowledge. According to Creswell (2014), it is a tool that assists researchers in choosing appropriate research methods and practices for exploring research phenomenon. Bahari (2010) argues that research philosophy is extremely crucial in any kind of research whether natural sciences or social sciences. There main reasons being given why an

individual should understand philosophy in research by Easterby-Smith et al. (2015) are: (a) It can assist to simplify research designs, (b) which design will function and will not, and (c) to distinguish and even produce, designs that may be external his or her past experience.

The two main and widely adopted research philosophies are positivism and interpretivism (Wilson, 2014; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Another philosophy that is discussed widely in literature is Pragmatism (Wilson, 2014; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016; Saunders et al., 2016). To gather a deeper understanding of all major research philosophies and to select an adequate research philosophy for this research, all three key philosophies are reviewed below.

3.3.2.1. Positivism

In positivist philosophy, as stated by Merriam (2009), objective reality exists and we can observe it, establish and measure it. Acquiring knowledge through this reality is stated as scientific which leads to the establishment and generalisation of law-like interpretations. According to Holmes and Lindsay (2018), a positivist philosophy proclaims that only one reality exists, and objective research can only result in establishing absolute truths about the world. Slevitch (2011) proposes that the definite truth exists and there is only one truth. Thomas (2017) asserts that a positivist philosophy can curtail bias as researchers often act as impartial viewers during the research process and try not to taint the research results. According to Levin (1998), the belief system of positivist is that reality is constant, observation and description can be provided through having an objective viewpoint, without affecting the phenomenon under research.

Abutabenjeh (2018) states that the traditional form of research is presented in a positivist world view and sometimes is called the scientific method. Further, he asserts that positivists tend to apply quantitative methods rather than qualitative, on cause-and-effect relationships that are anticipated in experiments. Experimental research assumes a positivist stance (Merriam, 2009). According to Bahari (2010), research methodologies in positivist beliefs are derived from natural science and inspired by the reasoning of experimental designs. In this approach utilisation of statistical analysis, measures of relationship and expansion of measurement models are substantial (Bahari, 2010). Deductive reasoning is used to formulate theories that can be tested by positivists through a fixed, predetermined research design and objective procedures (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Furthermore, Sekaran & Bougie (2016)

states that several hypotheses are developed first in this approach by researchers after conducting a literature review, and subsequently, prearranged hypotheses are either accepted or rejected with the help of statistical testing; in this approach, instruments such as questionnaires, surveys, and observations are used, and responses are generally conducted from a large sample.

The central aim of a positivist philosophy is to facilitate replication. Researchers that follow positivist philosophy adopt objective methodologies to guarantee the replicability of their findings (Saunders et al., 2016). However, According to Bell (2010), to answer a social question one should not rely entirely on positivist philosophy as it is a developing field, and it is exposed to continuous incursions of emerging factors and ideologies. The philosophy encompasses many shortcomings in the form of predetermined methods, which limits creativity and also prevents the investigators to improve the prevailing methods.

3.3.2.2. Interpretivism

Remenyi et al. (1998) state that the idea of exploring the in-depth details of a context is to understand reality. Normally a reality could be buried under the subjective nature of context also known as constructionism or social constructionism. Merriam (2009) is also of the view that interpretive research assumes that reality is socially formed and there is no single observability rather than many interpretations of a single event. Al-saadi (2014) is of the view that besides direct observation there are other ways to know about the world, people utilise their perception to read what their logics tell them.

As an alternative to positivist philosophy, interpretive philosophy was developed. Interpretivist researchers believe that social subjects are not easily investigated as they can be viewed differently by different researchers, due to aspects like thoughts, ideas, emotions, observations, and activities play central roles in defining individual perceptions (Thomas, 2017). Interpretivist researchers are considered as the researchers influenced by feelings and emotions (Bahari, 2010). Interpretive researchers are social actors who can clarify their daily social roles corresponding to the meaning given to these roles and interpret other social characters according to their own set of implications (Saunders et al. 2016). Interpretive philosophy is a creative philosophy since it allows a researcher to have freedom in terms of

incorporating new experiences and enhancing the research methods being monitored (Bell, 2010).

Interpretivist generally follows an inductive approach to perform their in-depth studies utilising relatively small samples sizes (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Furthermore, for the purpose of data collection qualitative techniques such as in-depth interviews and focus group discussion are utilised (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). To gain new insights, the collected data are interpreted using the qualitative data analysis technique in this approach. According to Ritchie and Lewis (2003), the social world including management and business is not ruled by law-like symmetries but is facilitated with meaning and human interventions. Researchers in social sciences should have the realisation of meanings utilising both the participant and researcher understandings (Bahari, 2010). In Saunders et al. (2016)'s view, due to its subjective nature and researchers bringing their own interpretations, it is probable that the beliefs of researchers and values perform a central role in interpreting research findings. Furthermore, Collis & Hussey (2014) state that the replicability of the results of the interpretive investigation could be limited.

3.3.2.3. Pragmatism

The pragmatism philosophy does not take any specific position on what encompasses good research, a pragmatist is of the view that research on subjective and objective meaning can generate valuable knowledge, subject to the research questions of the research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). According to Kelemen and Rumens (2008), pragmatist researchers assert that subjective and objective approaches are only applicable where they support actions. A pragmaticistic focuses on functional, applied research where various beliefs of research and the subject under investigations are helping to solve a business phenomenon (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). According to Saunders et al. (2016), to inform future practices and solve research problems, a pragmatist investigator settles with both subjective and objective ideas, facts and principles, experiences and knowledge. To solve underlying problems pragmatist researchers, utilise tools offered by positivists and interpretivist philosophies.

According to Sekaran& Bougie (2016), pragmatism defines research as a procedure where theories and concepts are generalisations of our past activities and encounters, and of the exchanges one had with the surroundings. The pragmatists, thus, highlight the socially constituted nature of research; various investigators have different concepts about, and

clarifications for, what is materialising around us. The pragmatism philosophy helps in solving research problems and to inform future practices, pragmatist researcher forms relevant research questions and identify appropriate research methods in order to answer them. The range of research methods adopted in this philosophy comprises qualitative, quantitative, mixed, multiple and actions research (Saunders et al., 2016).

The pragmatists consider theories and ideas as vital instruments to discover their way in the world that encircles us. For a pragmatist researcher, the research value remains in its applied implication; the rationale of theory is to enlighten practice (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The researcher's own ability in understanding the complexity of the research problem is vital for the success of pragmatist research. If the researcher is unaware of the availability of a full range of available tools this will lead to inappropriate deployment of research methods (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Furthermore, if a research process is not thoroughly constructed, findings of the research could be subjected to researcher bias due to the priority given by researchers to their own beliefs and values while interpreting the results (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

3.3.2.4. Philosophy chosen for this research

According to Neuman (2011), a positivist philosophy is widely used and the oldest philosophy in social sciences. Oates (2006) states that researcher relying on positivist approach desire precise quantitative data and mostly utilise experiments, survey and statistical tools. It is anticipated that the goal of social science is to uncover universal laws. The main aim of a positivist philosophy is to help in replication (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). In comparison to the positivist paradigm, the interpretive paradigm includes the epistemological belief that inspection is not conceivable (Oates, 2006). It is up to the observer how he/she interprets it. The interpretivist philosophy contends that humans to be dissimilar from physical phenomena as they produce sense (Saunders et al., 2016). The objective of an interpretivist researcher is to uncover new insights by utilising research instruments like in-depth interviews of small samples; on the other hand, a positivist researcher statistically authenticates original assumptions in different contexts utilising large samples (Wilson, 2014).

Interpretivist studies are mostly elaborative and highly useful in uncovering new insights, while pure positivist research could result in failure in terms of addressing an emerging phenomenon that is not available in literature yet. A careful mix of interpretivist and positivist approach can lead to a meaningful research combination. An interpretivist approach can be utilised to explore new insights of the findings of the literature review, for identifying relationships between research variables through statistical tests a positivist approach is best suited. Both research approaches have their own significances while pursuing a research. For this research, pragmatism was considered as the appropriate philosophical stance as pragmatism is a paradigm that offers to link the gap between the scientific method and structuralist positioning of older methods and the naturalistic approaches (Creswell 2014). This study aims to explore the impacts of customer engagement on their value co-creation attitudes. Given that very few numbers of studies are conducted in the Pakistani textile industry, a wholly objective approach is not suitable. Therefore, this study a pragmatic research philosophy for achieving its objectives.

3.4. Research Approach

Trochim (2006) mentions two comprehensive approaches of theory creation, namely inductive and deductive.

3.4.1. Inductive Approach

Trochim (2006) refers to induction as shifting from the explicit to the general. Creswell and Plano Clark (2007: 129) describe the inductive investigator as somebody who engages from the “bottom-up, using the participants’ views to build broader themes and generate a theory interconnecting the themes”. Furthermore, Creswell (2007) states that qualitative research is related to the inductive approach, developed and shaped by the researcher experience in data collection and its analysis. During the examination, the researcher follows a system of analysing the data to develop and increase knowledge of the topic being studied. Furthermore, Al-saadi (2014) states that a research process is largely inductive when the purpose of the study is to generate a theory from the collected data instead of utilising it to test an already prevailing theory.

3.4.2. Deductive Approach

Trochim (2006) states that while deduction initiates with the general and closes with the specific, opinions constructed on experience or observation are best conveyed inductively,

the opinions constructed on laws, systems, or other commonly accepted values are rightly conveyed deductively. Therefore, the deductive approach to testing a theory is more likely to be associated with quantitative research. Creswell and Plano Clark (2007: 130) state that the deductive investigator “works from the ‘top-down’, from a theory to hypotheses to data to add to or contradict the theory”. As Greener (2008) asserts that a deductive researcher tries to adopt an objective view in their writings but that such a thing as total impersonal objective research does not exist.

3.4.3. Abductive Approach

Abductive reasoning is the creation of a possible assumption from what you know (Merriam-Webster, 2020). Abductive reasoning starts by initiating a goal state illustrated by a problem to be resolved with no urgent solution found (Schvaneveld and Cohen, 2010). According to McGregor (2008), abductive reasoning usually begins with a partial arrangement of observations and advances towards the probable possible explanation for the set of observations. Abductive reasoning is being utilised by individuals in order to make sense of their multifaceted life (Kolko, 2010). While sensemaking, accuracy is not important and more significant is to provide certain abstract and demonstrable structure to the concepts, views and reflections (Kolko, 2010).

Abductive reasoning is the method of producing hypotheses, theories or descriptions and it incorporates both deductive and inductive reasoning (Mirza et al., 2014). Further, Schvaneveld and Cohen (2010) also state that abductive reasoning comprises determining new hypotheses or justifications. According to McGregor (2010), abductive reasoning is in sharp contrast to the commonly known deductive and inductive reasoning. Abductive thinking is generally stated as Inference (Douven, 2017). Abductive reasoning is a resourceful inference, which includes the incorporation and reasoning of concepts to produce new knowledge (Mirza et al., 2014).

3.4.4. Selected Approach and Justifications

The research adopts pragmatism as a research philosophy. As stated by Saunders et al (2016), the theories in the deductive approach are generated through statistical testing of multiple propositions, this approach is often considered as a scientific/positivist research approach. However, the inductive approach is deemed beneficial in determining emerging themes as the holistic approach is taken during the investigation of a phenomenon (Wilson, 2014). Having

reasoned the main approaches above, the researcher adopted abductive reasoning as it fits the design of research. As Mirza et al. (2014) suggested, abductive reasoning produces hypothesis, theories or descriptions as it heads deductive and inductive reasoning, and it is often used for theory creation under pragmatic philosophy. This research adopts abductive reasoning to utilise both deductive and inductive reasoning. Through deductive reasoning, the current research examines the relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation attitude, testing research hypotheses. On the other hand, inductive reasoning is utilised to achieve a better insight into the role of customer engagement in value co-creation processes.

3.5. Research Strategy

A research strategy is a plan of action designed to achieve a specific goal and is different from the research method (Denscombe, 2010). A review of the literature suggested various key research strategies, namely case study, survey, action research and ethnography. Prior to selecting the most suitable research strategy for this research, all key research strategies are briefly discussed below.

3.5.1. Survey

The survey is one of the strategies used to collect data in the social sciences (Williman, 2011). According to Queiros et al. (2017), a survey helps in collecting data directly from the subject taking part in research with the help of an arrangement of questions in a specific order. By utilising this method, the investigators manage to encapsulate the phenomenon on spot (Williman, 2011). Survey research tends to utilise cross-sectional research designs with large samples, allowing multiple aspects to be quantified simultaneously and therefore possible core relationships to be observed (Easterby-Smith, 2015). In business research, the survey strategy is quite popular due to the fact that it lets the researcher gather quantitative and qualitative data on different types of research questions (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

There are mainly three types of surveys that pursue to choose a separate viewpoint; they are factual, inferential and exploratory studies (Easterby-Smith, 2015). According to Creswell (2003), quantitative research utilises approaches of inquiry such as experimental and surveys. Queiros et al. (2017), state that the survey is a low-cost method as a representative or entire population but on the other hand, there is an issue of data reliability as it is dependent on the structure of the survey and the answers provided by the participants.

3.5.2. Case Study

The case study approach is helpful in examining a phenomenon when there is no distinct boundary between such phenomenon and its context (Yin, 2003). The case studies have been used for an extensive range of functions within social research (Denscombe, 2010). According to Gummerson (2001), the case study could be mostly inductive, where the case data results in conceptualization and theory development. It can also be mainly deductive where the cases are used to examine the theory already existing. The case study approach performs well once the investigator wants to explore a problem in-depth and can come up with explanations that can handle the density and delicacy of the situations in real life (Denscombe, 2010). Gummerson (2001) states that cases can be selected and defined in many ways according to the problem being studied, how accessible it is, the amount of time the researcher has access to it and the resources available to conduct it.

3.5.3. Ethnography

According to Queiros et al. (2017), ethnography comprises of studying a condition and interviews are being conducted with participants. In this type of research, the investigator explains the situation under study from the participants perspective. Nurani (2008) states two features of ethnography: (a) the observation is being done in natural arrangement, and (b) researcher must comprehend how an event is noticed and explained by the persons in a speech group. According to Charmaz (2006), in ethnography, a holistic view should be taken by a researcher, in which a researcher must analyse the specifics of all the available features. Saunders et al. (2016) state that ethnography is entrenched tightly in the inductive approach. Queiros et al. (2017) state that ethnography main benefit is that it allows a researcher to acquire in-depth knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation. The main disadvantage of ethnography is that it is time-consuming and diverse results are produced in the study and will lead to difficulty in extracting precise and targeting conclusions (Queiros et al., 2017).

3.5.4. Selected Research Strategy and Justifications

A research strategy is an inclusive plan of action that facilitates achieving research objectives and also in answering the main research question. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), research strategies vary subject to the nature of objectives and questions of the research.

The survey is the most common research strategy in management studies and is broadly accepted. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), the survey strategy allows researchers to gather both quantitative and qualitative data in order to answer different research questions. Questionnaires, structured interviews, and structured observations are the data collection methods that are part of the survey strategy (Poorrezaei, 2016). For this research, the researcher utilises survey strategy as the key research strategy as is it perceived as the appropriate strategy for achieving research objectives. The data required for the current research are collected through physical questionnaires, online questionnaires, and interviews.

3.6. Research Methods

Research methods are tools and techniques regarding the practical implementation of the research (Slevitch, 2011). Williman (2011) notes research methods as techniques to conduct research. Research methods are being stated as tools for data collection by Denscombe (2010) including things like questionnaires, interviews, observation and documents. The author further elaborates that certain methods are associated with certain strategies as the use of survey is often linked with questionnaires being used as a data collection method. Marczyk et al. (2005) state that there are two broad categories of research that researchers are familiar with, qualitative and quantitative, choice of which depends on the research question. Coming to business studies, Greener (2008) is of the view that currently in research it is most likely to see a mix of the two. All three methods are being discussed at length below.

3.6.1. Qualitative Method

Qualitative research is involved with qualitatively studying a phenomenon. This is the case when the phenomena under study involve some qualities or kinds. For instance, when it is to investigate the reasons for human behaviour, through qualitative research, one can study the various aspects which stimulate people to behave in a certain manner or make people adore or dislike a certain thing (Kothari, 2005). Qualitative research is the involvement of studies that do not try to quantify their results through a statistical summary of the analysis. These studies involve interviews, observation without formal measurement, or similar (Marczyk et al., 2005).

Creswell (2007) believes that qualitative investigation characterizes the legitimate mode of social and human science exploration without confession to quantitative analysis and suggests the use of analytical tools such as computer programs. Furthermore, Greener (2008)

states that the qualitative method is associated with the inductive approach and leads to the generation of theory. It also often uses an interpretivist model allowing to have subjective perception and constructs knowledge rather than going for the objectivity of the reality. Creswall (2007) states that regardless of the approach, all qualitative research inclines to follow the basic process of research i.e., introduction, questions, methods of data collection and analysis etc.

3.6.2. Quantitative Method

Quantitative research deals with numbers involving making use of statistics systematically to attain the findings (Marczyk et al., 2005). Kumar (2011) states that a study is considered quantitative if one wants to quantify the variation in a phenomenon, situation or problem. It is based on measurements applicable only to phenomena that can be specified in expressions of quantity (Kothari, 2004).

With quantitative research the investigator recognises what he/she is searching for, all features of the study are sensibly planned before data collection starts (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014). Greener (2008) is of the view that the quantitative method is associated with the deductive approach to test theories by using numbers or facts and leads to the objective view of the phenomenon being studied. Here researcher utilises instruments such as questionnaire to collect data, which is a more effective way to test hypotheses, but the researcher manages to be separated objectively from the subject matter (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014). Gummerson (2001) states that quantitative analysis is bound by some rules but not fully as it gets influenced by subjective and intersubjective notions and verdict calls. Table 3.1 presents the distinctions between the features of qualitative and quantitative research.

TABLE 3-1: QUALITATIVE VS QUANTITATIVE

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Qualitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Describes intangible characteristics (Williman, 2011)• Done at the more personal level (Merriam, 2009)• Leads to theory development (Kolb, 2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analysis is time-consuming (Bryman & Burgess, 1994)• Hard to assemble a study sample (Gummerson, 2001)• Subjective in nature (McCusker & Gunaydin, 2014)
Quantitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Builds cause-effect relationships (Bells, 2010)• More popular among researchers (Gummerson, 2001)• Requires extensive data manipulation to be useful (Saunders et al., 2016)• Leads to objectivity than subjective interpretation (McCusker & Gunaydin, 2014)• More preliminary steps are involved (Kumar, 2011)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Requires statistical software packages to be performed (Daniel, 2016)• Not sufficient on its own, Requires qualitative to elaborate (Gummerson, 2001)• Data collection is needed to be extensive to allow generalisation (Morgan, 1998)• Same conditions cannot be guaranteed for all respondents (Baxter and Jack 2008)

3.6.3. Mixed Methods

Denscombe (2010) refers to the term mixed-methods as a method that is a combination of both qualitative and quantitative research. Also, Easterby-Smith et al. (2015) highlight that, recently, there has been a high interest to adopt research methods that draw from both positivist and constructionist epistemologies that combine both quantitative and qualitative methods in the same investigation. In addition, he points out two types of data is available for collection, primary and secondary with primary being considered more reliable. If the research is related to human beings it often combines the examination of both qualitative and quantitative data (Willman, 2011). This view is supported by McCusker and Gunaydin (2014)

recalling that numerous studies have been conducted in the field of human research utilising both quantitative and qualitative methodologies.

According to Abutabenjeh (2018), the research methods comprise of various components a) data collection, b) analysis and c) interpretation. Furthermore, the investigator may apply quantitative methods like close-ended questions or numeric data in the collection of data and then utilise statistical analysis to obtain the desired outcomes. On the other hand, an investigator may follow qualitative methods like open-ended questions or interviews in data collection and utilise image and text analysis or themes and patterns interpretation to get desired result or researcher may mix various methods for data collection, analysis and interpretation to get their results (Abutabenjeh, 2018). One should remember that combining both data can be time-consuming and expensive (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014).

3.6.4. Selected research Method and Justifications

Three research methods, namely qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods were discussed above. As this research aims to examine the Pakistani textile businesses and their customers, this involves both parties – one interviewed and the other surveyed, the mixed methods is considered useful for addressing both subjective and objective natures of this research. As stated by Denscombe (2010), the term mixed method research is the combination of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. It is to be noticed that mixed-methods consists of both quantitative and qualitative analyses; in this research, it is the latter that forms a major part of the study. The mixed-methods approach can provide numerous benefits when investigating complex research questions as the researcher is able to investigate the phenomenon both subjectively and objectively.

In mixed-methods research, an in-depth understanding of the survey responses can be achieved through qualitative data (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014). Interviews are valuable tools in social science research, and if executed effectively, a researcher can abstract a rich set of relevant information from the participants (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). According to Robson (2011), unstructured and semi-structured interviews are beneficial in the discovery of new insights and patterns. As there are limited studies conducted in the Pakistani textile industry, a qualitative method was considered appropriate for identifying new themes. On the other hand, as this research also incorporates the views of customers, the quantitative method

was considered suitable for identifying findings that are generalizable. Thus, a mixed-methods research design was the most preferred research design for this research.

Numerous previous studies also used mixed-methods research design for investigating similar phenomena. For example, Alexander (2012) adopted a mixed-methods approach to explore how value co-creation at railway stations might affect passenger behaviour, and what is the impact of trust and equity in co-created exchanges. Besides, Dessart et al. (2016) conducted a mixed methods research comprising of interviews and questionnaires surveys to advance the conceptualisation and operationalisation of consumer engagement in the context of online brand communities. Similarly, to examine the role of customer engagement experiences in a satisfaction-loyalty relationship in the digital business environment, Thakur (2019) undertook a mixed methods research design, which adopted a qualitative study to identify the relevant engagement experiences and a quantitative study to evaluate proposed relationships. In order to develop a consumer engagement scale, Vivek (2009) applied mixed methods design comprising of a variety of qualitative techniques to explore the nature, dimensions and scope of consumer engagement, and using data collection instruments field interviews with executives, focus groups, participant observations, and analysis of online contents. Additionally, Ahn and Back (2018) also used a mixed-methods research design to identify the main antecedents and consequences of customer brand engagement in the integrated resort context. In the Russian hotel industry, Oyner and Korelina (2016) applied a mixed-methods design to investigate the influence of customer engagement in value co-creation and customer satisfaction. Considering the nature of variables of this research, and comparing them with the variables used by past studies, a mixed-methods research design was considered the best fit for this research.

A detailed assessment of patterns of responses can be attained through statistical analysis (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014). According to Collis and Hussey (2014), in social science research, questionnaires are very common techniques for data collection. Sekaran & Bougie (2016) states that questionnaires are considered highly important in business research as it allows researchers to extract relevant and accurate data in a cost-effective way. Questionnaires are classified into two types of personally-administered (Saunders et al., 2016) and electronic questionnaires (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). As a part of mixed-methods research, this research incorporates quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interviews for primary data collection.

3.7. Pilot study

The mini version of full-scale research is termed a pilot study, it comprises pre-testing of specific research tools like questionnaire or interviews (Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). According to Glass (1997), a pilot study should be considered as research and advancement actions in all research; guidelines should be followed but not very rigorous procedures being taken into consideration. Furthermore, not all pilot studies being treated in a similar way some require more firmness than the others. According to Kim (2010), a pilot study helps in assessing if the variables and actions are operationalised to an accurate level.

An effective pilot study helps the researcher to save time and money by making sure that the measurement instruments are precise prior to a conduct a large-scale study. A pilot study was conducted during this research prior to collecting both qualitative and quantitative data. To refine the data collection instruments, views of the pilot survey participants were collected, and changes were made in the data collection process. Chapter 4 details the procedures followed during pilot surveys and changes made following the analysis of data collected through pilot surveys.

3.8. Data Collection

As a crucial step in all research projects, data collection helps a researcher to empirically examine the hypothesis established through literature review. According to Collis and Hussey (2014), the process of data collection is of two types: primary and secondary. Saunders et al. (2016) point out that the term primary data denotes researchers collecting data directly from original sources and on the other hand, secondary data collection signifies the collection of data from published or existing sources.

For this research, two primary data collection methods are being employed for primary data collection, namely interviews and questionnaire. In order to collect meaningful data, it is critical to know the target population and sampling frames (Wilson,2014). The next sections offer explanations on different sampling techniques and on the adopted ones for this research.

3.8.1. Sampling Methods

To answer research questions, it is not possible for researchers to collect data from all cases, so they opt to collect the sample from the population (Taherdoost, 2016). It is a subset of the

whole population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The sampling methods comprises of two main types: probability sampling and non-probability sampling and are discussed below.

3.8.1.1. Probability Sampling

According to Taherdoost (2016), probability sampling refers to each item in the population gets an equal opportunity of inclusion in the sample. Zikmund (2002) states that a researcher can conduct random sampling by constructing a sampling frame first and later utilising a random number generation computer software to choose a sample from the sample frame. Brown (1947) stated that probability sampling offers freedom from unfairness but may signify the costliest sample with regards to the time and energy of a given level of sampling error. Probability samples comprise of subcategories comprises of systematic sampling, simple random sampling, cluster sampling, stratified random sampling and multi-stage sampling.

3.8.1.2. Non-probability Sampling

Non-probability sampling refers to the probability of elements in the research that cannot be specified (Collis and Hussey, 2014). According to Taherdoost (2016), case study research design and qualitative research are usually associated with non-probability sampling. Yin (2003) states that case studies incline toward small samples and are interested in examining a real-life phenomenon instead of making statistical inferences with regards to a larger population. According to Fricker (2008), non-probability sampling faces criticism as not being representative of the whole population. Participation of participants is generally voluntary and only those tend to participate who have a strong interest in taking part in the research question. This leads to data not being representative of the whole population (Easterby-Smith et al. 2015). The non-response bias of non-probability sampling has also led to criticism (Saunders et al., 2016). Data could be less representative of the population due to the high non-response rate. A researcher should also take into account that responses acquired forcefully result in inaccurate information being provided by the respondents.

The non-probability sampling technique in which respondents characteristics are the source of their selection is quota sampling; the overall sample will exhibit similar dispersal of features as the broader population (Davis, 2005). Taherdoost (2016) states snowball sample as a non-probability sampling technique that utilises a limited case to assist in encouraging

others to participate in the research, ultimately enhancing the size of a sample. Furthermore, Breweton and Millward (2001) are of the view that snowball sampling is highly suitable in small populations in which accessibility is an issue due to their restricted nature. Malhotra and Birks (2006) state that snowball sampling is quite time-consuming. Another type of non-probability sampling is convenience sampling which is a selection of participants because they are often easily accessible (Taherdoost, 2016). Within convenience sampling, the researcher can utilise friends and family rather than targeting unknown individuals. It is the least expensive, least time consuming and most convenient (Malhotra and Birks, 2006). Purposive sampling is an approach in which particular situations, individuals or proceedings are selected intentionally in order to acquire vital knowledge that cannot be attained from other choices (Maxwell, 1996). Taherdoost (2016) states that it is where the cases or respondents are included in the sample because they consider that they deserve addition. This technique is ideal for exploratory research but does not allow generalisation (Malhotra and Birks, 2006).

3.8.2. Selected Sample Size and Justifications

A sample design is a plan made before the data collection for obtaining a sample from the given population, sample designs can be either probability or non-probability (Pandey & Pandey, 2015). The researcher decided to choose non-probability sampling after carefully assessing the probability methods time and cost-related constraints (Saunders et al., 2016). A convenience sampling technique is considered appropriate as it is inexpensive, less time consuming and most convenient in comparison to random sampling (Malhotra and Birks, 2006).

Regarding sample size, a total of 11 interviews (each lasting 30 to 45 minutes) was conducted for collecting qualitative research data. Although the researcher planned on interviewing more respondents, the process was terminated early due to reaching data saturation. In terms of the quantitative research, the researcher distributed 550 questionnaires after careful consideration of literature evidence and sample size used by previous researchers. After data cleaning, a total of 332 responses were Identified as fit for further analysis. As Rosco (1975) mentions, a sample size between 30 and 500 is suitable for most quantitative analysis.

3.9. Data Analysis

The complexity of data analysis depends on research questions and objectives (Saunders et al. 2016). According to Collis & Hussey (2014) raw data, particularly quantitative, expressly limited connotations till they are dispensed and analysed. Researchers can get assistance from analytical techniques such as graphs, charts, statistical tools, thematic analysis to discover, present, describe and trends between variables is evaluated.

3.9.1. Quantitative Data Analysis

Before its processing and analysis, quantitative data in a raw form, carry very little value to people; to turn data into information it has to be processed (Saunders et al. 2016). Quantitative data can be analysed in various techniques in order to obtain conclusions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Quantitative analysis techniques such as charts, graphs and statistics let us discover, show, describe and examine associations and variations within our data (Saunders et al. 2016). To analyse quantitative data, a five-stage approach, namely data tidying, assessment of scales, data transformation, descriptive analysis, and inferential analysis (Dawson, 2017) was used in this research. This is further elaborated in Chapter 4 of this thesis.

3.9.2. Qualitative Data Analysis

In order to analyse the research data, thematic analysis was used. Thematic analysis has been described by Hayes (1997) as a wide-ranging procedure through which multiple cross-references between the data the research's developing themes are being identified. According to Boyatzis (1998), it is a form of qualitative analysis, utilised for the analysis of classifications and present themes relating to data; demonstrating the data in detail and addresses various themes through interpretations. The thematic analysis offers a chance to realise the perspective of any problem in detail (Marks and Yardley, 2003). Namey et al. (2008) defined thematic analysis as:

“Thematic Moves beyond counting explicit words or phrases and focuses on identifying and describing both implicit and explicit ideas. Codes developed for ideas or themes are then applied or linked to raw data as summary markers for later analysis, which may include comparing the relative frequencies of themes or topics within a data set, looking for code co-occurrence, or graphically displaying code relationships.”

Alhojailan (2012) states that, through thematic analysis, researchers ascertain the associations between concepts and equate them with the replicated data. It also gives the opportunity of linking different concepts and learners’ opinions and comparing these with the data that has been collected in a separate setting at different periods through the project; all likelihoods for explanation are viable (Alhojailan, 2012). For the analysis of the data, this research precisely followed the thematic analysis model of Miles and Huberman (1994).

3.9.2.1. Thematic Analysis Model of Miles and Huberman

Miles and Huberman (1994) developed a model for the thematic analysis, consisting of three streams i.e., data display, data reduction, and conclusion-drawing/verifying as stated in the picture below.

FIGURE 3-1: THEMATIC ANALYSIS PROCESS

Source: Miles and Huberman (1994)

The process of thematic analysis examines the data without employing established themes, making it to adapt any study that depends on categorisations, testimonies, and concepts to understand the issues that lead to an appreciation of the full picture (Alhojailan, 2012).

Notions are thus crafted to give a full picture of the researcher's opinions and activities, demonstrating resemblances and variances between the respondents viewpoints will contribute the leaders to attain a worldwide view (Joffe and Yardley, 2004; Blacker, 2009). Below, the steps outlined in Miles & Huberman (1994)'s model are discussed:

a. Data Reduction

Miles & Huberman (1994) highlighted data reduction as the first step in qualitative data analysis. This process comprises selection, simplification and transformation of data (Alhojailan, 2012). According to Miles & Huberman (1994) decreasing and transforming data in qualitative research can be accomplished in various methods. It could be by selecting, by summarizing or paraphrasing, and through being incorporated in a larger outline. The process of reducing data is processed in such a way that conclusion is drawn, and checks are finalised. Coding is immersed through allocating table units to the data that could be gathered from the respondents irrespective of a single announcement or a lengthy reply (Alhojailan, 2012). Different parts of data can be connected in thematic analysis with the help of coding (Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). Coding allows the investigator to assess the full of data by classifying its most important meaning or the main idea (Halldorson 2009; Coffey and Atkinson 1996). As a part of the data reduction process, the collected research data was summarised and codes were generated, which eventually helped to visualise the data and form narrations.

b. Data Display

Miles and Huberman (1994: 59) defined data display as “*an organised, compressed, assembly of information that permits conclusion drawing and action*”. This stage focuses on data visualisation by applying several different display methods, comprising of narrative text, citations, statistics, charting, variances and resemblances and simplifying the association incorporating its related complications of data (Gibbs 2002; Yin 2015). The usage of various data display methods crafts the description of the comparison and similarities visible; it also enhances the total consistency of the research in making it valid for other investigators. As a part of the data display process, developed codes during the data reduction process were carefully analysed and sub-themes themes were developed.

c. Data Drawing and Conclusions

Miles and Huberman (1994) suggested that data drawing and conclusion is the final stage of qualitative data analysis. They state that the utilisation of some points can assist researchers in drawing conclusions. These include:

- The representation of any outlines or themes and significance of any declaration particularly if similar or conflicting.
- Assembling or forming classifications of “information that can go together”
- Finding links among components and variables.
- Constructing conceptual logic and uniformity

In this part of the analysis, the generated sub-themes and themes were carefully scrutinised and relationships between them were assessed in the precise context of research to draw conclusions. Thematic analysis delivers a complete course for an investigator to categorise several references between the developing themes and the whole data (Hayes 1997). Cross-referencing and critical examination of the data helped the researcher to identify insights that were critical for achieving the research objectives.

3.10. Validity

Research validity ensures that the result outcomes are true representative of what they seem (Saunders et al., 2016). In order to establish the measurements instruments operationalised in the research are true and indeed capable of measuring the research variables accurately, consideration of the research validity aspect is essential in any research (Saunders et al. 2016). Content validity an important aspect of validity, it assesses whether the measurement encompasses related representatives items for measuring variables. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), superior content validity can be attained by enhancing the entire sum of measurement items. In this research, in order to attain content validity, pre-established scales were considered. In order to measure the consumers’ value co-creation attitude, the scale operationalised by Shamim et al. (2017) whilst the scale operationalised by Vivek et al. (2014) and Hollebeek et al. (2014) was used for measuring the consumer brand engagement.

In order to ascertain the validity of the qualitative data, interview questions were designed after thoroughly reviewing the previous studies in the area of research as well as the

questions used by those studies for collecting their primary data. As it is extremely hard to quantify content validity and face validity (Dawson, 2017), expert opinions were considered to safeguard these. According to Netemeyer et al. (2003), face validity and content validity are considered as the elements of translation validity. The measurement instruments designed were discussed with an expert and their suggestions were incorporated in the study.

3.11. Reliability

Reliability has been defined by Collis & Hussey (2014) as a vital feature of a study as it evaluates the consistency of responses. Reliability assessment accurately assesses the replicability of findings (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) to verify that if the research is repeated, it will generate similar outcomes (Collis and Hussey, 2014). According to Netemeyer et al (2003), “internal consistency examines the degree to which responses are consistent across the items with a measure”.

In this research, for assessing the internal consistency of the measurement scales, Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated. Cronbach (1951) presented Cronbach's alpha (α) index which can be utilised for the assessment of internal consistency of scales. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), Cronbach's coefficient alpha is a widely adopted approach for measuring internal consistency in modern studies for reliability assessment. A higher coefficient alpha determines a more reliable measurement instrument (Dawson, 2017). To assess multiple item-scale, internal reliability *Cronbach's alpha coefficient* is widely implemented. The acceptable value for Cronbach's alpha is 0.70 or higher (Hair et al., 2010). Furthermore, Kline (2011) states that reliability coefficients around 0.90 are deemed excellent while around 0.70 are agreeable and lower than 0.70 are considered as poor coefficient reliability. In this research, Cronbach's coefficient alpha of the measurement scales is calculated for ensuring the integrity of this research and the measurement scale was identified as highly reliable with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.939. Details are provided on the procedures taken during the analysis of internal consistency in Chapter 4.2 of this thesis.

3.12. Ethical Considerations

Research ethics concerns the way research topic is framed and explained, research is designed, access obtained, data is gathered, processed, stored and analysed and how should research findings be presented ensuring morality and responsibility (Saunders et al. 2016).

Hollway & Jefferson (2000) found a number of ethical issues that an academic researcher or student could face. The fundamental issue is to ensure data confidentiality and anonymity of respondents while proportionating and keeping a distinct environment to avoid biases. Fulfilling the ethical values and promising confidentiality and anonymity enhances the reliability of findings (Saunders et al. 2016).

Prior to collecting the research data, an extensive research plan was submitted to the ethics committee at the University of West of Scotland. The researcher was provided with an ethical clearance by the committee. In terms of data collection, the vast majority of data was collected remotely. Participants were provided with the participant consent sheet that consisted of detailed information about the research. No participants were physically or psychologically affected due to the nature of this research. To deal with the issue of sensitivity of the topic in terms of sharing stories or defining processes, the researcher aimed to keep the questions confined to the customer engagement value co-creation processes (Saunders et al. 2016).

The participants were ensured regarding the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Personal data that could lead to the identification of participants (i.e., name, address, exact age, ID numbers) were not collected. Participants were allowed to skip the questions in case of feeling uncomfortable and participation in the survey was voluntary. To avoid misinterpretation, researcher information was given to the participants, they were suggested to contact the researcher (via university email) in case if they have any confusion.

Only the researcher and his director of studies had access to raw data. Physically collected questionnaires are stored in a locked environment and will be destroyed after the successful completion of this research. Electronically collected data are stored in a password-protected computer and will be utilised for data analysis purposes only. No third party will have access to this data under any circumstances. Only the participants aged 18 or over were allowed to participate.

3.13. Conclusions

This chapter outlined the suitable research philosophy and methods in order to facilitate the answering of research questions in an organised manner. It was decided to choose pragmatic philosophy encompassing both positivist and interpretivist philosophies after careful

considerations of all key research philosophies. As value co-creation has both subjective and objective nature, and in the context of Pakistan is under-discussed in the literature, the abductive approach was chosen to explore emerging themes qualitatively and produced findings quantitatively which are replicable and generalizable.

In order to collect the research data, a decision was made to select the survey strategy by utilising instruments such as questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. For the purpose of data collection, non-probability sampling was considered. This chapter helped in understanding the theoretical foundations in relation to various research techniques. The subsequent chapter presents the details involving the collection and analysis of primary data along with the findings.

4. DATA ANALYSES AND FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to highlight and explain the strategies adopted for the collection and analysis of the research data. This chapter elaborates upon how different instruments of data collection such as pilot interviews, pilot questionnaires, main interviews, and main questionnaires were used for collecting data that is robust and reliable. In this chapter, quantitative and qualitative research findings are presented individually. The earlier part of the chapter deals with quantitative data analysis and findings whilst the latter deals with qualitative data analysis and findings.

4.2. Quantitative Data Analysis and Findings

Saunders et al. (2016) state that, to conduct a quantitative analysis of research data, a researcher should consider the followings: the type of data, arrangement in which data will be inserted into the software, effect of data coding on subsequent analyses, need to weigh cases, methods intended to use to check data for errors. Sekaran & Bougie (2016) suggest that after acquiring data from questionnaires, they need to be coded, keyed-in, and edited. Below, procedures followed during the data collection and analysis are detailed.

4.2.1. Pilot Study

In order to ensure that the scales used for the collection of the research data are reliable, a decision was made to contact a pilot study. The researcher conducted a pilot study by deploying Google Forms. The questionnaire was sent to a total of 43 potential respondents and a total of 32 respondents. After a careful review of all responses, a total of 30 responses were identified as valid.

Respondents were also requested for their suggestions related to further improving the questionnaire. Some of the respondents suggested that the questions used in the questionnaire were difficult to understand. As such a questionnaire could have affected not only the response rate but also the way in which the respondents understood the questions, a decision was made to further simplify the questions by replacing academic terms with easily understandable words. Once the data was collected, it was coded into SPSS and its reliability was assessed.

4.2.1.1. Reliability Analysis of the Pilot Survey

Reliability has been described by Collis & Hussey (2014) as a vital feature of research as it evaluates the consistency of responses. To assess multiple item-scale, internal reliability Cronbach's alpha coefficient is widely implemented. Cronbach (1951) presented Cronbach's alpha (α) index which can be utilised for the assessment of internal consistency of scales.

Collis & Hussey (2014) states that a measurement scale can be counted as acceptable with a Cronbach's alpha (α) value greater than or equal to 0.8. Other researchers have indicated that scales with Cronbach's alpha(α) value greater than or equal to 0.7 as reliable (Nunnally, 1978; Hair et al., 2010; Al-Eisawi, 2014; Bagale, 2019). In this research, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the measurement was measured using SPSS software. The combined scales internal reliability was calculated as Cronbach's alpha (α) .810. This suggests that the measurement scale used in this research is reliable. Table 4.1 presents the findings of reliability analysis.

TABLE 4-1: RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE PILOT SURVEY

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	30	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	30	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.810	25

Source: The Author

4.2.2. Main Data Collection and Analysis

4.2.2.1. Main Data Collection Processes

Primary data was collected by using both physically administered questionnaires and online surveys. For online surveys, a questionnaire was coded into Google Forms and distributed through various electronic mediums such as email, instant messaging, and social media. Recruiting respondents through social media to participate in the electronic survey is the most affordable and effective way. It is a widely adopted approach in business research (Ashley & Tuten, 2014). On the other hand, some of the questionnaires were also physically distributed. An assistant of the researcher physically distributed questionnaires to the consumers in the Pakistani textile industry and collected their responses. Approximately, 500 questionnaires were distributed digitally whilst 50 were administered physically.

The majority of the distribution was done digitally after giving careful consideration to the safety of both the researcher and participants. Besides electronic distribution was considered appropriate as it provides respondents with ease of time and device, which can enhance the reliability of data. To collect data, this research adopted strategies of reaching respondents through different Facebook groups. Facebook was considered a good platform for reaching a wider range of participants as over 37 million people in Pakistan actively use Facebook (Anjum, 2020). Additionally, nearly all textile retailers in Pakistan have Facebook pages where they engage with their consumers on a daily basis.

4.2.2.2. Data Coding and Editing

For the analysis of research data, SPSS software was utilised. SPSS is a vastly used software for data analysis in management and social sciences (Dawson, 2017). As previously mentioned, Google Forms were used to collect a vast majority of responses. The collected data was then inserted into SPSS and carefully examined, and cross-checked to ensure that all data was accurately entered. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), at least 10 percent of data should be cross-examined for making sure that data is correctly transferred. Over 50 responses were reviewed, and no inaccuracy was found.

Some of the responses consisted of a high number of missing values. Sekaran & Bougie (2016) suggest that responses with over 25% missing values should be omitted from the

dataset. Therefore, any response that contained over 25% missing values was omitted. After administering the data editing procedures, only 332 (45 physically collected and 287 digitally collected) were considered fit for further analysis. In order to further ascertain the reliability of measurement scales, reliability testing was conducted on the main research data.

4.2.2.3. Reliability Analysis of the Main Data

Once the main research data was collected, a reliability analysis was conducted once again to ascertain the internal consistency of the scales. The tables below present the findings:

TABLE 4-2: RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN SURVEY

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	332	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	332	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.939	25

Source: The Author

As observed in table 4.2, the analysis suggested the dataset as reliable with a Cronbach Alpha value of .939, indicating the dataset is fit for further analysis. The next section now presents descriptive findings.

4.2.3. Descriptive Findings

4.2.3.1. Gender of the Respondents

TABLE 4-3: GENDER

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	111	33.4	33.4	33.4
	Male	176	53.0	53.0	86.4
	Prefer not to say	45	13.6	13.6	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

As presented in table 4.3, a majority of the respondents (53%) identified themselves as male whilst one-third (33.4%) of respondents identified themselves as females. A total of 45 respondents (13.6%) preferred not to reveal their gender identity.

4.2.3.2. Age of the Respondents

TABLE 4-4: AGE

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	103	31.0	31.0	31.0
	25-34	138	41.6	41.6	72.6
	35-44	76	22.9	22.9	95.5
	45-54	9	2.7	2.7	98.2
	55-64	5	1.5	1.5	99.7
	65+	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

A large number of the respondents (41.66%) were from the 25-34 age category, while 31% of the respondents represented the 18-24 age group and 22.9% represented the 35-44 age group

category. Only 5 (1.5%) of respondents were of group 55-64 and 1 respondent (.3 %) represented the age group 65+. The limited participation of elderly participants could have occurred due to most of the data being collected online.

4.2.3.3. Income of the Respondents

TABLE 4-5: INCOME

Income					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 20K	41	12.3	12.3	12.3
	20K-40K	53	16.0	16.0	28.3
	40K-70K	50	15.1	15.1	43.4
	70K-100K	28	8.4	8.4	51.8
	100K+	39	11.7	11.7	63.6
	Prefer not to say	121	36.4	36.4	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

Table 4.5 presents the income of the individuals who took part in the survey; only 12.3% of respondents belonged to the least earning income category while 16% of people had an income between 20K-40K and 15.1% earned 40K-70K. The higher income categories of 70K-100K were represented by 28 respondents (8.4%) and 100K+ by 39 respondents (11.7%). A large number of respondents (36.4%) preferred not to disclose their income.

4.2.3.4. Education of the Respondents

TABLE 4-6: EDUCATION

Education					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid					
	School	12	3.6	3.6	3.9
	College	34	10.2	10.2	14.2
	Bachelors	125	37.7	37.7	51.8
	Masters and Above	156	47.0	47.0	98.8
	No Formal Education	4	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

Nearly all of the participants had some form of formal education: 156 respondents (47.0%) had education at the master's level and above while 125 respondents (37.7%) had a bachelor's degree. Only 4 (1.2%) participants had no formal education. If the respondents are highly educated, it indicates that data is highly reliable, mainly because respondents are more likely to understand the question and provide accurate answers.

4.2.3.5. Professions of the Respondents

TABLE 4-7: PROFESSIONS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Writers/Journalists	4	1.2	1.2	1.2
	Admin	36	10.8	10.8	12.0
	Academic	75	22.6	22.6	34.6
	Fashion Designer	14	4.2	4.2	38.9
	IT	20	6.0	6.0	44.9
	Law	31	9.3	9.3	54.2
	Others	152	45.8	45.8	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

The profession of the respondents is presented in the table 4.7. Out of the 332 respondents who took part in the survey, 4 respondents (1.2%) identified themselves as Writer/Journalists, while some 36 respondents (10.8%) worked in the administration. The smallest category of the respondents (4.2%) is fashion designers. During the survey, a large number of respondents (45.8%) selected ‘others’ as they worked in fields not covered in the list provided.

4.2.3.6. Favourite brand of the Respondents

TABLE 4-8: FAVOURITE BRANDS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Khaadi	70	21.1	21.1	21.1
	Bareeze	19	5.7	5.7	26.8
	Junaid Jamshed	85	25.6	25.6	52.4
	Gul ahmed	76	22.9	22.9	75.3
	Sapphire	28	8.4	8.4	83.7
	Other	54	16.3	16.3	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

Out of 332 respondents, 85 respondents (25.6%) chose Junaid Jamshed as their favourite brand whilst only,19 respondents (5%) had chosen Bareeze as their favourite brand. Other customers participating in the survey chose Khaadi (21.1%), Gul Ahmed (22.9%) and Sapphire (8.4%) as their favourite brand. Table 4.8 suggests that the majority of the respondents selected their favourite brand from the list provided in the table.

4.2.3.7. Shopping frequency of respondents

TABLE 4-9: SHOPPING FREQUENCY

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Weekly	7	2.1	2.1	2.1
	Monthly	77	23.2	23.2	25.3
	Once in 3 Months	146	44.0	44.0	69.3
	Every year or less	102	30.7	30.7	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Author

The data suggests that least number of respondents (2.1%) shop their favourite brand weekly, while 23.2% shop their favourite brand on a monthly basis. 44% respondents shopped once in three months whilst 30.7% purchased from their favourite brand only once a year or less.

4.2.4. Descriptive Analysis of the Research Variables

While conducting primary data collection, ordinal Likert-scales were developed for measuring seven variables of this research, namely Interaction Attitude, Knowledge Sharing, Responsive Attitude, Conscious Attention, Cognitive Engagement, Affective Engagement and Enthused Participation. Each variable was measured using multiple Likert-scale statements.

According to Dawson (2017), if measurement scales have good reliability and validity, a set of appropriate categorical figures (e.g., Likert Scale) can resemble into numerical data. Ordinal data is the commonly encountered category of data in the social sciences (Chen and Wang, 2014). Transforming ordinal data into numerical scales not only generates measurement scores for individual variables but also offers statistical flexibility. Wilson (2014) states that mean, median and mode can be calculated to describe the data if data is in interval mode. After carefully considering the high reliability and validity of measurement scales, a decision was made to upgrade the categorical data into interval data. This was done by computing measurement items related to each variable into a new variable. The average of

measurement items represented the new variables. Table 4.10 presents a descriptive analysis of the new variables.

TABLE 4-10: DESCRIPTIVE FINDINGS OF RESEARCH VARIABLES

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Interaction Attitude	332	1.00	4.75	3.3870	.56627
Knowledge Sharing	332	1.00	5.00	3.3775	.79190
Responsive Attitude	332	1.00	5.00	3.7485	.67765
Conscious Attention	332	1.00	5.00	3.6396	.76750
Cognitive Engagement	332	1.00	5.00	3.5833	.81119
Affective Engagement	332	1.00	5.00	3.8253	.71082
Enthusied Participation	332	1.00	5.00	3.6175	.73464
Valid N (listwise)	332				

Source: The Author

As presented in table 4.10, within value co-creation attitude, RA (3.74) has a marginally higher mean than CA (3.63), IA (3.38) and KS (3.37). KS possess the lowest mean but has the highest dispersion (SD=0.79). On the other hand, within customer engagement, AE (3.82) has the highest mean, while EP (3.61) has a higher mean than CE (3.58) which also has the highest dispersion (SD=0.81). The next section of this chapter now assesses the relationships between different variables using inferential statistics in order to answer the research objectives.

4.2.5. Inferential Analysis and Findings

In order to draw inferences about a population, inferential analysis is used (Wilson, 2014). Two approaches, namely parametric and non-parametric (Collis & Hussey, 2014) can be used for analysing quantitative data. Parametric tests are bound to certain assumptions whilst non-parametric tests are free from assumptions. According to Field (2013), if data is not normally distributed and are not in either ratio or interval mode, parametric tests should be avoided. Gay (1976) states that a non-parametric test is used when the data represent an ordinal or

nominal scale, once a parametric supposition has been defied, or the distribution nature is not identified.

To draw inferences about the population, non-parametric tests are used in this research (Collis & Hussey, 2014). This research used a convenience sampling technique, where sampling is not random, Field (2013) suggests using non-parametric tests. Besides, an assessment of the data indicated the data is not normally distributed, further approving the suitability of non-parametric tests.

As a part of non-parametric tests, this research employs cross-tabulation and spearman correlation for testing research hypotheses. To test the statistical significance of the cross-tabulation, Chi-square tests have been conducted. According to Kothari (2007), Chi-square represented as χ^2 , is suitable when the data is in an arrangement of frequency sums happening in binary or more jointly special groups. Similarly, Spearman-rho correlation assesses the strengths of the relationship between two or more variables. The section 4.2.6 now presents the research hypotheses as well as the findings or analysis.

4.2.6. Hypotheses Testing

In order to achieve the research objectives, multiple hypotheses were outlined in chapter two of this thesis. Table 4.11 presents the hypotheses of this research:

TABLE 4-11: RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

No	Hypotheses	Tests
H1	H1 ₀ : There is no statistically significant relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes in the Pakistani textile sector. H1 ₁ : There is a statistically significant relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes in the Pakistani textile sector.	Spearman Correlation
H2A	H2A ₀ : There is no statistically significant relationship between shopper's age and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector. H2A ₁ : There is a statistically significant relationship between shopper's age and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector.	Chi-Square Test
H2B	H2B ₀ : There is no statistically significant relationship between shopper's gender and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector. H2B ₁ : There is a statistically significant relationship between shopper's gender and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector.	Chi-Square Test
H1C	H2C ₀ : There is no statistically significant relationship between shopper's income and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector. H2C ₁ : There is a statistically significant relationship between shopper's income and shopping frequency in the Pakistani textile sector.	Chi-Square Test

Source: The Author

4.2.6.1. Testing of Hypothesis 1: the relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes

The second research hypothesis (H1) was developed to examine the relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes. In order to identify the statistical associations, Spearman Correlations tests were conducted. The Spearman rank correlation coefficient (Spearman ρ) is a non-parametric measurement correlation and was used to determine the relationship existing between two sets of data (Deming, 1990; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). According to Field (2018), the small effect is represented by coefficient ± 0.1 while medium and large effects are represented by ± 0.3 and ± 0.5 . It can

be interpreted as describing anything between no association ($\rho = 0$) to a perfect monotonic relationship ($\rho = -1$ or $+1$) (Schober et al. 2018).

The first part of table 4.12 present the findings of correlation analysis between research variables customer engagement and customer’s value co-creation attitudes whilst the second part presents the correlation analysis of different dimensions of both variables.

TABLE 4-12: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT AND CUSTOMER’S VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES

Correlations				
			Customer Engagement	Value Co Creation Attitude
Spearman's rho	Customer Brand Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.677**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	332	332
	Value Co-Creation Attitude	Correlation Coefficient	.677**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	332	332
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Correlations									
			IA	KS	RA	CA	CE	AE	EP
Spearman's rho	Interaction Attitude	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.547**	.363*	.373**	.438**	.316**	.383**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Knowledge Sharing	Correlation Coefficient	.547**	1.000	.543*	.592**	.562**	.448**	.534**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Responsive Attitude	Correlation Coefficient	.363**	.543**	1.000	.570**	.527**	.504**	.446**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Conscious Attention	Correlation Coefficient	.373**	.592**	.570*	1.000	.646**	.564**	.571**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Cognitive Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	.438**	.562**	.527*	.646**	1.000	.664**	.708**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Affective Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	.316**	.448**	.504*	.564**	.664**	1.000	.666**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332
	Enthusied Participation	Correlation Coefficient	.383**	.534**	.446*	.571**	.708**	.666**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	332	332	332	332	332	332	332

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: The Author

As presented in the table 4.12, customer brand engagement had large size effects on value co-creation attitude, $r = 0.677$, $p < 0.05$ (0.000). This indicates that customers that engage with brands and a regular basis are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities. Based

on this evidence, the alternative hypothesis (H_{11}) was accepted, and the null hypothesis (H_{10}) was rejected.

4.2.6.2. Testing of Hypothesis 2A: the relationship between shopper's age and shopping frequency

This research hypothesis was developed to examine the relationship between respondents age and their shopping frequency. In order to identify the statistical associations, crosstabulation and Chi-square test were conducted. Table 4.13 presents the findings of the tests.

TABLE 4-13: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESPONDENTS AGE AND THEIR SHOPPING FREQUENCY

			Cross-tabulation				Total
			How often do you shop with your favourite brand				
			Weekly	Monthly	Once in 3 Months	Every year or less	
Age	18-24	Count	2	30	39	32	103
		Expected Count	2.2	23.9	45.3	31.6	103.0
		% within Age	1.9%	29.1%	37.9%	31.1%	100.0%
	25-34	Count	2	32	59	45	138
		Expected Count	2.9	32.0	60.7	42.4	138.0
		% within Age	1.4%	23.2%	42.8%	32.6%	100.0%
	35-44	Count	1	14	42	19	76
		Expected Count	1.6	17.6	33.4	23.3	76.0
		% within Age	1.3%	18.4%	55.3%	25.0%	100.0%
	45-54	Count	2	0	2	5	9
		Expected Count	.2	2.1	4.0	2.8	9.0
		% within Age	22.2%	0.0%	22.2%	55.6%	100.0%
	55-64	Count	0	1	3	1	5
		Expected Count	.1	1.2	2.2	1.5	5.0
		% within Age	0.0%	20.0%	60.0%	20.0%	100.0%
	65+	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.0	.2	.4	.3	1.0
		% within Age	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	7	77	146	102	332	
	Expected Count	7.0	77.0	146.0	102.0	332.0	
	% within Age	2.1%	23.2%	44.0%	30.7%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.943 ^a	15	.009
Likelihood Ratio	21.837	15	.112
Linear-by-Linear Association	.258	1	.611
N of Valid Cases	332		

Source: The Author

As presented in the table 4.13, a statistically significant difference was found in shopping frequency across customers from different age groups, $X^2 (15, N = 332) = 30.94, p < .05 (.009)$. As identified in the crosstabulation table 4.13, variation in terms of shopping frequency was observed in age groups such as 18-24 and 25-34. 29% of customers in the age group 18 to 24 mentioned that they shop with their favourite brand and a monthly basis, 38% stated that they shop once in three months and 31% stated they shop every year or less. Similarly, in the 25 to 34 age categories, 23% of customers shopped monthly, 43% of customers shopped once every three months, and 32.6% of customers shopped every year or less. As observed, the proportion of consumer that shopped on a weekly basis from both categories was marginal (below 2%).

Although the shopping trend was similar to the consumers in the 35 to 44 age categories, there was a slight variation in terms of purchase frequency. A majority of customers (55.3%) in this age category shopped once in three months on average from their favourite brands. From the same category, only 18.4% of customers shopped on a monthly basis and 25% of customers shopped every year or less. On average, as observed in the table above, it was seen that as people get older, they tend to shop less and less from their favourite brands. As presented in the table above, this research also comprised of respondents of other age groups, such as 45 to 54, 55 to 64, and 65 and above. The findings of these groups were not taken into consideration as they violated the chi-square test assumptions (minimum cell count 5). The above results indicate that there is a negative relationship between customers age and their shopping frequency with their favourite brands.

4.2.6.3. Testing of Hypothesis 2B: *the relationship between shopper's gender and shopping frequency*

Similarly, this research hypothesis (H2B) was developed to examine the relationship between respondents' gender and their shopping frequency. In order to identify the statistical associations, crosstabulation and Chi-square test were conducted. Table 4.14 presents the findings of the tests.

TABLE 4-14: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESPONDENTS' GENDER AND THEIR SHOPPING FREQUENCY

Gender * How often do you shop with your favourite brand Crosstabulation							
			How often do you shop with your favourite brand				Total
			Weekly	Monthly	Once in 3 Months	Every year or less	
Gender	Female	Count	1	32	48	30	111
		% within Gender	0.9%	28.8%	43.2%	27.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	0.3%	9.6%	14.5%	9.0%	33.4%
	Male	Count	5	35	69	67	176
		% within Gender	2.8%	19.9%	39.2%	38.1%	100.0%
		% of Total	1.5%	10.5%	20.8%	20.2%	53.0%
	Prefer not to say	Count	1	10	29	5	45
		% within Gender	2.2%	22.2%	64.4%	11.1%	100.0%
		% of Total	0.3%	3.0%	8.7%	1.5%	13.6%
Total		Count	7	77	146	102	332
		% within Gender	2.1%	23.2%	44.0%	30.7%	100.0%
		% of Total	2.1%	23.2%	44.0%	30.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.016 ^a	6	.006
Likelihood Ratio	19.255	6	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	.007	1	.931
N of Valid Cases	332		
a. 3 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .95.			

Source: The Author

In table 4.14, statistically significant association was identified between shopper's shopping frequency and gender $X^2 (6, N = 332) = 18.02, p < .05 (.006)$. Out of total females, 29% shopped monthly with their favourite brand, while a majority of females, 43.2 % shopped with their favourite brand once in 3 months. It was also identified that 27% of females shopped their brand once a year or less. On average, it was observed that the majority of the female respondents shopped either once a month or every 3 months. In terms of males, on monthly basis, some 19.6% of males bought from their favourite brands, while 39.2% of males bought at least once in 3 months. Also, some 38.1% of males shopped their favourite brand once a year or less.

Comparison of shopping frequency across two groups suggested that females' monthly shopping frequency is higher than males' as 28% of females shopped monthly comparing to only 19.9% males. In terms of the respondent category that shopped once every three months, female shopping frequency is higher than their male's counterparts as well: 43% females shopped with their favourite brands whilst only 39.2% of males shopped their favourite brands. On the other hand, it is observed that the females shopping frequency is lower than males in every year or less section, representing 27% females and 38.1% males. Based on the valid findings of the analysis, it is concluded that, on average, female customers shopped more frequently than men. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (H_{2B1}) accepted, and the corresponding null hypothesis is rejected.

4.2.6.4. Testing of Hypothesis 2C: the relationship between shopper's income and shopping frequency

Hypothesis 2C was developed to examine the relationship between respondents' income and their shopping frequency. In order to identify the statistical associations, crosstabulation and Chi-square test were conducted. The tables below present the findings of the tests.

TABLE 4-15: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESPONDENTS' INCOME AND THEIR SHOPPING FREQUENCY

Monthly Income (In PKR) * How often do you shop with your favourite brand Crosstabulation							
			How often do you shop with your favourite brand				Total
			Weekly	Monthly	Once in 3 Months	Every year or less	
Monthly Income (In PKR)	Below 20K	Count	3	7	15	16	41
		Expected Count	.9	9.5	18.0	12.6	41.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	7.3%	17.1%	36.6%	39.0%	100.0%
	20K-40K	Count	1	6	26	20	53
		Expected Count	1.1	12.3	23.3	16.3	53.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	1.9%	11.3%	49.1%	37.7%	100.0%
	40K-70K	Count	1	11	24	14	50
		Expected Count	1.1	11.6	22.0	15.4	50.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	2.0%	22.0%	48.0%	28.0%	100.0%
	70K-100K	Count	0	10	10	8	28
		Expected Count	.6	6.5	12.3	8.6	28.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	0.0%	35.7%	35.7%	28.6%	100.0%
	100K+	Count	1	11	15	12	39
		Expected Count	.8	9.0	17.2	12.0	39.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	2.6%	28.2%	38.5%	30.8%	100.0%
	Prefer not to say	Count	1	32	56	32	121
		Expected Count	2.6	28.1	53.2	37.2	121.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	0.8%	26.4%	46.3%	26.4%	100.0%
	Total	Count	7	77	146	102	332
		Expected Count	7.0	77.0	146.0	102.0	332.0
		% within Monthly Income (In PKR)	2.1%	23.2%	44.0%	30.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.150 ^a	15	.255
Likelihood Ratio	17.410	15	.295
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.118	1	.146
N of Valid Cases	332		
a. 6 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .59.			

Source: The Author

As presented in table 4.15, a statistically insignificant relationship was identified between a shopper’s shopping frequency and income level $X^2 (15, N = 332) = 18.15, p > .05 (.255)$. Although the variations were not statistically significant, some variations were observed in the sample; for example, in the category of respondents earning below 20K, 17.1% bought with their favourite brand monthly, 36.6% bought only once in 3 months, and 39% bought from their favourite brand every year or less. Whilst in the income category of 20K-40K, only 11.3% of respondents shopped monthly, 49.1% shopped once in 3 months, and some 37.7% of respondents shopped every year or less. Although the data suggested some marginal variations across different income groups, the variations were not statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis (H2C₀). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (H2C₁) was rejected.

In order to further understand the difference in consumers’ value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across different categories of the demographic factors, multiple ANOVA tests were conducted. As previously stated, a non-probability sampling technique was used for collecting the research data and the collected data were not normally distributed; hence, non-parametric tests were used for the analysis of the research data. To assess the differences in consumers’ value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across different categories of the demographic factors, Kruskal-Wallis one-way ANOVA tests were used. The next section presents the findings.

4.2.6.5. The differences in the customers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across different income categories

In the table 4.16, the first part presents the mean ranks of consumers' value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across five different income categories: below 20K, 20K-40K, 40K-70K, 70K-100K, and 100K+. Whereas, the second part presents the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis H one-way ANOVA test.

TABLE 4-16: CONSUMERS' VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS INCOME CATEGORIES

Ranks			
	Monthly Income (In PKR)	N	Mean Rank
Value Co-creation Attitude	Below 20K	41	98.06
	20K-40K	53	111.33
	40K-70K	50	102.79
	70K-100K	28	118.77
	100K+	39	102.05
	Total	211	
Customer Brand Engagement	Below 20K	41	92.01
	20K-40K	53	105.36
	40K-70K	50	113.69
	70K-100K	28	111.96
	100K+	39	107.44
	Total	211	

Test Statistics^{a,b}		
	Value Co-creation	Customer Brand Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	2.625	3.245
df	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.622	.518
a. Kruskal Wallis Test		
b. Grouping Variable: Monthly Income (In PKR)		

Source: The Author

As presented in table 4.16, the differences in consumers' value co-creation attitudes and the level of consumer brand engagement across five different income categories (below 20K, n = 41; 20K-40K, n = 53; 40K-70K, n = 50; 70K-100K, n = 28; 100K+, n = 39) were identified as statistically insignificant with P-Values 0.622 and 0.518 respectively. These findings indicate that, in the specific context of the Pakistani textile industry, the consumers' attitudes towards value co-creation or their level of engagement with brands do not differ based on their income level.

4.2.6.6. The differences in the customers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across different age categories

Table 4.17 presents the mean ranks of consumers' value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across six different age categories: 18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55-64, and 65+ as well as the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis H one-way ANOVA test.

TABLE 4-17: CONSUMERS' VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS AGE CATEGORIES

Ranks			
	Age	N	Mean Rank
Value Co-creation	18-24	103	159.48
	25-34	138	165.49
	35-44	76	180.72
	45-54	9	137.06
	55-64	5	156.30
	65+	1	264.00
	Total	332	
Customer Brand Engagement	18-24	103	163.36
	25-34	138	170.38
	35-44	76	167.97
	45-54	9	108.67
	55-64	5	199.00
	65+	1	201.50
	Total	332	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}		
	Value Co-creation	Customer Brand Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	4.177	4.340
df	5	5
Asymp. Sig.	.524	.502
a. Kruskal Wallis Test		
b. Grouping Variable: Age		

Source: The Author

As can be seen in table 4.17, the differences in consumers' value co-creation attitudes and the level of consumer brand engagement across five different income categories (18-24, n = 103; 25-34, n = 138; 35-44, n = 76; 45-54, n = 9; 55-64, n = 5; and 65+, = 1) were not identified as statistically significant with P-Values 0.524 and 0.502 respectively. These findings indicate that, in the specific context of the Pakistani textile industry, consumers of different age did not have different attitudes towards value co-creation. Besides, consumers' level of engagement with brands did not differ depending on their age.

4.2.6.7. The differences in the customers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across different gender categories

In table 4.18, the first part presents the mean ranks of consumers' value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across three gender categories, namely male, females, and undisclosed. Whereas the second part presents the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis H one-way ANOVA test.

TABLE 4-18: CONSUMERS' VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS GENDER CATEGORIES

Ranks			
	Gender	N	Mean Rank
Value Co-creation	Female	111	154.49
	Male	176	159.60
	Prefer not to say	45	223.13
	Total	332	
Customer Brand Engagement	Female	111	163.00
	Male	176	159.32
	Prefer not to say	45	203.21
	Total	332	

Test Statistics^{a,b}		
	Value Co-creation	Customer Brand Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	18.345	7.739
df	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.021
a. Kruskal Wallis Test		
b. Grouping Variable: Gender		

Source: The Author

As can be seen in table 4.18, a statistically significant difference was observed in the consumers' value co-creation attitude, $p < 0.05$ (0.00), and the level of consumer engagement, $p < 0.05$ (0.021), across three different gender categories (male, $n = 176$; female, $n = 111$; and undisclosed, $n = 45$). As observed in the sample, males had higher tendencies to engage in value co-creation activities than females. On the other hand, females had higher behavioural engagement than men.

4.2.6.8. The differences in the customers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across different professional categories

In table 4.19, the first part presents the mean ranks of consumers' value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across seven different income categories, namely Writers/Journalists, Admin, Academic, Fashion Designer, IT, Law, and Others. Whereas, the second part presents the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis H one-way ANOVA test.

TABLE 4-19: CONSUMERS' VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS PROFESSIONAL CATEGORIES

Ranks			
	Profession	N	Mean Rank
Value Co Creation	Writers/Journalists	4	226.88
	Admin	36	185.01
	Academic	75	155.87
	Fashion Designer	14	196.96
	IT	20	168.33
	Law	31	206.92
	Others	152	154.48
	Total	332	
Customer Brand Engagement	Writers/Journalists	4	221.63
	Admin	36	157.38
	Academic	75	160.24
	Fashion Designer	14	188.21
	IT	20	179.53
	Law	31	201.02
	Others	152	159.55
	Total	332	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}		
	Value Co Creation	Customer Brand Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	13.160	7.880
df	6	6
Asymp. Sig.	.041	.247
a. Kruskal Wallis Test		
b. Grouping Variable: Profession		

Source: The Author

As presented in table 4.19, a statistically significant difference, $p < 0.05$ (0.041), in the consumers' value co-creation attitudes across different profession groups (Writers/Journalists, $n = 4$; Admin, $n = 36$; Academic, $n = 75$; Fashion Designer, $n = 14$; IT, $n = 20$; Law, $n = 31$; and Others, $n = 152$) were observed. Whereas, the difference in the level of consumer brand engagement was not statistically significant, $p < 0.05$ (0.247), across the exact same professional categories. These findings indicate that customer's value co-creation attitudes differ based on their professions whereas their level of engagement with brands is not influenced by their professions.

4.2.6.9. The differences in the customers' value co-creation attitudes and engagement across different education categories

In table 4.20, the first part presents the mean ranks of consumers' value co-creation attitudes and customer brand engagement across five different education categories: School, College, Bachelors, Masters or above, and No Formal Education. Whereas, the second part presents the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis H one-way ANOVA test.

TABLE 4-20: CONSUMERS' VALUE CO-CREATION ATTITUDES AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS EDUCATION CATEGORIES

Ranks			
	Education	N	Mean Rank
Value Co Creation	School	12	132.29
	College	34	139.59
	Bachelors	125	177.13
	Masters and Above	156	163.82
	No Formal Education	4	228.63
	Total	331	
Customer Brand Engagement	School	12	105.38
	College	34	163.78
	Bachelors	125	173.82
	Masters and Above	156	164.65
	No Formal Education	4	175.00
	Total	331	

Test Statistics^{a,b}		
	Value Co Creation	Customer Brand Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	7.576	5.753
df	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.108	.218
a. Kruskal Wallis Test		
b. Grouping Variable: EDU		

Source: The Author

As identified, the education level of the customers did not influence customers value co-creation attitude or brand engagement behaviours. As identified, the difference in consumers' value co-creation attitudes and the level of consumer brand engagement across five different education categories (School, n = 12; Collage, n = 34; Bachelors, n = 125; Masters or above, n = 156; and No Formal Education, n = 4) were identified as statistically insignificant with P-Values 0.108 and 0.218 respectively. The next section now deals with the analysis of qualitative data and its findings.

4.3. Qualitative Data Analysis and Findings

4.3.1. Pilot Study

In order to refine the interview questions, a pilot study was conducted by interviewing two participants from the Pakistani textile industry. The participants were posed with interview questions and their responses were carefully analysed to see whether or not they meet the requirements of the research. The participants were asked about the concept of value co-creation, customer engagement with the clothing brands in the context of Pakistan, the role of social media and support provided by the firms to their customers for the value co-creation process. Upon the completion of the interviews, participants were requested for their views related to the interview process. A pilot study was a good exercise, the interviews were recorded and conducted in Urdu, so the participants can feel comfortable in fully answering the questions.

After the pilot interviews, participants gave their feedback that the questions were too technical, lengthy and the number of questions being asked is too much. Based on the feedbacks, the interview questions were simplified to make them more relevant, easy to understand for participants as well as to keep them engaged throughout the interviews. During the analysis of pilot interviews, it was observed that participants gave short answers, and they were not sufficient to answer the research questions; the researcher, therefore, changed the interview approach during the final data collection process by allowing participants to speak without any interruption. One participant was found unaware of the concept of value co-creation; thus, the researcher learnt that, if a participant is unaware of a concept, an explanation would be given to the participant on the concept during the interviews so they can relate to their practical business experience. The pilot survey significantly helped the researcher to refine the interview questions and to gather the information that is highly valuable.

4.3.2. Qualitative Data Collection Process

According to Polkinghorne (2005), qualitative data are assembled mainly in the arrangement of spoken or written language rather than in the form of numbers. The researcher chose interviews as a primary technique of data collection for this study. Qualitative data collection instruments, such as interviews, offer a ‘deeper’ insight into social phenomena. Interviews

are, thus, most suitable where insufficient is known about the research phenomenon or where comprehensive understandings are essential from individual participants (Gill et al. 2008).

To collect the research data, participants were recruited from the textile sector of Pakistan. As the country was going through the Covid-19 pandemic, most of the companies within the sector were temporarily closed. Therefore, the task of recruiting participants for interviews was challenging. In order to reach out to the relevant people, the researcher utilised all available resources including personal connections in the Pakistani textile industry. In order to secure access to the participants, the researcher emailed various company departments as well as utilised LinkedIn to reach people directly.

The targeted sample of this research include participants currently working as a manager and dealing with day-to-day marketing or brand-related tasks. Some of the people whom the researcher came across were either dealing with international markets or working in a B2B context, not in a B2C context, thus not appropriate for the objective of this research. The researcher made every effort to ensure that the right people were recruited so that rich, in-depth and relevant data could be gathered. The participants were contacted prior to the interviews and requested to say their experience within the industry. Besides, the researcher also visited their LinkedIn profiles/bio to make sure they are suitable to participate in the interviews.

Once the participants were selected, the researcher sent them the participant information sheet as well as the participant consent form. The interview questions were comprised of 16 semi-structured and open-ended questions related to the research topic and objectives. Bill (2005) pointed out that when crafting an interview agenda, it is essential to inquire questions that hold more information about the research phenomenon as probable and also be able to tackle the aims and objectives of the research. Participants were asked semi-structured interview questions to have the flexibility in speaking and providing information on the subject area. On average, each interview lasted between 35-45 minutes. After conducting 11 interviews, data saturation was observed as the participants during the qualitative interviews were repeating the same answers about the strategies and concepts they employ while dealing with customers and running their day-to-day operations in the Pakistani textile industry. Although the researcher initially planned to conduct around 15 interviews, the interview process was terminated early due to reaching data saturation.

4.3.3. Qualitative Findings

4.3.3.1. Profiles of the respondents

As a part of this research, a total of 11 managers from the Pakistani textile industry were interviewed. Table 4.21 presents the profile of interviewees.

TABLE 4-21: PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Interviewee ID	Role	Age	Year of experience
1	Deputy Marketing Manager	43	5
2	Brand Manager	38	2
3	Marketing Manager	42	5
4	Merchandiser	37	4
5	E-commerce Manager	29	3
6	Product Manager	33	2
7	Deputy Marketing Manager	35	1
8	Brand Manager	44	3
9	Marketing Manager	46	5 +
10	Marketing Manager	36	2
11	Brand Manager	52	5 +

Source: The Author

The analysis of the qualitative data revealed various themes, the next section now presents the themes identified during the analysis.

4.3.3.2. Understanding of the concept of value co-creation among practitioners

The review of qualitative data indicated that all of the research participants had a fair understanding of the value co-creation process. They were able to highlight the processes in which value is co-created as well as how customers are engaged in the process. As one of the respondents suggested, although the process was not always referred to as 'value co-creation, the activities involving the process of value co-creation was familiar to him. For example:

I have come across this term, in fact, speaking frankly I was actually working on you know like some sort of value co-creation within our respective brand as well, it is already you know even without categorically calling it value co-creation but I was already thinking along these lines like we need to incorporate our audiences our customers in it.

(Interviewee 3)

Some of the other participants, also highlighted that they are aware of the concept but in their view, many of the companies working in the textile industry are not aware of the concept, or its usefulness. The researcher thinks that either it is due to that the concept has not been researched widely in the context of Pakistan and also the companies might be doing and co-creating the products by engaging customers in their day-to-day business operations without precisely knowing the concept. Furthermore, the participant also touched upon the use of value co-creation in terms of innovation and leading business to be ahead of the competition.

Yes, I have heard about it, but Pakistani companies do not know a lot about its importance and usefulness in terms of bringing innovation to their business and become competitive globally.

(Interviewee 5)

Generally, the participants were aware of the concept itself or the activities involved in the process. Many of them were already engaged in the process of value co-creation. The researcher then discussed the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the process of value co-creation.

4.3.3.3. Advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

The analysis of qualitative data identified five key advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes. Each of the advantages is presented below.

a. Meeting customers' demands through product customisation and personalisation

The advent of digital technology and modern manufacturing processes has resulted in personalisation prominence. Businesses have been able to address customer needs and developed their capabilities to cater for these needs. The respondents indicated that, through

value co-creation, customisation and personalisation of products is possible, which eventually results in increased customer satisfaction. Through the process of value co-creation, customers were able to order products that meet their precise needs, which otherwise would not have been possible. For example:

What we offer is we offer you complete customization we will show you a sample like this is how we have designed this piece but you can come over to our outlet, you can have something designed from scratch; as you can even take one of our custom products and what you can do is you can have your own additions to it and you alter it you can edit it how you want or you can have something developed completely from scratch with your own specifications your own measurements like a proper bespoke tailor-fit; use any type of fabric if you won't like if you want to make a waistcoat out of sherwani fabric, we can even facilitate you in that.

(Interviewee 1)

Another participant also informed the type of customisation their brand is offering and how it leads to customer satisfaction and this type of customisation also comes with a price tag, but it satisfies customers' requirements.

We offer bespoke tailoring so that is a big channel itself so if we like any good tailoring outlet or customisation channel we offer people to come and choose their own thing from scratch, have it developed and then we call them in for measuring; it is like consequent repeat visit so that the people are satisfied how the progress is going. we measure them again; we show them how it is turning out before the final product is tailored and ready for delivery. It is that we constantly keep involving and accepting their feedback in the process, so they are completely satisfied. Obviously, we do charge a price tag against such customised service, but people are least they get what they actually want and leave satisfied.

(Interviewee 9)

Practices of value co-creation allow customization and personalization of products and services. These customised and personalised products/services not only meet the specific needs of the customers but also increases their satisfaction. Besides, customised products tend

to be more expensive, which contributes to increasing revenue for the organisation. Therefore, product customization and personalization are identified as an advantage of value co-creation practices.

b. Developing better relationships with customers

During the interview, respondents indicated that engaging customers in the value co-creation processes can help in developing good relationships with them. One of the participants highlighted the steps their clothing brand has taken in order to develop a strong relationship with customers, which keeps the customer loyal to their brand. The response indicated that the organisation has a good level of understanding of customer relationship management. For example:

It is the foremost important channel of assessing customer satisfaction not just for our regular commercial customers but for our corporate customers as well; like we have a specific department just to address our corporate clients and partners. We keep gifting them stuff as well you know customer relationship building for any good business is the most vital thing, so this department is definitely essential.

(Interviewee 7)

Another participant talked about the approach their brand has taken to ensure better relationships with their customers.

Our service and marketing team handles this. We have a huge data bank of our consumers who receive our offers or are registered with our company. We analyse the trends in consumer purchasing and launch products according to market demand.

(Interviewee 4)

Customer relationship is a special bond created between customers and the company by employing new sales, marketing, customer service processes. Managing current customers is better than searching for new ones. Firms also need to develop a loyal customer base and keep on developing long and sustainable relationships with their customers. In order to develop customer loyalty, the companies/brands have to offer products that satisfy their

customer needs and offer them good value in return for their money and time spent with the brand/company. To make their brand successful the company needs to pay attention to their customer's needs, listen to their feedback, communicate with them, target them with the right advertisements and offer them good service. Organisations can build strong relationships with their customers from day one with the help of technology by offering incentives to the customers and offering them good service, alongside keeping an active presence on social media.

c. Innovation leading to competitive advantages

Participants suggested that engaging customers in the process of value co-creation not only helps to develop relationships but also helps to gather innovative ideas that can lead to development of new innovative products. Such innovative products can provide significant competitive edge to organisations. One of the participants, who is currently working as a brand manager in one of the textile companies demonstrated that engaging customers in the value co-creation process is essential for remaining as a market leader in the industry. For example:

We need to incorporate our customers in the value co-creation process, and you know like to stay at the top and stay the market leader, it is something it is imperative all the big players do that to some extent and this is how you ensure you stay at top of the industry.

(Interviewee 11)

Another participant discussed and highlighted the support structure their organisation offers for bringing innovation to their organisation for example:

We also conduct surveys from time to time at our outlets and at malls where we have people fill out forms and survey questionnaires to incorporate their feedback to get a bigger picture of how currently we stand and how the industry is working and which of our marketing channels are working the best and what improvements can be incorporated in our products and our services

(Interviewee 6)

As observed in the responses of the interviewees, innovation brings new ideas for the organisation to grow and be a leader in the industry, it is a process of delivering new products

and services to the market and it is one of the important subjects in business research today. In order to modify conventional practices or even create new and effective markets, companies use innovation processes. By bringing innovation, organisations will eventually achieve profitability and higher sales. In the business world, some organisations are always able to come up with great ideas over and over again, some of these ideas are based on bringing new products -which is one of the toughest challenges an organisation or its leadership faces.

Innovation provides competitive advantages by perceiving or discovering a new or better way to compete in the industry. It is the main source for an organisational competitive advantage by transforming ideas and creative proposals in a project and practical solutions workable and sustainable in terms of a new product or process organisation reforms or new business model in response to the changing needs of society and margins. The companies striving to achieve competitive advantage must launch radically creative product services or ideas that are able to change the conventional way of doing business. Various players can play their roles in bringing innovation to the organisation, their employees, customers and suppliers. In value co-creation processes, customers have important roles to play in helping companies to innovate, therefore, innovation is identified as one of the significant advantages of value co-creation processes.

d. Enhanced customer experience leading to customer loyalty

Another advantage of engaging consumers in value co-creation processes, as identified in this research, is customer loyalty. As identified, when customers have better experiences with the service providers, they are more likely to retain. One of the participants highlighted the significance of offering a better customer experience to their customers resulting in loyalty for their brand.

Absolutely no doubt about it. If the customer gets a better and desired experience from the company, they stay loyal to the brand; from ordering their products online to receiving these through online and offline channels. In the perspective of offline retail outlets, the first thing a customer experience is the behaviour of staff working over there. If they receive good customer service, then they become regular clients of that outlet and in turn stay loyal to the brand.

(Interviewee 7)

Another participant highlighted the importance of customer experience for a business to be successful and how loyal customers can help the company to grow.

Oh yes without a doubt and good customer experience is the biggest factor for any business to especially if they want to grow, they have to have satisfied customers, turn them into loyal advocates for the company and start referring their friends and families.

(Interviewee 5)

Offering a great customer experience to their customers should always be a central goal of every business. The conventional customer loyalty programmes and rewards are not suitable to generate brand commitment. Nowadays, customers are increasingly focused on attaining the customer experience which is simple, enhanced, and it is related to focusing on customers. The companies should not try to manufacture loyalty through some programmes or loyalty cards rather than they should view the loyalty through the customer experience offered. The loyalty of the customer is becoming the natural by-product of a customer experience that is fixed on inspiring repeated brand engagement which means that customers interact with the brand in terms of making purchases or offering their feedback, spreading a positive word of mouth to the customers and influencing other customers to make purchases of that certain brand. Loyal customers tend to engage with the company to create value. Therefore, customer loyalty through enhanced customer experience is identified as an advantage of engaging customers in the value co-creation processes.

e. Increase in Revenues

As observed in the dataset, respondents expressed that customer engagement in the value co-creation processes has led to an increase in revenues. As identified, implementation of value co-creation practices yields positive results for a business, including better products/services quality, attaining less business risk, greater productivity and increasing the company's revenue growth. This is because value co-creation can help businesses to meet the exact need of customers, eventually helping them enhance customer satisfaction as well as retention - which has positive impacts on overall revenues. One of the participants pointed out how value co-creation is leading to higher sales for their company due to the referrals made by customers to their friends and family. For example:

We have seen a lot of positive feedback generated in these communities as well; like somebody is satisfied with our service they will go and put pictures up, they will post and talk about to other people you know these guys are doing a good job and you can always go and purchase from them. If somebody is asking, they always refer us that I got this and this from there and it worked out very well for us and you can always go and purchase it for yourself.

(Interviewee 4)

Another participant also highlighted the importance of the value co-creation process in generating increase revenue for the company.

If the brand is already applying value co-creation in their business practice, they will listen to the customers' demands and requirements for a piece and create something according to that. The customer will have to pay more for this service, which is a good thing for the business, but the customers can also get what they want.

(Interviewee 9)

The way of doing business has changed with the implementation of value co-creation and customers, nowadays, play active roles in companies' day to day activities. Customers have an approach to a variety of information and are able to communicate their experiences with other customers through various digital platforms. When customers share their positive experiences with other customers, they are essentially involved in the marketing of a company's products and services. A clothing brand is created by the experience of a customer, so the test for a company is to ensure its quality and personalised experiences for individual customers during co-creation activities. When customers are pleased with service providers, they not only contribute towards a positive brand image but also higher revenues and profitability.

4.3.3.4. Challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process

The analysis of qualitative data revealed two key challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process. Here, challenges refer to possible negative outcomes of engaging customers in value co-creation processes. Below, each of the challenges is presented and interpreted:

a. Lack of consistencies of the products/services affecting brand reputation

Respondents suggested that, although the practices of valued co-creation can indeed help companies in many ways, it also poses challenges such as inconsistency of products and services. When new products are developed on a daily basis, maintaining the quality of products can be challenging and that can ultimately impact the brand reputation negatively.

A brand manager in the Pakistani textile sector states that incorporating too much audience feedback into their day-to-day product development processes can tarnish the brand image.

I feel if your audience is already developed and engaged you shouldn't really have too much of a problem in involving customers in co-creation like if have to have to step out and go for a total co-creation campaign tomorrow I am sure right now a scores of people will already be on board and we will be getting a ton of opinions, feedbacks and suggestions already. If we employ all of their suggestions on our products, I feel like we will lose our brand identity.

(Interviewee 2)

Highly reputed brands can be impacted by the increased involvement of customers in the brands' day to day activities. Brand reputation is generally built through the consistent quality of products and effective marketing. If a company is relying highly on the customer feedbacks while addressing the market needs, this might lead to negative consequences for the company because sometimes the customers may not know what they exactly want. The company will manufacture products and modify services according to meet some customers demand while neglecting the needs of a wider audience, this can affect the brand reputation severally.

b. Higher customer engagement leading to increased negative feedbacks and value destruction

When a company engages customers in the process of products/service development, the customers are not only likely to leave positive comments, but they are equally likely to leave negative comments as well in the events of dissatisfaction with products or services. Given that technology is highly accessible to all customer segments, in events where brands do not meet the expectations of customers, customers usually leave negative feedbacks that harm the organisational image for the long term. One of the respondents suggested that customers sometimes can be unreasonable, for example:

I already mentioned the kind of messages we get at times it's not always, like the customer is always right you there is no way other about it. At times people can be unreasonable but at times they are right. If there is a service loss or something from our experience, we seem like there is a lot of discussion in Facebook groups of consumers, they discuss different brands, they ask each other's opinions or referrals.

(Interviewee 7)

The value in service-dominant logic is produced by collaborative actions of co-creation between firms/brands and customers. Customers provide their resources in value co-creation in the form of feedback, positive word of mouth or even through cognitive engagement. The value may be co-destructed between both firm and the customers in some situations. A customer can get upset or angry as a result of insufficient resources, technological problems and misunderstandings. An angry customer will post negative comments about the brand through platforms online, stemming in diminished brand reputation, low sales and loss of customers leading to value destruction. When customers and employees of a company or brand blame each other for any service failure leading this also results in the destruction of value. In an online brand community settings negatively balanced engagement, technology-driven co-creation experiences present additional challenges for the company. Therefore, higher customer engagement leading to increased negative feedbacks and value destruction is identified as another challenge of value co-creation.

4.3.3.5. Roles of modern technologies in value co-creation processes

The analysis of qualitative data revealed various roles that modern technologies play in value co-creation processes.

a. Reaching a wider range of customers more efficiently

Technology enables companies to extend their reach to wider audiences by providing them services efficiently. Technology also allows the customers to access services remotely or communicate with the company virtually. New technologies have opened a new avenue of business that did not exist a decade ago. Participants highlighted that both business and customers are extensively using new technologies for engaging with each other. For example:

Well definitely right now technological channels stand as the most authentic, effective and efficient way of communication with the audiences. People are more comfortable speaking their mind as there are very few barriers in putting their messages out there. You will be surprised by the kind of messages we get at times and that is necessarily not too much of a bad thing because we are assured in that way that people are actually comfortable in expressing themselves to us.

(Interviewee 9)

Another respondent also highlighted that social media helps tremendously in reaching the wider population.

We have our Facebook page we have our Instagram, YouTube and, we have our website. So, these are all channels where we address people queries if they have issues with their orders or deliveries that's where we address them. if they give some feedback that where we record it, we are always available on chat and we even have our WhatsApp number and we have our WhatsApp business account where we broadcast our own messages, offers and new launches new offers which are also carried out through other digital channels and also takes people feedback in this.

(Interviewee 6)

As observed in the sample, the interactions between customers and firms in value co-creation are facilitated mostly with the help of IT in the Pakistani textile sector. Internet-based

technologies have empowered customers and compelled firms to be more customer-centric and service-oriented. The Internet has reduced the information gap between firms and customers, increased customers bargaining power, and subsequently, changed the channel power structure. By using technology, companies can access wider audiences and let them participate in the value co-creation process through their resource integration. Another great thing about the internet is that it helps small, newer businesses to reach audiences on an equal footing as multinational company. In the past, a start-up had to start by serving local clients and then expanding regionally or overseas when they were able to physically increase their presence; however, simply by establishing a website, businesses nowadays can immediately reach a global audience. In order to interact with consumers, the digital platforms currently used by businesses in the Pakistani textile sector include Facebook, Twitter, Whats App, Instagram and LinkedIn.

b. Digital Marketing

Firms in the Pakistani textile sector are utilising digital technologies to reach out to customers and market their products with the help of other customers. Digital technologies not only have helped the firms to reach a wider population, but they also have reduced the marketing costs significantly. One of the participants suggested that customer engagement has been made easier by digital technologies, for example:

Digital is basically the future and it's already here we are living the future right now. It will only grow from here so digital outlets; digital channels are the ones which you should primarily focus on now. They help engage with the customers; they help you spread word of mouth for brands; get conversions, get people on board get people to brand loyalty, that's where it helps.

(Interviewee 4)

Another participant also highlighted:

We have also done that we had people visit our outlets specifically through our digital channels like integration of both offline and online marketing in that sense; like go to our outlet and we have some frames, or some selfie booths go and take a picture of yourself, post on your timeline and tag us this that and you will get free prizes and gifts from us. So

that is something we have constantly tried to utilise through our technological our more efficient platforms you know so that we keep our audiences engaged in that sense.

(Interviewee 6)

Digital marketing includes using the Internet, smartphones, online platforms, search engines, and other channels to approach customers. It is a completely new exercise that needs a new approach to contacting customers and new ways of thinking about how consumers react in comparison to conventional marketing. Digital marketing is interactive and focuses on a particular section of the consumer base. It is on the higher trajectory and comprises of email ads, search result ads and promoted tweets – all that assimilates marketing with customer reaction or two-way communication between the consumers and companies. Companies are co-creating content with their audiences these days. To contest these challenges, brands throughout all industries are reinforcing to co-create content with their consumers and industry influencers to assist them to reach company target customers and communicate their brand stories.

Social media, being an extremely interactive platform, offer new prospects for value co-creation. Social media offers the prospect for social mixing between firms and customers that leads to the creation of value through the consumption of experiences and knowledge of the customers. People can post their positive experiences on different brands pages or their own personal accounts helping the company to generate positive word of mouth for a brand. These days, companies in the Pakistani textile sector consider social media marketing as a core of their marketing strategy.

c. Improved customer support systems

Modern technologies have improved customer support systems in the Pakistani textile sector. Customers, nowadays, can receive instant support through multiple media of communication such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, email, etc. Providing support to the customers when needed help them to engage more with the brand and have peace of mind. Participants reported that due to improved support systems, more and more customers are seeking help from multiple channels, for example:

The other channel we have the alternate which again which is a stronger channel for us right now is our retail outlets across the nation and in fact across the globe. All of these outlets also work as you know like not just as a sale channel but it's a two-way street over there because people come over there they have their opinions views and questions they ask our sale people they get it directly answered there their queries are facilitated at the same time.

(Interviewee 8)

Another participant also highlighted.

If customers can go to the outlet for reporting complaints, that's even better if they want to deliver it and ship it to our offices, we will do it that way. So that is one strong aspect we have already developed for mitigating any customer complaints, ensuring they are happy. Other than that, if they have any queries or concerns, we have our digital platforms, we have our sales teams in our outlets who address their queries then and there.

(Interviewee 4)

With the help of technology, customers in the Pakistani textile sector can now receive supports through multiple channels and have a hassle-free shopping experience. This is made possible by the introduction of digital payments, use of click and collect services, online shopping, or self-service at a brick-and-mortar store. Customers can get support from the company through their websites, WhatsApp business accounts, Facebook pages, Twitter accounts or other social media platforms. Companies employ digital technologies in the form of AI Chatbots to answer customer general queries. All these activities help companies to enhance customer experience and allow customers to engage more with the brand.

4.4. Conclusions

This chapter presented the processes of quantitative and qualitative data analysis as well as the research findings. Prior to collecting the main quantitative research data, a pilot study was conducted to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales. An assessment of internal consistency indicated that the measurements scales are reliable. The vast majority of research data was collected electronically using Google Forms whilst some were collected physically. In order to analyse the data and test the research hypotheses, SPSS was used. The

analysis revealed a negative relationship between shoppers' age and shopping frequency. In terms of shoppers' gender and shopping frequency, a significant relationship was identified with women shopping more frequently than men. No significant relationship was identified between income and shopping frequency. Finally, a correlation test revealed that there exists a positive relationship between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitude.

On the other hand, during the qualitative data collection, various steps were followed for refining the interview questions (i.e., conducting a pilot study, asking respondents for suggestions, etc). Following a pilot survey, main data was collected from 11 managers in the Pakistani textile industry. A thematic analysis of the data uncovered that engaging customers in value co-creation processes bring various benefits to organisations. They include building relationships with customers, attaining a competitive advantage through innovation, offering a better customer experience leading to customer loyalty, and higher revenues. The analysis also uncovered various challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes such as inconsistencies in the quality of products and services and increased negative feedbacks which results in value destruction for the company. Finally, the qualitative analysis also highlighted the role of technology in the value co-creation process by suggesting they help in reaching wider customers, digital marketing, and improving customer support systems. The next chapter now discusses the findings identified in this chapter.

5. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

5.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to critically discuss and evaluate the findings of this research by locating them in a broader context. In order to achieve the research aim, four objectives were designed in chapter one. The final objective was designed to make recommendations to the practitioners based on the findings of this research whilst the remaining three objectives were designed to assess the relationships between different variables of the research as well as to explore new insights in the context of the research. This chapter of the thesis evaluates how the empirical findings of this research fit in the broader context and what kind of contributions do they make. In order to discuss the findings related to all three objectives, this chapter is organised into three parts. Firstly, the key findings related to each objective are summarised. Secondly, the findings are discussed by discussing them in the context of previous empirical findings and highlighting the contributions they make. Finally, each finding is evaluated by assessing its strengths and weaknesses.

5.2. Relationships between customer engagement and value co-creation

5.2.1. Summary of the Findings

Various theoretical concepts related to customer engagement and value co-creation were discussed in chapter two of this thesis. After an extensive literature review, the researcher identified a positive impact of customer brand engagement on their value co-creation attitude. However, no evidence specifically related to the Pakistani textile sector was found. In order to measure customer brand engagement and value co-creation attitude in the Pakistani textile industry, different dimensions of each variable were identified. After measures were finalised, a questionnaire was designed by utilising scales that were already adopted by previous researchers whilst researching customer brand engagement and value co-creation attitude; this helped to establish the content validity of the measurement scales. Once the scales were finalised, a pilot survey was conducted, and good reliability of measurement scales was attested.

After the collection of the main research data, responses were screened and coded into SPSS. Any inconsistent and outlier responses were removed and a total of 332 responses were determined as valid for further analysis. In order to draw inferences, ANOVA tests, Chi-

square tests and correlation tests were conducted. Prior to assessing the relationship between customer brand engagement and value creation attitude, chi-square tests were conducted to assess how customer purchase frequency of their favourite brand varies across different age categories, genders and income levels. The findings indicated that as people grow older, they tend to shop less from their favourite brands in the Pakistani textile sector. Further analysis of gender and income level revealed that on average females buy more often than men from their favourite brands and income does not affect the shopping frequency of customers. Further, an assessment of the relationship between customer brand engagement and value co-creation attitude revealed that the customers that engage with their favourite brands are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities.

5.2.2. Discussions of the Findings

In order to test statistical associations between different research variables, four research hypotheses were developed. Below, findings related to each hypothesis are discussed individually.

5.2.2.1. Shopper's age and shopping frequency

As identified by this research, as people grow older, they tend to shop less from their favourite brands. The Chi-square test finding indicated a negative relationship between shoppers age and shopping frequency. This finding of this research is consistent with the findings of existing studies. Carpenter (2006) identified that age validates opposite association to shopping frequency, showing that younger people are most likely to be frequent shoppers. Pare and Pourazad (2016) also pointed out that, compared with middle age and older shoppers, the shopping frequency of younger customer is higher. Shopping is an everyday activity of younger people (Brudsal & Lavik,2008). According to White (1994), shopping is an entertainment activity for young people, but they do it also for learning and gathering information. Hortman et al. (1990) state that younger shoppers focus on services and goods rather than price. It is being stated by Bhatnagar (2007) that people with younger age tend to shop online more as they are risk-takers.

Parker and wang (2016) revealed that younger customers are more immersed in apparel shopping than older consumers. A comparative study identified that young people in India and Taiwan have different needs and experiences for apparel shopping than older age

customers (Yi-Chun, 2010; Kalia, 2017). This indicates that a country's economic status can significantly influence shoppers' behaviours. Furthermore, Jay (2020) states that the younger generation is the driving force behind luxury fashion products.

Age is a vital demographic aspect that influences customer behaviour. While considering age as a variable, prior researches have consistently identified positive associations between age groups and shopping frequency (i.e., Westbrook and Black, 1985; Roy, 1994). Gehrt and Yan (2004) state that individual characteristics also affect shopping quality significance. Shoppers over the age of 35 are more time-conscious (Sharma et al., 2012). According to Baylock (2006), older and well-informed consumers shop less frequently in comparison with less-educated younger shoppers. According to Hortman et al. (1990), elderly people are price conscious and prefer lower prices while focusing on experience and quality. Moe and Giddings (2002) state that in terms of elderly men and women, both prefer clothing shopping with ease, variety and branded clothes. Lumpkin (1985) pointed to elderly customers as economic, uninvolved (less frequent shoppers).

Nonetheless, Kuruvilla and Joshi (2010) stated that there is no substantial difference in age group and shopping frequency. From the perspective of gender and age, Roy et al. (2016) stated that in terms of fashion shopping there is not much difference among younger and older females; both are inclined to fashion products with different enthusiasms and attitudes. However, younger females shop with friends for enhancement of their self-image and social identity (Bannister & Hogg, 2004) whilst elder women prefer to shop with other family members in order to enhance their social status (Thomas and Peters, 2009).

The finding of this research is consistent with the existing belief in the literature. The findings of this study make contributions to the body of knowledge by supporting the overwhelming literature evidence and making the area of study further strong. In terms of practical implications, as younger customers are more likely to be fashion-centred and tend to shop more, the managers in the Pakistani textile industry should proactively target younger customers for increasing sales and profitability.

5.2.2.2. Shopper's gender and shopping frequency

As identified by this research and presented in chapter 4, on average, females are more likely to shop than males in the context of the Pakistani textile industry. The sample showed that the shopping frequency of females on a weekly or monthly basis was slightly higher in comparison to males. This finding of the research is consistent with the finding of Brudsal and Lavik, (2008) – who suggested that women shop more than men. Furthermore, Dholkia (1999) also identified that shopping is also a gendered activity; for example, their research on shopping centre usage between 1986 and 1991 found females to be dominant throughout with a higher ratio (2:1) than males. Significant differences were also observed by Seock and Bailey (2008) between male and female shopping orientations and experiences.

Females tend to spend more time searching for an item than males (Gehrt and Yan, 2004). For females, shopping fashion is fun, flirty, exciting, joyful and they are interested in co-creation (Miller and Mills, 2012). Hansen and Jensen (2009) also identified less involvement of males in fashion shopping activities. Women tend to buy more fashion brands than men and like to be anticipated as fashion leaders (Pentecost and Andrews, 2010). Rield et al (2010) highlighted that women are associated more with greater levels of engagement and trust – which are the factors associated with higher shopping frequencies. Shopping for clothes is considered more appealing to females (Buttle, 1992). Dholkia (1999) states that, unlike males, females while shopping for clothes, prefer to do it by themselves. According to Carpenter (2006), there is a difference in the selection of products during shopping between males and females: females buy more beauty products whilst males spend more on electronic products. Nonetheless, Brudsal & Lavik (2008) state that females are big shoppers, but males are also closing gaps.

In terms of online shopping, Smith (2014) pointed out that the traditional view is that females drive shopping trends as 80% of household spending is under their control; however, e-commerce data suggest that males initiate similar spending online in the US as females. Slyke et al. (2002) state that women are less likely to purchase a product or service online. As studies conducted by Chen (2007) and Shaouf et al. (2016) noticed, e-commerce channel usage for shopping is preferred by males than females who have a higher liking for high street retail.

The findings of this study are consistent with the literature as prior studies also suggested that females tend to be more shopping-savvy compared to males. Precisely in the textile sector, females are more particularly interested in certain brands. This may be due to treating shopping as an experience by females (Miller and Mills, 2012) rather than a task. The findings of this study make contributions to the body of knowledge by reconfirming the literature evidence and making the area of study stronger. The findings also make contributions to the professional practice by suggesting females are the key buyers in the textile industry and marketing managers should focus more on female customers while designing their strategies. This will also help the firm to engage them in value co-creation and generating higher sales.

5.2.2.3. Shopper's income and shopping frequency

This study identified that there is an insignificant difference in the shopping frequency of customers from different income groups in the Pakistani textile industry. The research findings are also validated and supported by literature as various researchers (i.e., Rocha et al., 2005; Paridon et al., 2006) have examined the role of income in shopping frequency. Baylock (2006) states that income is inversely associated with shopping frequency, the reason for this is having a higher income suggests a lower minimal function of money. In terms of clothing shopping frequency, Carpenter (2006) identified that income validates opposite association to shopping frequency, suggesting that low income does not affect shopping frequency. Maden et al. (2015) emphasise that the consumption of fashion good is performed by consumers, particularly from the lower-income groups. However, Parker and Wenyu (2019) identified that occupation, income level and education has no association with changes in shopping frequency.

In terms of shopping for branded products, Carpenter (2006) suggested that customers belonging to lower-income groups have less inclination towards brands. On the other hand, Smith (2014) stated that in spite of earning less, millennials, those customers who belong to the age category 18 to 34, continue to be the key age demographic in terms of online commerce. Furthermore, Moe and Giddings (2002) state that elder age customers possess higher income and wealth, but they are less likely to shop often.

There is an overall established consensus in the literature that younger people tend to have low income as they are more expected to shop in contrast to elder people who have higher incomes or wealth. Although a positive relationship between income and shopping frequency was anticipated, the finding of this research indicated no significant statistical associations between income level and shopping frequency in the precise context of the Pakistani textile industry. This may have been due to the large income gap in the country. Nonetheless, the findings of this research make contributions to the literature by adding a new insight related to the Pakistani textile industry.

5.2.2.4. Relationships between consumer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes

This research identified that there is a strong statistical association between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitude. The findings of this research indicated customers that who interact with brands more frequently are more likely to engage in value co-creation processes. Oyner and Korelina (2016), in their study on the Russian hospitality industry, identified that there exists a positive association between customer engagement in value co-creation. In their research, the authors found that companies that are familiar with co-creation and have resources are likely to engage in value co-creation activities with customers. Financially, successful companies offer better customisation option and experiences to their target audiences (Oyner and Korelina, 2016). This indicates that the successful clothing brands with resources operating in the Pakistani textile industry can design and implement strategies that will facilitate customers engagement resulting in value co-creation.

Similarly, Harrigan et al. (2020) identified that value co-creation positively affects customer brand engagement behaviours after investigating the relationship between value co-creation and customer brand engagement on social media. The results of Harrigan et al. (2020) are similar to the findings of Rosenthal et al. (2017) who also identified that value co-creation will enhance attachment with brands. In terms of value co-creation, Leclercq (2017) states that customer engagement may produce positive or negative effects on the general functions of the co-creation platform due to different user's background. Further, research conducted by Harrigan et al. (2020) on social media use in the tourism industry found that value co-creation impacts customer brand engagement, further emphasizing its role as a basis for

customer-brand relationships. Furthermore, Nysveen and Pedersen (2013) state that that co-creation has a positive influence on brand experience; suggesting that engaging in co-creation activities with the customers intensifies the brand experience.

Mane and Diop (2017) outlined that, in China, international brands like Coca-Cola (Crowdsourcing platform), Pepsi Co (creative challenges), Nescafe (design contests), Ford (Mobility Integration Challenge) and Volkswagen (People's Car Project) have engaged their consumers in offering new products/service ideas in value co-creation. In their study, the researchers found that to initiate customer engagement in value co-creation, it is essential for companies to underline how they are perceived by the customers in terms of their ability, determination to enhance the quality, design, features of products and services; also, their ability to deliver the value asserted by the proposal. A study by Chen and Wang (2016) proposed a conceptual model for examining associations between customer participation, co-created value and customer loyalty in air transportation. They collected, their survey data from Taiwanese air passengers and found that customer participation while using an online check-in system is positively associated with value co-creation, which boosts satisfaction with respect to the system.

Additionally, Banyte and Dovalience (2014) also identified that there is a significant association between customer engagement into value co-creation and customer loyalty. Auh et al. (2007), on the other hand, analysed the direct impact of customer engagement on value co-creation in the perspective of financial services and established a relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation. Furthermore, research conducted by Rajah et al. (2008) on companies offering tourism services exhibited that engagement of customers into value co-creation results in the enhanced association between company and customer. Grissemann and Stokburger-Sauer (2012) explored the impact of customer engagement into value co-creation and stated that customer engagement into value co-creation has an impact on their satisfaction with the firm, expenses and loyalty, and customer satisfaction with the firm influences their loyalty.

These research's findings are consistent with literature evidence as a majority of previous studies also identified that customer engagement has an association with value co-creation, and it results in customer satisfaction and loyalty. The finding of this research also suggests that there is a relationship between customer brand engagement and value co-creation

attitude. If the customers are communicated properly, facilitated and offered platforms for engagement, it will have an impact on their value co-creation attitude. The more customers will be engaged by the clothing brands in the Pakistani textile industry, it will have a positive impact on customers value co-creation attitude. The findings of this research make significant contributions to the body of knowledge by further strengthening the area of study. The findings also provide guidance to managers in the industry for aligning their strategies in facilitating customers brand engagement in the value co-creation process. Enhanced customer engagement and implementation of value co-creation practices will produce innovative products/services, enrich customers' experience, higher customer satisfaction and loyalty to the brand.

5.2.3. Evaluation of the Findings

To collect the primary data for this research, a convenience sampling method was followed after considering the time, access, and resources available to the researcher. As the data was collected through a non-random sampling method, it may not be able to produce generalizable findings; thus, the findings identified in this research may not be applicable to the entire Pakistani textile industry. Besides, considering the circumstances around COVID-19, the vast majority of the research data was collected through online surveys. The incorporation of the online survey could have led to participant bias, ultimately impacting the reliability of the findings. Besides, imitated existing literature involving value co-creation attitude was identified in the research context. This may have impacted the robustness of the findings.

The findings of this research will help businesses in targeting the relevant customers, catering for their needs efficiently, and generating more sales. It will also help managers working in the textile industry of Pakistan to understand their customers better, make them more engaged with the brand and how the value co-creation could be enhanced. Previous studies conducted in the Pakistani textile industry did not explore the role of customers' demographics on shopping frequency. This study, therefore, adds significant knowledge to the literature.

5.3. Advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

5.3.1. Summary of the Findings

In order to gather detailed knowledge of value co-creation processes in the textile sector, in-depth interviews with managers working in the Pakistani textile industry were conducted. The researcher first conducted pilot interviews to refine interview questions, before executing a full-fledge qualitative data collection. In total, 11 interviews were conducted comprising of 16 semi-structured questions, with each interview lasting between 35-45 minutes. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data by following analysis processes such as coding, categorisation and conclusions. The analysis of qualitative helped the researcher to uncover an understanding of the value co-creation process among practitioners, the advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes, and the challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process. As identified, implementing value co-creation practises in business processes helps organisations to enhance customer experience and loyalty, develop better relationships with customers, facilitates product customization and personalization, encourages innovation, and in general, increases the overall revenue. However, in circumstances where value co-creation practises are not effectively conducted, it can lead to an increase in negative feedbacks and inconsistency in the quality of products and services. Figure 5.1 briefly summarises the findings of this research:

FIGURE 5-1: ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF ENGAGING CUSTOMERS IN VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES

Source: The Author

5.3.2. Discussions of the Findings

5.3.2.1. Advantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

As identified by this research, one of the advantages related to involving customers in the value co-creation processes is being able to meet consumer requirements through service customization and service personalization. When customers are engaged in the process of value co-creation, they are able to communicate their needs and requirements more effectively to the brands, which help brands in developing personalised products that can enhance the possibility of customer satisfaction. Zhang and Chen (2008) stated that in order to satisfy consumer needs firms are increasingly offering customised products and services. Pine (1993) pointed out that the firm sustainable success cannot be dependent on offering

mass customisation of products and services. Companies can achieve success through personalised interaction with consumers to co-create value (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004; Prahalad and Krishnan, 2008), as identified by this research. Customers can contribute to the co-development of new products, retail and after-sales services (Parasuraman and Grewal, 2000). Firms can gain competitive gain through personalisation and by engaging customers to co-create value (Zhang and Chen, 2008). Personalisation and customisation will result in better quality, better service experience and satisfaction for the customers (Zine et al., 2014). This research also revealed that engaging customers in value co-creation help in developing better relationships with their customers as customers will interact with the company with ease and offer their services for co-creation. These findings are supported by the findings of Xie et al. (2008), who indicated that attitudes, capabilities and ongoing behaviour can have a positive impact on customer intention to purchase. Furthermore, Bazi et al. (2019) highlighted that customer engagement has a positive impact on co-creation. Engaging customers in value co-creation is promoted as a significant means of starting a dialogue with customers (Ballantyne and Varey, 2006), creating a community around company interest (Healy and McDonagh, 2013), strengthening the commitment towards new offerings and fuelling positive attitudes from customers (Kaptein et al., 2015; Nishikawa et al., 2013). Enhancing engagement in customer communities can generate more gains as customer enhances brand and relationship impartiality by producing exogenous loyalty plans for a company without requiring input from the company (Vargo, 2009). Rajah et al. (2008) identified that engagement of customers into value co-creation enhances customer satisfaction and trust. There may also be cognitive and affective advantages of engaging customers in co-creation activities. Higher involvement with a firm may give customers a feeling of achievement, spirits of self-efficacy and largely, the satisfaction of the procedure itself (Dong et al., 2008; Meuter et al., 2005). The findings of this research are consistent with the literature as this research also identified that developing relationships with customers through engaging in value co-creation will lead to customer loyalty and satisfaction.

Another finding of this research suggests that engaging customer in value co-creation processes helps the company to produce better products/services, enhance existing product/services and attain competitive advantages. These findings are supported by Alexander (2012) that asserts firms that engage the customers in co-creation processes gain uneven information regarding the marketplace – such insights not instantly accessible to competitors. Through co-creation activities, companies generate information that helps to

meet customers' needs and produce ideas to design and manufacture (Jaworski & Kohli, 2006; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004) together with improvements to customer experience (Ramaswamy, 2011). Saarijarvi et al. (2013) gave an example of Dell idea storm, where customers can be engaged in the new product development process; customers are engaged in company value creation to share their ideas to make computers better.

During the investigation, the researcher found that through engaging customers in value co-creation, firms can provide a better customer experience to their customers which will result in customer loyalty. Customer experience is an ongoing process, and it is one of the advantages a company can gain through engaging customers in a value co-creation process. If a company satisfies its customer by offering them better products/service experiences, listens to their feedback, offer the improvements demanded by them in products and services, it will motivate customers to engage more in value co-creation. A seamless customer experience will also help a company to maintain its loyal customer. Offering a great customer experience to their customer should always be a fundamental goal of every business. As suggested by Lemon and Verhoef (2016), customer experience focuses on customer's cognitive, emotional, behavioural, sensorial, and social reactions to a company's contributions during the customer's whole buying journey. Ahn and Back (2018) point out that customer engagement is stimulated by experience and affects their future engagement, as also suggested by the findings of this research.

By enhancing customer experience, both company and customer can benefit from enhanced predictability and quality in exchange (Evans et al., 2008); customers will also raise their co-creation activities offering opportunities for higher advances (Auh et al., 2007), the findings of this research also confirmed this view in the context of the Pakistani textile industry. This research identified that, if a customer has a good experience as an outcome of an engagement, it will lead to loyalty. Jakkola and Alexander (2014) state that customer engagement in value co-creation can result in customer loyalty and satisfaction with the brand. As, level of customer engagement increases, customers may become uniformly more dedicated to the value co-creation process and contribute more towards the process (Dong et al. 2008; Wilson et al. 2008).

Co-creation can help a company in terms of loyalty benefits as customers develop a bond with the company and attachment towards the firms (Jaworski and Kohli, 2006), this may

also help companies to stop their customers from switching and overcome the problems found in traditional loyalty programs (Dowling and Uncles, 1997; Uncles et al., 2003). Thakur (2016) argues that customer engagement has a considerable influence on customer loyalty alongside customer satisfaction, which underscores the requirement of safeguarding customer participation. Engagement can be the means for companies to maintain their customers, constructing devoted customer support for the firms. These research findings echoed the existing beliefs of the literature by suggesting engagement in value co-creation results in better customer experience, which eventually leads to customer loyalty.

The findings of this research revealed that higher revenue generation can be attained with an application of customers involvement in value co-creation. Application of value co-creation practices yields positive results for the company, which includes better products quality, less business risk, greater productivity and an increase in revenue. The findings of this research are supported by Bazi et al. (2019)'s study suggesting customers incline to engage in a co-creation process with other customers and transfer their experience and knowledge about product/brand, eventually helping each other with their shopping decision making. Piligrimiene et al. (2015) state that customer engagement in the value co-creation process, customer participation in the preparation of firm capabilities, word of mouth and various others are the advantages for the company. According to Jaakkola and Alexander (2014), the consequences of customer engagement for a firm can be gained directly or indirectly through positive or negative word of mouth. According to Hsu (2017), the interaction between customers in online channels can generate meaningful results for the company. In past, customers used to communicate among themselves and with the company differently (Hyken, 2018), however, through the internet and social media, customers nowadays can interact with their brands more easily (So et al., 2014).

As this research identified, engaging customers in value co-creation processes lead to higher revenues as well as saves costs. Alexander (2012) states that the employees working in firms might get benefits if the firms increase their co-creation activities; employee workload may be lessened if customers engage as co-creators with higher involvement. According to Schneider & Bowen (1995), customer involvement derives positive feelings in employees as they assume both are taking suitable functions within the exchange which helps a firm to save additional costs.

5.3.2.2. Challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

This research uncovered that if value co-creation activities are not executed appropriately, they may also have negative impacts on firms. One of these implications includes loss of reputation if a brand cannot meet its customers' demands. Zhang et al. (2018) state that companies offer many promises through value co-creation but when the customers are involved in the process and the company try to avoid their complaints thus cannot fulfil the promises, the customers then become confrontational, which damages the brand's image. According to William et al. (2009), customers have high expectations from their brands in terms of their commitment to business practices. Failure to meet customer expectation will create disappointments (Ann, 2013). Damaging emotions such as anger and sadness are expected to be produced in events when firms fail to meet customer expectations (Shaver et al., 1987). Moreover, customers may regret their decision in participating in the company value proposition (Inman, 2007). These can have a negative impact on their future participation as well.

This research identified that one of the challenges organisations face while employing value co-creation practices is building trust with their customers. This trust is mostly crucial between the customer and the company and it can be established through repeated interactions, having good communication from the company sides inspires customers to engage more in the co-creation activities. As Gibbert et al. (2002) states, there are two blocks while firms utilise customer knowledge: the first one is the inner culture of a firm not incorporating or trusting their customers' knowledge, and the second one is a firm not having capabilities for active engagement of customers due to inadequate system and procedures. Bateson and Hoffman (1999) highlight that customer engagement with the company to co-create may result in a fight over control of the interaction between staffs and customers and it raises staff role stress. Hsieh et al. (2004) pointed out that there is a view that engaging customers in the value co-creation process will lessen staff workload is not true, the reason is that as staff workload lessens the companies usually reduce the number of staffs, therefore the level of workload remains unchanged. Therefore, it is essential that firms evaluate possible implications of implementing value co-creation practices beforehand and develop viable plans by considering all parties.

This research also uncovered that value destruction may take place between a company and its customers if value co-creation activities not implemented properly – it is one of the main challenges faced by organisations. This occurs due to negative feedback from customers, instead of positive word of mouth. The findings suggest that technology makes it easy for a company to connect with its customers, but it also gives them the power to criticise and spread negative information about the brand. In terms of challenges, Alexander (2012) states that engaging customers in co-creation faces challenges and is not without risks. According to Surachartkumtonkun et al. (2015), lack of resources, faulty technologies and arguments can turn customers upset and angry. Angry customers may post negative comments about organizations/brands online (Zhang et al. 2018). Ple and Caceres (2010) state that there are customers who accidentally engage in the destruction of value and their negative actions result in damage for the company. Fournier and Avery (2011) pointed out that negative feedback generated in customer communities will affect brand reputation.

5.3.3. Evaluations of the Findings

The findings of this research are consistent with the evidence available in the literature in relation to the advantages and challenges faced by companies when they engage customers in the value co-creation process. Alongside uncovering advantages, this research also identified the negative consequences of engaging customers in the value co-creation process to give a holistic view. The findings of this research will help businesses to assess their strategies towards customer engagement and help them in mitigating any challenges faced during the implementation of the value co-creation process. These research findings will enrich the existing knowledge available on the subject and add new knowledge especially from the perspective of the Pakistani textile industry.

5.4. The roles of modern technologies on value co-creation processes

5.4.1. Summary of the Findings

One of the objectives of this research was designed to identify the roles modern technology play in value co-creation activities. Thematic analysis of the primary data led to the identification of three key themes, namely reaching a wider range of consumers, digital marketing – electronic word of mouth, and enhanced customer support. As identified, with the help of technology, firms are able to cater and reach consumers which are out of their range in physical settings; it minimises the communication gap and helps customers to take

part in the value co-creation process. The usage of technology by firms, also help organisations to engage customers effectively and in real-time through different digital mediums. It has also helped them in reducing their marketing costs, as marketing through digital channels is cost-effective and customers can help a company through electronic word of mouth. Finally, better customer service is available for customers, in case if they have any service failure or any other issues. Technology helps firms in offering a better experience for their customers which in return motivates customers to engage more with the firms to co-create value. Figure 5.2 summarises the findings of this research.

FIGURE 5-2: THE ROLES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN VALUE CO-CREATION PROCESSES

Source: The Author

5.4.2. Discussions of the Findings

Modern technologies help companies to have access to a wider range of customers, generating more revenue for the company and helping a company to get more feedback to make its products/services better. It makes engagement easy with customers alongside digital marketing which saves cost for the company and also offers them better support when needed, as Nasir et al (2018), suggested that consumer feedbacks and product reviews are an important factor in brand image building and awareness.

The findings of this research state that technology plays a vital role in engaging customers in the value co-creation process. Brands that only operate in physical retail settings have limited

access in terms of interactions with their customers. With the help of technology, brands are able to sell their products to consumers globally and also makes it easier for them to incorporate their feedback into existing and new products/service launches. Buttner and Gortiz (2008) state that technological platforms have a wider range of the target market and potential consumer. As stated by Prabhakar (2010), with the help of different technological platforms brands can engage with consumers and reach them without spending too much on advertisements as social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter provide cost-effective ways of reaching millions of followers. The findings of this research emphasize that, through digital platforms, brands can reach wider and easily interact with their customers leading to value co-creation in terms of enhancement of products/services through active consumer engagement.

The findings of this research, similar to the findings of Bilal et al. (2014), indicate that technology has enabled users and organisations to get close to each other and offer mutual benefits at less cost, higher revenues and cost-effectiveness. Mckinsey (2020) conducted research on 72 brands including Hugo Boss, Ralph Lauren and found that the traffic and presence of people to the sites of these brands which utilised technological platforms had doubled over the years. By adoption of technology, companies can reach wider customers, listen to their needs and address their issues; it will also help companies in engaging customers in their value co-creation processes as the findings of the current suggests.

One of the findings of the research indicated that technology helps organisations to engage customers in real-time, and such engagement leads to value co-creation. Prior research by Ahmad et al. (2015) states that, with the help of technological platforms, clothing brands and fashion houses facilitate and authenticate their relationships in real-time with consumers. Elizabeth (2011) suggests that customers engage with brands through the use of technology on a personal level and it affects the industry in many ways by offering the platform to interact with customers and promote their products. Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015)'s investigation found a positive relationship between customer engagement of social networking and customer purchase behaviour. Their research emphasised that technological platforms including social media channels, help brands to communicate better with their consumers which in return affects their purchases in a positive way and let the company know about customers shopping trends. The findings of this research also suggest that technology helps the company in multiple channel integration, leading them to an effective

engagement of their customers in real-time. This also enhances the chance of customers participating in the value co-creation process.

This research identified that technology also plays significant roles in the adoption of digital marketing by companies through the internet, smartphones, social media, search engines, and other channels to influence the customer; which not only helps organisations in enhancing the goal of value co-creation but also saves costs and time. With the help of technology, customers are treated as co-creators and their voices are heard. King et al. (2014) stated that there is an agreement in the literature that word of mouth is powerful, the impact it generates is much higher than other types of marketing messages. Not only that there exists an interaction between a customer and the firm but interaction between customer to customer is possible with the help of technology and it has both negative and positive impacts on customer value co-creation, depending on customers' experience with firms.

Ather et al. (2018) found that there is a positive relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase behaviour, indicating social media can be utilised as a useful advertising instrument. Ahmad et al. (2015) state that there has been notable growth in the utilisation of social media by businesses in the fashion industry; for example, during 2009, Alexander McQueen's fashion show, Lady Gaga one tweet crashed the fashion show as many people clicked on the live stream (Michault, 2009). Ahmad et al. (2015) investigated the impacts of social media on the fashion industry and found there is a significant relationship; an increase of 1% in social media results in a growth of 20.6% in the fashion industry. Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015) state that social media is quite useful for marketers as a customer these days choose their preferred groups that make target marketing quite easier. This research also suggests that it is easier for brands these days to know which products are more popular among customers than others.

The findings of this research identified that technology if used appropriately, can immensely help companies to offer enhanced support for their customers, which in turn will lead to a better customer experience, loyalty, and higher engagement in value co-creation processes. Nowadays, customers require brands to assist them before buying a product as well as after the purchase for a certain time. Also, there is high pressure on brands to offer multichannel supports and a hassle-free shopping experience. According to Barhemmati and Ahmad (2015), some customers value price or quality of the good or services offered but there are

also customers who are attached to technological platforms and care how a company interacts and offer care to its customers virtually or physically.

Similarly, Mangold and Faulds (2009) found that consumers feel more engaged with products and brands when they are able to offer their feedback; therefore, many companies have set up programmes to enhance this engagement. Bilal et al (2014) highlight that companies that emphasize customer knowledge management should utilise technology such as social media and other digital networks to maximise their knowledge about customers, so a decision could be taken to support customers. In terms of support for customers, the online shopping experience can be provided to thousands of consumers in familiar and accessible settings (Buttner and Gortiz, 2008). The findings of this research uncovered the roles technology can play in terms of engaging customers in value co-creation in the Pakistani textile industry. The findings are consistent with the literature.

5.4.3. Evaluations of the Findings

The findings of this research suggest that technology has profound impacts on value co-creation activities as it helps the company to reach a wider range of customers and serve them efficiently, which is not possible in normal settings without the utilisation of technology. In the current marketplace, the survival of any retail business relies on technological adaptation. The findings of this research, as discussed above, are consistent with the broader consensus of the literature. Findings also add new insights to the literature by highlighting how the Pakistani textile industry is incorporating technologies for engaging customers in various business processes.

This research also highlighted the importance of modern technologies and various digital platforms to meet companies marketing goals. Various themes uncovered from the primary data validates the significance of findings for a successful business as these findings touch all the areas from a firm inside operations to reaching out and engaging with customers. This research has enriched the existing literature. However, these findings are based on qualitative research. As qualitative findings tend to have generalisability-related implications, it is recommended that the managers consider the potential weakness of the findings carefully prior to applying them in their business processes.

5.5. Conclusions

This chapter discussed and evaluated the findings which were presented in chapter four of this thesis. The majority of the findings of this research were consistent with the evidence available in the literature. As discussed, relationships of shopper's age and gender with their shopping frequency was consistent with the literature. However, unlike previous studies, this research identified no significant statistical associations between shoppers' income and their shopping frequency with their favourite brands. On the other hand, a positive and strong relationship was identified between customer engagement and value co-creation attitude. This finding is in line with the existing findings.

This research also highlighted the advantages and disadvantages of engaging customers in value co-creation processes. The findings provide a holistic view to the practitioners in the industry because previous research has either highlighted one aspect of value co-creation or solely focused on customers in the online context. The findings of this research indicated that engaging customers in the value co-creation process has more benefits for the company and it adds to the value co-creation process rather than leading towards value destruction if value co-creation activities are appropriately executed. This research also identified that modern technology plays a critical role in facilitating the engagement process which in return leads to value co-creation. The technology helps the company in communicating with its customers and also in products/service marketing, saving cost and helps in engaging with customers in the shortest time. It also helps firms to provide a better customer experience, manage customer relationship, and achieve customer loyalty.

6. CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to summarise the findings of this research as well as highlight how each research objectives was achieved. This chapter also deals with the theoretical, methodological and practical contribution of the findings of this study. Moreover, recommendations are also provided to the managers in the textile industry of Pakistan for the enhancement of customer engagement in value co-creation processes. Finally, limitations of this research are pointed alongside offering suggestions for future researchers for further extending the area of study.

6.2. Summary of the Research

Customer engagement in the process of product/service development is seen as one of the crucial business activities recently. This is because the market competition across all sectors is intensifying and organisations need to find new ways of outperforming competitors and satisfying customers. The textile sector of Pakistan plays a significant role in the economy of the country. The companies/brands operating in the sector has a large customer market and the application of the value co-creation concept can significantly enhance interaction between customers and service provider companies for increasing revenue generation, enhancing customer experience and customer loyalty. This was designed to assess the relationship between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitude as well as to identify the opportunities and challenges associated with involving customers in the value co-creation processes in the context of the textile sector of Pakistan.

In order to be able to recommend effective strategies for value co-creation through customer engagement, a total of four research objectives were developed in this research. The first objective was designed to measure the relationship between customer engagement and customer's value co-creation attitudes by applying a quantitative approach. The second and third objectives were designed to understand the advantages and challenges and the role technology plays while implementing value co-creation practices and engaging customers in the value co-creation process whilst the final objective was established to offer recommendations to partitioners in the textile industry of Pakistan on the basis of the research findings.

This research built on the service-dominant logic (SDL) theory of Vargo and Lusch (2004, 2008) and the service logic theory of (Gronos, 2008). SDL is one of the prominent theories that explain value co-creation between firms and customers by putting value at the centre of research attention (Vargo and Lusch, 2008). Liang (2017) states that value co-creation is the central idea of SDL, which requires an integration of resources sought through mutual exchanges and shared institutions, active participation of the customer in service creation. The research also followed the idea of value creation stated by Prahalad & Ramaswamy (2004a, 2004b) that the creation of value now results from a joint production process involving both the company and the customer. Additionally, Hollebeek et al. (2014) and Vivek et al. (2014) concepts of customer engagement were also incorporated in this study.

The research followed the pragmatic philosophy to generate meaningful results about the role of customer engagement in the value co-creation process, by developing both subjective and objective ideas, facts, principles, experiences and knowledge. The researcher utilised an abductive approach for this research to structuring the concept, developed views and reflect on these. Furthermore, a survey strategy was used to collect primary data from the customers and the firms operating in the textile industry. Mixed methods research design was used in this research to gain in-depth knowledge about the research topic through interviews, and also through questionnaires distribution.

For the analysis of the research data, SPSS was used. A total of 332 responses were identified as fit for analysis were selected for analysis. Research hypotheses were tested by applying Chi-square, One-way ANOVA, and correlation tests to examine the frequency and associations among variables. Statistical tests revealed significant relationships between shopper's age and shopping frequency and female shopping frequency was identified as significantly higher than that of their male counterparts. Further analysis also revealed that income level did not significantly impacted customers shopping frequencies. Finally, customer engagement was identified to be positively related to their value co-creation attitudes.

In order to have an in-depth understanding of value co-creation processes in the textile industry, qualitative research was also conducted by interviewing 11 managers in the Pakistani textile industry. The analysis revealed five key advantages of engaging customers

in value co-creation processes, namely meeting customers demand through product customisation and personalisation, developing better relationships with customers, innovation leading to competitive advantages, enhanced customer experience resulting in customer loyalty, and increased revenue collection. During the analysis, the researcher also found the challenges associated with engaging customers in value co-creation processes. They include reputation damage due to inconsistencies in products/services offered and value destruction as a consequence of negative feedback from customers. Furthermore, the researcher uncovered the roles of modern technologies in the value co-creation process. The technology was identified to immensely benefit the value co-creation processes by helping businesses to reach a wider range of audiences, providing digital marketing and electronic word of mouth opportunities, and offering enhanced support systems to customers.

The findings of this research, in general, are consistent with the literature evidence. For example, this research revealed that demographics play role in shoppers' shopping frequency in the textile industry. These findings are consistent with the findings of Pare and Pourazad (2016), White (1994), Brudsal and Lavik, (2008), Dholkia (1999), Baylock (2006), and Maden et al. (2015). Furthermore, this research also identified that customer engagement is positively associated with their value co-creation attitudes. This finding is consistent with the findings of Harrigan et al. (2020), Banyte and Dovalience (2014), and Auh et al. (2007). The concept of value co-creation and customer engagement has been widely studied in different contexts and industries; however, no empirical study was identified in the case of the Pakistani textile industry.

The findings of this research make both theoretical and practical contributions. The findings fill the existing knowledge gap by outlining consumers who are highly engaging with brands are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities. Besides, the attitude towards value co-creation varies depending on the gender of the participants; whilst females are more engaging with brands, males participate in value co-creation more often than females in the context of the Pakistan textile industry. The findings also make a contribution to the professional practice by suggesting businesses in the Pakistani textile industry should extensively focus on utilising the digital market environment (i.e., social media) to engage with customers as well as to allow them to participate in firms' value co-creation initiatives. Doing so will not only help them to reach a larger number of people, but they will also be

able to reduce their operational costs and innovate on a regular basis. The subsequent section of this chapter now details how the research aim and objectives were achieved.

6.3. Achieving Research Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research was to recommend strategies for enhancing the level of customer engagement in value co-creation processes in the textile industry of Pakistan. In order to achieve the aim of this research, four distinctive research objectives were designed. The first objective investigated the relationships between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes, the second objective explored the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation processes, and the third objective revealed the roles modern technologies play in engaging customers in value co-creation processes. Finally, after carefully considering the findings of the research as well as the findings of the prior studies available in the literature, strategic recommendations are proposed to the stakeholders of the Pakistani textile industry in Chapter 6.5. Prior to making recommendations and thereby demonstrating how the research aim was achieved, the section below details upon how each research objectives were achieved.

6.3.1. Objective One

To assess the impacts of customer engagement in their value co-creation attitudes in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

The first research objective intended to assess the impacts of customer engagement on their value co-creation attitudes in the textile industry of Pakistan. In order to do this, customer engagement and value co-creation were measured quantitatively by using established frameworks that are already available in the literature. After individually measuring various dimensions of both variables, scores for each variable were generated. In order to identify the impact of customer engagement in their value co-creation attitudes, Spearman correlation tests were conducted. The tests indicated a significant and large impact on customer engagement on their value co-creation attitude, meaning customers that actively engage with their favourite brands are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities.

A critical evaluation of this finding, as presented in chapter 5.2 of this thesis, confirmed that this finding of the research is consistent with the finding of similar prior studies. This finding, therefore, makes contributions to the body of knowledge by further strengthening the area of study by confirming a positive relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes in the precise context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

6.3.2. Objective Two

To evaluate the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process in the textile industry in Pakistan.

The second research objective was developed to identify the benefits customers bring to firms while they participate in the value co-creation processes. This objective also focused on determining the challenges encountered by companies when they engage customers in value co-creation processes. The analysis of the qualitative research data uncovered various advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes. As identified, such engagement can help to meet customer demands through product customisation and personalisation helps in developing better relations with customers, brings innovations that can provide competitive advantages, and provide better customer experience resulting in loyalty and higher revenues. On the other hand, identified challenges include the lack of consistencies of products/services affecting brand reputation and negative feedback through online channels resulting in value destruction. The findings make contributions by not only enriching the existing literature but also by providing guidance to practitioners in the industry.

6.3.3. Objective Three

To assess the roles of modern technologies in engaging customers in value co-creation processes in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

Objective three evaluated the importance of modern technologies for implementing value co-creation processes. In order to achieve this objective, interviews were conducted with managers in the textile industry in Pakistan. During the interviews, participants stated that technology plays a pivotal role in helping companies to engage customers in the value co-creation process. The researcher uncovered various themes through a thematic analysis of the primary research data. They conclude that modern technologies help in reaching a wider range of consumers, enable digital marketing generating electronic word of mouth, and

enhance customer support systems. The review of the literature conducted in chapter two of this thesis identified that no prior study was conducted in the textile industry of Pakistan to evaluate the role technologies play in implementing value co-creation processes. The findings of this research, hence, make contributions to the body of knowledge by adding new insights.

6.4. Contributions of the Research

The research findings make multiple theoretical and practical contributions. Below, some of the key contributions of this research are discussed:

6.4.1. Theoretical Contributions

This study makes four key theoretical contributions. Below, the key contributions are highlighted and discussed:

6.4.1.1. Identification of the impacts of demographic factors on customers' shopping behaviours

As identified by this research, shoppers shopping behaviours are impacted by their demographical factors such as age, gender and incomes. The findings of this research suggested that, on average, women shop more often than men whilst the younger customers tend to shop more often than the older ones. As no prior study was conducted precisely in the context of the Pakistan textile sector, this study bridges the knowledge gap and makes a contribution to the literature. These findings also make contributions to future researchers.

6.4.1.2. Identification of relationships between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes

Although a number of studies were conducted in different industries around the world to assess the statistical associations between consumer engagement and their value co-creation attitude's, no study was particularly conducted in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan. Prior studies identified positive and significant statistical associations between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes. The findings of this study also confirmed a positive and statistically significant association between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes, precisely in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan.

This finding makes a significant and original contribution to the literature by reconfirming the existing evidence and making the area of study further stronger.

6.4.1.3. Identification of advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes

Although the existing literature dealt with various antecedents and consequences of customers engagement (discussed in chapter 2), no study attempted to identify the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in the value co-creation process. The literature mainly emphasized providing a better customer experience to attain brand loyalty. This research, however, extended the scope of literature by adding new insights related to the advantages and challenges of engaging customers in value co-creation processes. The findings of this research suggest that involving customers in value co-creation processes can help to meet customer demands through product customisation and personalisation, helps in developing better relations with customers, brings innovations that can provide competitive advantages, and provide better customer experience resulting in loyalty and higher revenues. On the other hand, challenges identified by this research include the lack of consistencies of products/services affecting brand reputation and negative feedback through online channels resulting in value destruction. These findings of this research are unique and make significant contributions to the body of knowledge.

6.4.1.4. Identification of the role of modern technologies for engaging customers in value co-creation processes

Finally, this study also identified the roles modern technologies play in engaging customers in value co-creation processes. An extensive review of the literature indicated that no prior study was conducted in the Pakistani textile sector to identify how modern technologies and social media facilitate increased consumer engagement in value co-creation processes. The findings indicated that these technologies help in reaching a wider range of consumers, enable digital marketing generating electronic word of mouth, and enhance customer support systems. These findings are unique and add new insights to the body of knowledge.

6.4.2. Practical Contributions

This research also makes valuable contributions to the textile industry in Pakistan. The findings are based on primary data that was collected for the purpose of this research. Key practical contributions made by this research are presented in sections below.

6.4.2.1. Businesses must consider demographic factors whilst developing new marketing strategies

The primary findings of this research as well as the findings of several prior studies suggested that demographic factors of consumers significantly affect their shopping behaviours. Therefore, companies should analyse and consider the demographics of customers prior to developing new marketing strategies. Understanding the customer demographics can help firms in segmenting customers and locating their individual characteristics and needs. Besides, by considering the demographics of customers during the process of designing marketing campaigns, firms can effectively deliver the right message to the right individuals.

As the findings of this research identified, younger shoppers and women are likely to shop more frequently than older shoppers and men; therefore, companies should target these consumer segments while developing new marketing strategies in order to increase sales and revenues. The findings indicated that as people grow older, they tend to shop less from their favourite brands in the Pakistani textile sector. This research also suggests that women shop more than men as shopping is a gendered activity and women also tend to spend more time than searching items as shopping for clothes is more appealing to females. Although there was already established consensus in the literature regarding these, these findings make contributions to the practitioners by confirming this consensus precisely in the context of the textile industry in Pakistan. Based on the finding of this research, business managers in the Pakistani textile industry can develop marketing strategies that are more appealing, appropriate, and can lead to generating more sales. It is expected that these findings are generalisable across similar textile industries in developing countries.

6.4.2.2. Managers in the Pakistani textiles sector should focus on engaging customers in their business processes.

As discussed in the earlier chapter of this thesis, customers that engage with a company on a regular basis are more likely to participate in value co-creation activities than customers who do not actively engage with the company. Giving consumers increased access to the company and providing them with value co-creation opportunities will not only help firms to increase their sales and profits in the long term, but also firms can consistently understand consumer requirements and needs on a regular basis. Engaging consumers can also help firms to innovate product and services by collecting new ideas from consumers. When a company engages with consumers, it helps the brand to design more market-appropriate products, eventually helping it in building a good brand image and forming a stronger position in the local markets. When consumers are provided with the products of their need on a consistent basis, it also helps to build customer loyalty.

Based on the findings, businesses operating in the Pakistani textile sector should focus on facilitating customer engagement through online and offline channels, collecting customers feedback about product/services before and after product/service launch, connecting with customers on social media platforms, providing them omnichannel experience, and rewarding them for their loyalty whilst remaining cautious of possible implications of such engagements including consequential lack of consistencies in the quality of products and services and negative feedbacks arising due to not being able to adequately meet the specific requirements of individual customers. These findings provide guidance to managers in the Pakistani textile sector by providing them with pathways to increase revenues and profitability through higher customer participation in value co-creation activities. It is expected that this contribution is generalisable across the textile industry globally.

6.4.2.3. Companies should promote the use of technological channels within and across organisations as such channels are the most efficient ways of engaging customers in business processes

This research identified that modern technologies such as social media play a pivotal role in engaging customers in value co-creation processes. These technologies help in reaching a wider range of consumers, enable digital marketing generating electronic word of mouth, and enhance customer support systems. Therefore, the managers in the textile industry of Pakistan

should focus on offering better technological solutions to their customers, which will facilitate customers engagement with the brand and leading to value co-creation. Besides enriching the existing knowledge, these findings also make contributions to the practice by offering guidelines to the managers. By focusing on customer engagement through social media, companies can increase sales and profitability.

Modern technologies are able to provide real-time engagement opportunities to customers, and if effectively used, these technologies can play substantial roles in minimising communication gaps or miscommunication between firms and consumers. Firms are able to receive instant feedback by the utilisation of modern technologies. They can then make immediate changes in the business operations, eventually reducing further damage to the brand image. In the textile industry, a new trend of online retailing is becoming increasingly common. With the use of modern technologies, firms can make sales without having to invest in physical infrastructures, eventually reducing operational costs. Hence, textile companies should promote the use of technological channels so that they are not only able to engage with consumers more effectively but also are able to gain competitive advantages. This contribution is expected to be generalisable across the textile industry globally.

6.5. Recommendations

Co-creation is becoming increasingly popular across all industries as it not only allows customers to be able to buy products that they desire but also provides companies with great ideas that can lead to innovations. Co-creation activities empower customers and entangle them into companies' productive activities. The customer interaction with the company might not always stem from financial gains but their motivations may derive from other reasoning, such as simple feedback, recognition or the experience of the interaction may prove sufficient reward. So, businesses need to focus on the interactive process and co-creative experiences as these lies at the core of customer engagement. Companies should consider value co-creation as a source of innovation, generating new ideas, and learning from customers. Co-creation of value can be referred to as a form of innovation occurring not only in the activities sponsored by the companies but also in independent co-creation activities, comprising of individuals and communities voluntarily producing activities of value by utilising the platform provided by the company to support such activities. Companies can ask consumers to submit their

ideas for improvement in product/services, take part in creative activities to generate new ideas.

When customers experience a strong involvement in business processes (i.e., product development, service delivery, etc.), and given that the products and services meet the consumer requirements, this can lead to an enhanced level of customer loyalty to brands. Customer loyalty contributes towards the survival of a firm; in the short term, customers tend to buy more often from brands that they are loyal to, whilst, in the long term it helps brands tremendously by attracting new customer as a consequence of the advocacy and positive word of mouth generated by satisfied and loyal customers, eventually increasing the level of overall business sustainability and profitability. Thus, in order for companies to grow sustainably, it is recommended that they engage customers in their daily activities by introducing value co-creation initiatives.

However, if value co-creation activities are not conducted adequately, it can impact the organisation negatively, eventually destructing the brand image. For example, miss utilisation of resources can result in value co-destruction as excessive digital communications (i.e., emails and texts) can annoy customers because such communications can be perceived as invasive and annoying. On the other hand, customers too can be overly obsessed with a brand; they dominate the online community forums and annoys the company consistently asking about prices or new releases, which sometimes can lead to unintended aggression or cyberbullying. In order to maintain an adequate level of communications and thus to create a healthy business environment where brand and customers creatively engage and share their views for mutual benefits, it is recommended that firms in the Pakistani textile sector introduce digital apps where customers can customise their individual products and place orders. It is recommended that regular electronic surveys are conducted in order to gather the views and perceptions of the customers. Having an effective platform in place will not only make the participation of customers smoother but also minimize the impacts on firms by reducing the resources required to communicate with customers for engaging them in value co-creation processes.

Finally, social media, nowadays, are used by customers of all demographics. These channels have not only made communications with known parties (i.e., regular customers) easier but it has also opened opportunities for reaching out to potential customers. Effective management

of a brand across various social media platforms can result in countless fruitful benefits whilst mismanagement can be fatal for the future of the entire organisation. For example, incidents of service failures such as delayed delivery or the delivery of faulty products might lead to value co-destruction in the form of negative customer feedback on social media and online forums, eventually impacting the purchase decisions of other customers negatively and tarnishing the brand image as well as customer loyalty. Therefore, it is recommended that businesses in the Pakistani textile industry consider carefully both the usefulness of these platforms as well as the harms they can bring to their business.

6.6. Limitations

Prior to considering the findings of a study, it is crucial to understand the limitations of the findings. The findings of this study could have been impacted by the following limitations:

Electronic data collection

After considering the risks posed by COVID-19 to both the researcher and participants, the vast majority of the questionnaires were distributed through electronic channels. Although electronic data collection provides respondents with time and place convenience, the collected data, in some cases, can be affected by respondent bias.

Limited generalisability of the findings

Given that the research was conducted on the textile industry of Pakistan, the findings may not be generalisable globally. This is because, due to various environmental factors, consumers in different economies may act differently. Thus, the generalizability aspect of the findings must be considered carefully before applying them to a business environment.

Lack of prior studies in the Pakistani textile industry

The researcher conducted an extensive literature review, which revealed that no previous research was conducted on customer engagement and its impacts on their value co-creation attitudes in the textile industry in Pakistan. This may have prevented the researcher from designing a robust questionnaire and interview questions, eventually affecting the robustness of the findings.

Manual analysis of qualitative data

The researcher performed qualitative data analysis through a manual approach. There may have been some human errors during the analysis, affecting the research findings.

6.7. Further Research

Given that this research was conducted on companies within the Pakistani textile industry, future studies outside of Pakistan could extend the area of study. Future studies can also explore the roles of consumers in engaging with the company for value co-creation in online contexts only. Besides, a study examining the influence of social media on value co-creation activities could further extend this study. In this research, various variables that shape customer engagement towards a brand and their attitude towards value co-creation were identified. It will be useful to understand the mediating role of these drivers of customer brand engagement and value co-creation attitude in future studies. In terms of analysis of data, future studies could incorporate more statistical tests such as multiple regressions. Future researchers may also undertake a study on engaging in value co-creation in business-to-business or supplier-to-businesses contexts in the textile industry in Pakistan.

6.8. Conclusions

This research reflected upon the importance of engaging customers in the co-creation of value. This study assessed the impacts of customer engagement on their value co-creation attitude in the textile sector of Pakistan. The researcher adopted a mixed-method approach by utilising qualitative and quantitative methods to achieve the research aim. For qualitative research, interviews were conducted to have in-depth insights into the current value co-creation practices in the Pakistan textile industry. On the other hand, through a quantitative approach, the researcher examined the statistical relationship between customer engagement and value co-creation attitudes for drawing conclusions. The researcher utilised existing scales for measuring both research variables in the context of the Pakistani textile industry.

The findings of this research make significant contributions to the body of knowledge by highlighting the roles of customer demographics in determining the customers shopping behaviours as well as by identifying the relationship between customer engagement and their value co-creation attitudes in the Pakistani textile industry. This research also makes significant contributions to professional practice by providing clear guidelines on increasing customer engagement in the value co-creation process with the help of modern technologies.

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8. APPENDICES

8. APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Consent Form

Thank you for reading the information sheet. If you are happy to participate, then please complete and sign the form below. Please tick the boxes to confirm that you agree with each statement:

*Please Initial
box:*

I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.

I understand that my responses will be kept strictly confidential. I understand that my name will not be linked with any research material and will not be identified in the report or reports that result from the research.

I agree for this interview to be recorded. I understand that the recording made of this interview will be used only for the analysis and that extracts from the interview, from which I would not be personally identified, may be used in any conference presentation, report or journal article developed as a result of the research. I understand that no other use will be made of the recording without my written permission and that no one outside the research team will be allowed access to the original recording.

I agree that my anonymised data will not be kept for future research purposes such as publications related to this study after the completion of the study.

I agree to take part in this interview.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Syed Muhammad Ali Shah
Principal Investigator

Date

Signature

To be counter-signed and dated electronically for telephone interviews. Once this has been signed by all parties, the participant should receive a copy of the signed and dated participant consent form, and the participant information sheet.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2: Guiding Interview Questions

1. Have you heard about the concept of value co-creation?
2. How do you think value co-creation will benefit your company as well as customers?
3. Currently, how do you engage them in the process of value co-creation?
4. Why do you think engaging customers in the value creation process is beneficial?
5. How effective do you see digital technologies in engaging customers? What approaches, as a business, have you taken to engage customers in the value co-creation process?
6. What do you make of social media in engaging customers and helping manage the relationships? Is it not the most effective channel of communication? Any alternative methods of communication?
7. What sort of customers do you see are more interested in engaging with the company to help create value? Are customers with certain characteristics more likely to engage more in the value co-creation process?
8. What are the measures in place to ensure the successfulness of value co-creation programmes, and how do you mitigate challenges that occurred in the process?
9. What are the measures in place for the customer services team to address consumer needs and mitigate negative feedback?
10. Do you think a good customer experience leads to loyalty? open- tell us your experience –
11. How do you make sure that interactions with customers through technological platforms and franchises result in brand popularity?
12. How effective is the role of customer relationship management in terms of organisational efficiency and collecting consumer data?
13. Do you incorporate customers and employees' feedback before launching a product?
14. What support structure you have in place for customers to get involved in the innovation process?
15. How do you gather information from company employees for new products?
16. What do you think is the most valuable resource your company have?

Appendix 3: Sample Interview Response (Translated)

Participant No:

1. Have you heard about the concept of value co-creation?

Yes, I know, and I have heard about this concept of value co-creation in which information has been sought from the customers and mould the products or services according to consumer needs. I'm also of the view that this concept might not be applicable to all the industries, I am saying this because sometimes the customers are not very technical, and they expect their company to create something which addresses customer's demand.

2. How do you think value co-creation will benefit your company as well as customers?

If I talk about our company it is working on two fronts B2B and B2C. In B to B the value co-creation is highly effective, and we are working daily. If I may talk about business to customer section especially in the clothing brands it is also very effective, and we are practising It. If I may talk about our company, we get feedback from our customers through engagement about the quality and designs of our product, the services they receive from us through our offline and online channels. It also enables us to share information about our products easily and quickly as they become part of our community. It is also beneficial for our customers because it helps them to get customised products if they want or they can get the products and services in which they played some sort of role.

3. Currently, how do you engage them in the process of value co-creation?

Before engaging customers in the value co-creation, we have over expert panel we discuss things and what are the benefits and how much cost is over there and if it's a win situation then we fully go for it. Getting customer feedback about the product is very important customers usually tell us if the product is very good or very bad and mostly, we come to know this through our retail channels and on social media channels. Customers also inform us that if the design of these years was rubbish or they were brilliant, so this is important information which helps us to plan for next season.

4. Why do you think engaging customers in the value co-creation process is beneficial?

It is beneficial for the company to involve customers in company processes as I must say that the customer is always the King and their feedback is of high importance for the company. Companies working in the textile sector can't achieve competitive advantages and produce the desired products and services without involving customers by getting their feedback before launches or after launches. It helps a brand to know its audience their demands and a company can improve and set its direction right which will also help to generate higher revenues and loyal customers.

5. How effective do you see digital technologies in engaging customers? What approaches, as a business, have you taken to engage customers in the value co-creation process?

There has been a major shift to e-commerce in Pakistan over the last few years. More people have started to use digital medium nowadays most of the conversions or engagement is happening through digital mediums and yes, it is very very effective in terms of brand conversions, engagement or awareness. I must say the way of engaging also changes over time. If you talk about the effectiveness of digital marketing or engagement. As of today, if I talk about 80% or not even 90% of the marketing to the customer is being done through digital tools all the marketing promotions. Even the billboards and the TV's they're on the lesser sides than the social media and other platforms we use. Through our digital platform and support systems, we reach larger audiences for interaction, getting their viewpoints and it enhances our company operation and we offer enhanced support to our customers.

6. What do you make of social media in engaging customers and helping manage the relationships? Is it not the most effective channel of communication? Any alternative methods of communication?

As of today, most of our marketing campaigns run online through social media, If I take you back like 5 or 10 years the role of social media would have been only 10%. The role of print and electronic media was much higher than today. At present most of our promotions are done through social media. If I talk about communication social media is one of the channels and one of the most effective channels a brand would use, through social media you can

directly interact with the customers. It could be through Facebook, Instagram, Twitter or Tiktok, you are coordinating with your customers through these mediums but at the same time that is not the only mode of communication. Our brand also uses SMS Web push content, newsletters they are also effective, but the social medium communication is very very high and it's a good communication channel. Every Retail industry is very aggressive on social media and it plays a very big role in selling, designs are easy to showcase through apps – and mostly customer sees online and visit our brick-and-mortar stores.

7. What sort of customers do you see are more interested in engaging with the company to help create value? Are customers with certain characteristics more likely to engage more in the value co-creation process?

There is a wide range of customers, at present times price war is going on in the market. Many of the consumers focus on good quality and reasonable price. From a consumer perspective hardly 10 per cent or 15 per cent of consumers engage and interact with their brands regularly. Some people give feedback about the company who had a problem with their product. We also have witnessed that the engaged customers also belong to our TG, we know this because there are the ones whom we are selling for quite some time. We target that audience with our ads etc and most of the impact is coming from that target group. Usually, those customers engage with our brand who are our regular customers, but we have also seen other customers who just want to experience before they start engaging with us.

8. What are the measures in place to ensure the successfulness of value co-creation programmes, and how do you mitigate challenges that occurred in the process?

For an effective engagement let's say if you use your regular methods like posting ads on your social media pages etc and if we haven't been successful in that so these days you know vloggers or fashion vloggers and influencers, you partner with these and what happens is these influencers they have a niche, who closely follow them, and their engagement is very high. Generally, the clothing brands hire influencers and celebrities to run campaigns and through these campaigns, the companies try to engage their customers and get their feedback as long as the company provides customers good value for their money and they run successful social media campaigns involving customers with the brands become easy for the company. So, in my point of view if you do everything right but your price is not at the

customer's acceptable level then this might harm your value creation programme. Sometimes we have experienced if a customer receives some service issue, they are not hesitant at all to say negative things about the brand on our social media pages.

9. What are the measures in place for the customer services team to address consumer needs and mitigate negative feedback?

There is always bashing on social media and besides that our service team continuously monitor any feedback received and take corrective actions to fix any issues at our end. We have our pages where we have already posted frequently asked questions so the customers can get guidance from there. The service team has a key role and brands takes it very seriously, in the retail industry if a customer raises some issue and the company does not address its customer concern, it has negative consequences for the company. If we do the consumer survey mostly the consumer buys some expensive products, they are more willing to give their feedback than a person who has bought a cheaper thing. But on the other side, if a company does not listen to the customer who has bought a lower-priced product, they get annoyed. If the customer issues are addressed on time or in a certain time frame, it will lead to customer loyalty and positive word of mouth for the company. We try to resolve customer issues as much as we can, firstly what we investigate the claimed customer is making is genuine we try to solve it and ask customers to post that their issue is being resolved.

10. Do you think a good customer experience leads to loyalty? open- tell us your experience –

Of course, it does, customer experience including their shopping experience plays an important role in building a positive brand image and customer loyalty. If I give an example of our brand we have our websites we have our social media pages and we got our retail stores in which we have good ambience and pleasant staff who or willing to help their customers and they are trained to provide consumers with a positive feeling while they are shopping. And also, our staff are knowledgeable even they market our future products launches and inform our customers about incoming products, so it keeps our customers engaged with our brand. If I talk about our company, we are already an established brand and like others, we do have a following. Repeat purchases are always done by loyal customers if a customer is coming to you and you giving them value for money and your brand has a standing too. If you meet customer expectation, offer them a seamless

experience they come back to the company. The more a customer is loyal the most he is engaged with the brand.

11. How do you make sure that interactions with customers through technological platforms and franchises result in brand popularity?

Our Ideas Gold Ahmed service section is very capable and active. If a customer has any issue we try to address and resolve those issues within the time frame. We follow the basic norms like you meet and greet customer, treat them well we follow all the protocols like if they visit our franchise or our website, we make sure that from the very first touchpoint to the last touchpoint we give them a wow experience, we try to delight customers and give them positive shopping experience and if that happens, the result is a positive word of mouth generated by the customer.

12. How effective is the role of customer relationship management in terms of organizational efficiency and collecting consumer data?

I would say it's quite important and we keep a close eye on it. We gather all the shopping frequencies and different age brackets data and discuss these and plan for the future. CRM is very important if you are doing everything right but if it's not generating the desired results it means you are not building your relationships properly. If there is a disconnect in the relationships that's a disaster, in terms of effectiveness its very crucial internally and externally.

13. Do you incorporate customers and employees' feedback before launching a product?

Ultimately all our products and services are based on customer's feedback. Even from our stores, we get a day-to-day feedback from the customers visiting our retail stores. We gather all the feedback from different touchpoints yearly and quarterly and discuss. Our R&D team is involved in this of course. In terms of implementing customers feedback, let's see this running summer campaign, will be based on our last season findings, customers provide feedback on products designs, quality and price. The feedback collected from the previous season will be implemented in this one. The feedback we are receiving now we will implement it later this is how we evolve.

14. What support structure you have in place for customers to get involved in the innovation process?

We have different tools for this, we have our surveys going on and most of the time we have third parties who are doing this on our behalf. They have a set of questionnaires they get fill these from the customers, and It comes back to us and accordingly it becomes part of our innovation. On the other hand, we have our trained sale representative in our franchisees it's their job to get information from the customers and pass on to the R&D.

15. How do you gather information from company employees for new products?

The company relevant employees are involved, our R& D, a pool of designers we have, and our marketing teams give their feedback too. We encourage our employees to be open and share their ideas. Our employees visit market exhibitions even go abroad, attend different fashion shows, study different cultures and do our research development.

16. What do you think is the most valuable resource your company have?

Anything for our company is about customers inside out. Customer -infrastructure plus employees. If we talk about addressing customer needs a company must have resources so for that have Our employee and infrastructure – we assume this is valuable. Utilise the resources and employees to satisfy customers.

Appendix 4: Questionnaires

2/21/2021

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

Thank you for taking the time to read the participant information. You are being invited to participate in a research study titled Value co-creation Using Ecosystem Approach in Textile Sector of Pakistan. This study is being done by Syed Muhammad Ali Shah, a DBA researcher of the University of the West of Scotland School of Business

The purpose of this research study is to examine the key impact factors on the effective implementation of value co-creation between firms and customers in the textile industry of Pakistan and will take you approximately less than thirty minutes to complete. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You do not have to answer any questions you do not want to.

To the best of my knowledge, I believe there is no known risks associated with participating in this research study. All measures are taken so as to make sure your participation in this study will remain confidential and only anonymised data will be used for the purpose of any publication. This is secured through the technology SurveyMonkey.com uses to collect and store data, which does not divulge personal information such as your name, email and IP address.

If you are happy to proceed, please choose agree to move the questions A copy of this consent form along with the participant information as well as your answers to the questionnaire will be emailed to you once this is completed. Clicking on the "Agree" button indicates that

- You have read the above information
- You voluntarily agree to participate
- You are 18 years of age or older

- Agree
 Disagree

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1/12

2/21/2021

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

1. Age

Mark only one oval.

- 18-24
 25-34
 35-44
 45-54
 55-64
 65+

2. Gender

Mark only one oval.

- Female
 Male
 Prefer not to say

3. Profession

Mark only one oval.

- Writer/Journalist
- Administration
- Academia
- Fashion designer
- IT Industry
- Lawyer
- Other: _____

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2/21/2021

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile

4. Monthly Income (In PKR)

Mark only one oval.

- Below 20,000
- 20,000-40,000
- 40,000- 70,000
- 70,000-100,000
- 100,000& above
- Prefer not to say

5. Education

Mark only one oval.

- School
- College
- Bachelors
- Masters and above
- No formal education

-
6. Please choose your favourite brand (If your favourite brand is not in the list, kindly select other and write your favourite brand name) .

Mark only one oval.

- Khaadi
- Bareeze
- Junaid Jamshed
- Gul Ahmed
- Sapphire
- Other: _____

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Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

7. How often do you shop with your favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Every week
- Every month
- Once in three months
- Every year or less

8. I like to interact with my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9. I like to interact with my favourite brand for information seeking

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

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2/21/2021

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

10. I like to interact with other customers to get information regarding products and services (e.g making comments on Instagram, Facebook pages and websites).

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

11. I like to interact with my favourite brand to share information

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

12. I like to share knowledge with my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

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2/21/2021

Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation: A case of Textile Industry in Pakistan

13. I like to involve in dialogue for knowledge sharing when my favourite brand takes initiatives

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

-
14. I am more attracted to involve in dialogue for sharing knowledge with my favourite brand's service employees who are uniformed

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

15. I like to respond positively when my favourite brand seeks my suggestions to improve its products and services

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

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16. I like to respond positively when my favourite brand get my opinion about the design of products

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

-
17. I like to respond positively when my favourite brand involve me in the development of products

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

18. I like to respond positively when my favourite brand take initiative to get my recommendations for innovation in its products

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

19. Anything related to my favourite brand grabs my attention

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

20. I pay a lot of attention to anything about my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

21. I get involved to learn more about my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

22. While using brand products I think about my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

23. I think about my favourite brand a lot when I use its products

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

24. Using my favourite brand products, it stimulates my interest to learn more about the brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

25. I feel very positive when I use my favourite brand products

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

26. Using products from my favourite brand makes me happy

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

27. I feel good when I use products of my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

28. I feel proud to use products of my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

29. I spend a lot of time with my favourite brand in comparison to other similar brands

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

30. Whenever i need any clothing products, I usually buy from my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

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31. I enjoy buying clothing products from my favourite brand

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Appendix 5: Ethical Approval

09/07/2019

Dear Syed Muhammad Ali Shah,

Your application 8273: Value Co-Creation using Ecosystem approach in Textile sector of Pakistan, submission 6843, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean